

Harnessing AI and Data-Intensive Technologies

Deliverable 2.2: Survey of Compliance Methods and Tools

Project acronym	HARNES S
Project title	Harnessing AI and Data-Intensive Technologies
Project DOI	https://doi.org/10.3030/101169409
Project duration	01.01.2025 – 31.12.2028
Project website	https://harness-network.eu/
Deliverable no.	D2.2
Doc. title	Survey of Compliance Methods and Tools
Doc. authors	Célestine Lecat, Meem Manab, Fabian Linde, Victoria Wiegand, Sheyla Leyva Sánchez, Marlin Kisia
Doc. contributors	n.a.
Doc. reviewers	Prof. Monica Palmirani, Dr. Harshvardhan Pandit
Doc. work package	WP2
Doc. nature	R – Document, report
Doc. dissemination	PU – Public
Doc. DOI	10.5281/zenodo.19252086
Doc. date	26/03/2026

Document History

Version	Date	Contributor	Description
1	2025.12.18	Célestine Lecat (UNIBO), Meem Manab (UPM), Fabian Linde (UPM)	First version of the deliverable's scope and methodology
2	2026.01.14	Célestine Lecat (UNIBO), Meem Manab (UPM), Fabian Linde (UPM), Victoria Wiegand (TCD), Sheyla Leyva Sánchez (UPM), Marlin Kisia (UGent)	Multivocal Literature Review
3	2026.03.06	Dr. Harshvardhan J. Pandit (TCD)	Preliminary review
4	2026.03.10	Célestine Lecat (UNIBO), Meem Manab (UPM), Fabian Linde (UPM), Victoria Wiegand (TCD), Sheyla Leyva Sánchez (UPM), Marlin Kisia (UGent)	Polished draft ready for the official final review
5	2026.03.17	Pof. Monica Palmirani (UNIBO)	Final review by Prof. Monica Palmirani
6	2026.03.24	Célestine Lecat (UNIBO), Meem Manab (UPM), Fabian Linde (UPM), Victoria Wiegand (TCD), Sheyla Leyva Sánchez (UPM), Marlin Kisia (UGent)	Implementation of the comments proposed by Prof. Monica Palmirani
7	2026.03.25	Dr. Harshvardhan J. Pandit (TCD)	Final review by Dr. Harshvardhan J. Pandit
8	2026.03.26	Célestine Lecat (UNIBO), Meem Manab (UPM), Fabian Linde (UPM), Victoria Wiegand (TCD), Sheyla Leyva Sánchez (UPM), Marlin Kisia (UGent)	Submission of the final reviewed version to UPM

Acronyms

Acronym	Definition
AIA	Artificial Intelligence Act
ASP	Answer Set Programming
ATL	ATLAS Transformation Language
BPMN	Business Process Model and Notation
BSI	British Standards Institution
CCPA	California Consumer Privacy Act
CEN	European Committee for Standardisation
CENELEC	European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardisation
CLO	Core Legal Ontology
CLSum	Common Law Court Judgment Summarisation
CNIL	French National Commission on Informatics and Liberty

D2.2 Survey of Compliance Methods and Tools

CRF	Conditional Random Fields
CTL	Computation Tree Logic
CUAD	Contract Understanding Atticus Dataset
DC	Doctoral Candidate
DCAT	Data Catalogue vocabulary
DCU	Dublin City University
DeLP	Defeasible Logic Programming
DFD	Data Flow Diagram
DGA	Data Governance Act
DIN	German Institute of Standardisation
DKE	German Commission for Electrotechnical, Electronic, and Information Technologies
DLTL	Dynamic Linear Time Temporal Logic
DMN	Decision Model and Notation
DOLCE	Descriptive Ontology for Linguistic and Cognitive Engineering
DPA	Data Protection Authority
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
DPO	Data Protection Officer
ECLI	European Case Law Identifier
EDPB	European Data Protection Board
EEA	European Economic Area
ELI	European Legislation Identifier
EMF	Eclipse Modeling Framework
EO	Executive Order
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
FCA	UK Financial Conduct Authority
FERPA	Family Educational Rights and Privacy Act
FOLaw	Functional Ontology for Law
FRIA	Fundamental Rights Impact Assessment
HTML	Hypertext Markup Language
GenAI	Generative Artificial Intelligence
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HIPAA	Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
ISO	International Organisation for Standardisation
JTC21	CEN and CENELEC Joint Technical Committee 21
KNAW	Koninklijke Nederlandse Akademie van Wetenschappen
LDS	Legal Document Summarisation
LGPD	Brazilian General Personal Data Protection Law
LKIF	Legal Knowledge Interchange Format
LLM	Large Language Models
LTL	Linear Temporal Logic
MCDA	Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis
MDE	Model-Driven Engineering
ML	Machine learning
MLR	Multivocal Literature Review
MOF	Meta Object Facility

D2.2 Survey of Compliance Methods and Tools

MRU	Mykolo Romerio Universitetas
NER	Named Entity Recognition
NIST	U.S. National Institute of Standards and Technology
NLP	Natural Language Processing
NRV	Normative Requirements Vocabulary
OCL	Object Constraint Language
ODRL	Open Digital Rights Language
OWL	Web Ontology Language
PET	Privacy-enhancing technologies
PIA	Privacy Impact Assessment
QVT	Query/View/Transformation
RAG	Retrieval-augmented generation
RDF	Resource Description Framework
ROPA	Register of Processing Activities
SCC	Standard Contractual Clause
SEC	US Security and Exchange Commission
SHACL	Shapes Constraint Language
SME	Small-medium enterprises
SMT	Satisfiability Modulo Theories
SPARQL	SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language
STM	Structural Topic Model
SWRL	Semantic Web Rule Language
TCD	The Provost, Fellows, Foundation Scholars & the other members of Board, of the College of the Holy & undivided Trinity of Queen Elizabeth near Dublin
UFO	Unified Foundational Ontology
UGent	Universiteit Gent
UML	Unified Modeling Language
UNIBO	Alma Mater Studiorum - Università di Bologna
UPM	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
URN	Uniform Resource Name
UT	Universiteit Twente
VUB	Vrije Universiteit Brussel
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
XAI	Explainable Artificial Intelligence

TABLE OF CONTENT

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	8
1 INTRODUCTION	9
1.1 Goal	9
1.2 Scope	9
1.2.1 Legal scope	10
1.2.2 Scope of tools and methods	10
1.3 Importance of Compliance in Legal Systems	11
1.4 Challenges in Legal Compliance Verification and Validation	13
2 METHODOLOGY	16
2.1 Multivocal Literature Review (MLR)	16
2.2 Data collection method	16
3 THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS	20
3.1 Legal Norms and Their Formalization	20
3.2 Deontic Logic and Defeasible Logic	21
3.2.1 Deontic Logic	21
3.2.1 Defeasible Logic	22
3.3 Regulatory Frameworks and Compliance Mechanisms	22
3.3.1 European Legislation	24
3.3.2 European Harmonised Standards	26
3.3.3 Standards and Certifications	27
3.3.4 Guidelines and Codes of Practice	28
3.4 Impact Assessments	28
4 ASSESSMENT AND COMPLIANCE CHECKING APPROACHES	31
4.1 Manual Review and Auditing	31
4.2 Rule-based compliance checking	32
4.3 Model-driven approaches	34
4.4 Normative reasoning and logic-based methods	37
4.5 Semantic Web Technologies	40
4.5.1 General Semantic Web standards:	41

D2.2 Survey of Compliance Methods and Tools

4.5.2 The Semantic Web for law	43
4.6 Ontologies and Knowledge Representation	44
4.6.1 Classifying ontologies.....	45
4.6.2 Foundational or upper-level ontologies	46
4.6.3 Core ontologies	47
4.6.4 “Lightweight” ontologies	48
4.6.5 Domain ontologies	49
4.6.6 Legal Knowledge Graphs.....	51
5 AUTOMATED AND AI-BASED METHODOLOGIES.....	52
5.1 Use of AI in Extraction, Assessment and Checking Compliance	52
5.2 Natural Language Processing for Legal Texts.....	53
5.2.1 Legal Document Summarisation	53
5.2.2 Named Entity Recognition	54
5.2.3 Text Mining and Legal Information Retrieval	54
5.2.4 Generative AI, Large Language Models and Hybrid AI	56
5.2.5 Neuro-symbolic and Hybrid Approach.....	57
5.3 (Non-NLP) Machine Learning Approaches in Compliance	58
6 CHALLENGES AND LIMITATIONS	60
6.1 Ambiguity and Vagueness in Legal Texts	60
6.2 Dynamic and Evolving Regulations	60
6.3 Human Accountability versus Automation	61
6.4 Ethical Considerations.....	62
6.5 Digital Sovereignty	64
7 EVALUATION METRICS AND PERFORMANCE.....	66
7.1 Accuracy and Precision of Compliance Tools.....	66
7.2 Scalability and Efficiency	67
7.3 Explainability and Transparency	68
7.4 Risk Assessment and Prioritisation	68
7.5 Adaptability and Customisation.....	69
7.6 Interoperability of Compliance Tool Outputs	70
8 CASE STUDIES AND APPLICATIONS	71
8.1 GDPR: The CNIL Privacy Impact Assessment (PIA) as a Structured Compliance Workflow	71

D2.2 Survey of Compliance Methods and Tools

8.2 AI Act: “Is My AI System High-Risk?”—Semantic Tool for Determining High-Risk AI Systems - Golpayegani et al.	72
DECLARATION OF USE OF AI-ASSISTED TECHNOLOGIES	76
REFERENCES	77
APPENDICES	98
Appendix A: Tools and Software for Legal Compliance	98
1. Rule-based tools and methods.....	98
2. Model-based tools and methods	100
3. Normative reasoning tools and methods.....	103
4. Semantic Web tools and methods	106
5. Ontologies and knowledge representations.....	110
6. NLP tools and methods	116
7. Legal Document Summarization tools and methods.....	117
8. NER tools and methods.....	118
9. Text Mining and Legal Information Retrieval tools and methods	120
10. Generative AI tools and methods.....	123
11. Machine Learning tools and methods.....	126

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

WP2 "Methods and Tools for Compliance with AI and Data Regulations" is concerned with the alignment of legal requirements and obligations with AI and data technologies. The aim of this deliverable is to provide an overview of existing and prospective categories of compliance-checking methods and tools based in literature and real-world applications.

The specific scope of the deliverable is limited to a set of EU AI and data regulations, namely the GDPR, AI ACT, Data Governance Act, Data Act and Interoperable Europe Act. Additionally, this deliverable describes some of the limitations of said categories, along with metrics and considerations to be used when evaluating them.

Its broader purpose is to provide an overview on technical solutions that could support or replace manual compliance checking, which is a strenuous task when facing a complex and evolving legal framework, and has been the subject of recent discourses and legislative efforts such as the Digital Omnibus. To this end, the DCs conducted a multivocal literature review on tools and methods that can be leveraged, or that are explicitly designed, to check compliance with EU AI and data regulations.

The review can be divided into three main parts. The first part is descriptive, it lays down the theoretical background of the EU regulatory and automated compliance, before defining the main tool and method categories, with examples found in the literature. The second part analyses the challenges faced when checking compliance and the limitations of current tools and methods, proposes criteria for their evaluation, and examines two specific tools as case studies.

The deliverable also provides a summary overview of tools and methods identified during the review in its annex. This Deliverable will be of assistance for further work on other activities in WP2, and will also be of relevance to tasks and deliverables within WP1 "Analysis of AI and Data Regulatory Framework" and WP3 "Application in Specific Domains". WP1 contains, inter alia, two deliverables (D1.4 and D1.5 "Legal Knowledge Formalization") that will build on the overview provided by this document, as their aim is to create formal ontologies aligned with existing legal ontologies, specifications and standards, to serve as a common shared model for creating methods and tools for compliance.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Goal

Compliance is defined in common use as obeying a particular law or rule, which translates into fulfilling a set of official requirements (Merriam-Webster dictionary). By extension, compliance checking is the act of verifying that a specific action, service, product, design, document or process respects the regulatory constraints – permissions, prohibitions and obligations – laid out by a law or provision (Salama & El-Gohary, 2012). Compliance checking is not simply concerned with adherence to laws at a certain point in time. It also encompasses feedback on the rules that have been violated, upstream assessment of technologies and processes under development, continuous assessment of already-deployed processes, and anticipation of future violations by entities that are currently compliant (Ly et al., 2015). Compliance is also used to adhere to technical standard specifications (e.g. ISO standard 42001¹).

There is a general trend toward the digitalization and formalization of law, with legal norms increasingly being encoded into machine-interpretable forms (Witt et al., 2024). Simultaneously, the European Union has adopted a growing number of legislative measures related to AI and data, which is itself subject to ongoing revision and adaptation, notably in the context of the Digital Omnibus proposal (COM(2025) XXX final) (European Commission, 2025). Manual compliance checking against this evolving legal framework is particularly demanding, as these regulations are complex, dense, and often interdependent. Compliance obligations affect a wide range of stakeholders, including public sector bodies, private companies of varying sizes, and data subjects. For these reasons, traditional compliance checking methods are increasingly supplanted by technology-driven approaches for the sake of efficiency and accuracy (Amantea et al., 2026; Novelli et al., 2023; Quaranta et al., 2025). Despite these challenges, there is currently no comprehensive review of compliance-checking tools and methods in general, nor of tools and methods specifically suited to assess compliance with EU AI and data regulations.

For this reason, we aim to produce a multivocal review of the literature (MLR) on tools and methods that can be leveraged, or that are explicitly designed, to check compliance with EU AI and data regulations. The objective of this review is to improve understanding of the current landscape of methods and tools developed for ensuring compliance with AI and data regulations, including their strengths and limitations, as well as the considerations needed when choosing and using them.

We utilised the following research questions to define the goal of the review:

- **RQ1:** What categories of compliance-checking methods and tools, both current and prospective, can be found in the existing literature?
- **RQ2:** What are the limitations of existing categories of compliance-checking tools and methods?
- **RQ3:** What metrics and considerations can be used to evaluate compliance-checking tools and methods?

1.2 Scope

¹ <https://www.iso.org/standard/42001>

1.2.1 Legal scope

The legal scope of this review covers legislation on AI and data, adopted by the European Union. Considering the time at our disposal, we had to select a set of regulations that would be manageable for the six DCs involved. The two main criteria for choosing the regulations were that (1) they should be in force, and (2) they should directly concern AI or data. We wished to study a set of regulations that would broadly encompass the lifecycle of data in digital systems. This is why we included the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (Regulation (EU) 2016/679) (European Parliament & Council of the European Union, 2016) and the Artificial Intelligence Act (AI Act or AIA) (Regulation (EU) 2024/1689) (European Parliament & Council of the European Union, 2024), which are key regulations for personal data and artificial intelligence, respectively. We also selected the Data Act (Regulation (EU) 2023/2854) (European Parliament & Council of the European Union, 2023), focused on data access and portability, and the Data Governance Act (DGA) (Regulation (EU) 2022/868) (European Parliament & Council of the European Union, 2022), concerned with trusted data sharing and reuse. On top of regulating data provision and management, the Data Act and Data Governance Act are foundational for other laws such as the European Health Data Space. Last, we included the Interoperable Europe Act (Regulation (EU) 2024/903) (European Parliament & Council of the European Union, 2024), because our approach focused, among other things, on the interoperability of systems and processes, which is also a key consideration in compliance-checking tools and methods.

Some regulations were excluded when they were more sectoral or competition-focused, such as platform regulations – the Digital Services Act (Regulation (EU) 2022/2065) (European Parliament & Council of the European Union, 2022b), the Digital Markets Act (Regulation (EU) 2022/1925) (European Parliament & Council of the European Union, 2022c), and the P2B Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2019/1150) (European Parliament & Council of the European Union, 2019a) – or regulations primarily concerned with security, competition, intellectual property, or contract law, such as the Cybersecurity Act (Regulation (EU) 2019/881) (European Parliament & Council of the European Union, 2019b), the European Digital Identity Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2024/1183) (European Parliament & Council of the European Union, 2024c), the CDSM Directive (Directive (EU) 2019/790) (European Parliament & Council of the European Union, 2019c), and the InfoSoc Directive (Directive 2001/29/EC) (European Parliament & Council of the European Union, 2001), inter alia. Other regulations, such as the European Health Data Space Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2025/327) (European Parliament & Council of the European Union, 2025), were excluded because they concerned specific sectorial implementations.

1.2.2 Scope of tools and methods

The goal of this review is not to be comprehensive, but it nonetheless aims to provide an overview of the different existing solutions to assist compliance checking. This includes full-fledged technical tools, as well as "softer" tools and methods, like frameworks or decision-tree compliance checkers, that can be applied in combination with other means. Tools and methods are defined as follow:

- Tool: a digital artifact that is the product of human conception and that can be directly used to check compliance, either independently or in combination with other tools and methods. A compliance-checking tool can be automated or semi-automated.
- Method: a theoretical procedure or technique that can indirectly help in achieving or checking compliance. Some methods can be coupled with compliance-checking tools; however, the methods themselves are not automated and must be followed or implemented by humans.

Some systematic literature reviews have been published on tools for compliance checking against standards and regulations for software processes (Castellanos Ardila et al., 2022; Sovrano et al., 2025a), and on monitoring the compliance of business processes against internal and external regulations (Haarmann et al., 2021), but literature reviews specific to tools for checking compliance with EU AI and Data regulations are more scarce. The scope of this multivocal literature review is not restricted to tools and methods that are specifically designed for checking compliance with EU regulations, and will include tools and methods that can be used to assist or check compliance with a broader range of norms, such as standards and internal business process management regulations.

All the tools and methods encountered in the MLR corpus were then included from the review based on the following criteria:

- Tools and methods must provide a solution for directly or indirectly helping with compliance checking. This includes identifying relevant and applicable laws and requirements, identifying real-world facts to be checked, and/or checking these facts against these requirements.
- The relevant and applicable laws and requirements must be part of the selected EU AI and data regulations: the GDPR, the AI Act, the Data Act, the Data Governance Act, and the Interoperable Europe Act.

1.3 Importance of Compliance in Legal Systems

The European Union is undergoing a true regulatory expansion in the scope of AI and data, increasing the accountability and liability of organisations and companies concerned with handling data and AI technologies. The GDPR, AI Act, Data Act and Data Governance Act support the strategy “A Europe fit for the digital age²” (previously the European Digital Strategy) and the European Strategy for Data³, aimed at building a single market for data and trustworthy AI in Europe. They are framed around the protection of core values like transparency, privacy, data access and sharing, trust, fairness and innovation. But these values are not the only incentive to comply with these new regulations, which impose strict fines on non-compliers.

For instance, violators of Article 5 prohibitions of the AI Act may be fined up to €35 million, or up to 7 % of its total worldwide annual turnover of the preceding financial year if they are an undertaking (AIA Article 99(3)). Violators of the GDPR may be fined up to €20 million, or up to 4% of

² https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/europe-fit-digital-age_en

³ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/strategy-data>

the annual worldwide turnover (GDPR Article 83(5)). On May 2nd 2025, the Irish DPA (called the Data protection commission, or DPC) has fined TikTok €530 million due to the unlawful transfer and storage of personal data from users in the European Economic Area on Chinese servers⁴. These reasons underline the importance of compliance with EU AI and data regulations. But achieving compliance, or even simply checking compliance can be a time- and energy-consuming task because of its complexity.

Compliance has to be distinguished from assessment and risk analysis. Compliance is about ensuring that an organization's actions and processes meet required rules set by external authorities or internal governance. However, as described in section 3.3, assessment is one of the four levels of compliance. Assessments can be mandated by declarative rules that describe how to implement compliance in a specific domain, entity, or context. They often produce a report or checklist as an evidence of compliance. Risk analysis is an ex-ante process that more specifically focuses on identifying potential threats and estimating their likelihood and impact. Risk analysis can be part of a compliance strategy, to mitigate the risks of non-compliance. In a risk-based approach such as that of the AI Act, risk analysis is part of a broader risk-management strategy.

Compliance based on roles

One of the difficulties of checking compliance is that prohibitions, rights, permissions and obligations depend on the roles assumed by entities or people, as defined in the law. These roles are diverse, vary between pieces of legislation, and can change with time. Some examples of roles defined by the regulations we are interested in are controller and processor defined by the GDPR (GDPR Article 4), provider and deployer for the AI Act (AIA Article 3), user and data holder for the Data Act (Data Act Article 2), or data holder, data user, Data Intermediation Service Providers and Data Altruism Organisations for the DGA (DGA Article 2).

These roles, even when using the same terms, are not always consistently defined. For example, the definition of "data holder" found in the Data Act is not identical to the one found in the Data Governance Act. Another challenge is the fact that one entity or person can play more than one role. EU legislation is aiming to define roles pertaining to a very complex interplay of evolving actors.

Who checks compliance?

It is in the interest of organisations to make sure they comply with EU regulations. To this end, they can perform an internal self-assessment. In fact, the GDPR requires public authorities, public bodies and entities that do large-scale processing of personal data to appoint a Data Protection Officer (DPO), responsible for independently monitoring the organisation's compliance and providing guidance (GDPR, article 37). The AI Act, Data Act and Data Governance Act do not

⁴ <https://www.enforcementtracker.com/ETid-2584>

require the appointment of a similar figure but still require the organisation to ensure its own compliance through other means.

Another solution is to rely on independent, external auditors or official accreditation bodies. Audit reports and accreditations cannot replace oversight by legal authorities, but provide a solid proof of compliance. In both cases, organisations and companies have to invest money and time in record keeping (policies, procedures, contract and data processing agreements, incident reports), in order to have tangible proof of compliance.

Legal compliance can also be verified through investigations conducted by public authorities. In these cases, a competent regulator examines whether an organisation has respected the obligations imposed by a law. Investigations may be triggered by complaints from individuals, reports of potential violations, or routine supervisory activities. During the investigation, the authority may request documents and inspect internal practices, hence the importance of keeping records to prove compliance. Under the GDPR, Member States are required to designate one or more Data Protection Authority (DPA) responsible for monitoring the application of data protection law (GDPR, Article 51).

Compliance based on lifecycle

Compliance is not only a point-in-time issue and has to be checked across the lifecycle of artificial intelligence systems and data processes. The lifecycle of technical tools refers to the different stages of design, development, deployment, use and maintenance. The lifecycle of data refers to data processing (GDPR Article 4), i.e., any operation or set of operations which is performed on data, which includes collection, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, use, disclosure or erasure. Regulatory obligations intersect with every stage of AI and data lifecycle and depend on the type of data (personal and non-personal) and on the type of data processing involved. Thus, one of the challenges faced by organizations and companies wishing to check compliance is the identification of relevant and applicable laws and requirements for each step of the lifecycle. This is essential for long-term regulatory compliance.

Compliance checks and audits can be performed at different stages of the lifecycle. If we consider the execution of a tool or data process, compliance can be checked ex-ante as part of a planning strategy, in real-time, or ex-post (Ceci & Bianculli, 2026). These can respectively be considered prevention, detection and remediation strategies (Root, 2019).

1.4 Challenges in Legal Compliance Verification and Validation

The complexity of the AI and data regulatory landscape poses a significant challenge for compliance checking. More broadly, however, it is the very nature of law itself that raises questions, both for manual compliance checking and, more specifically, for automating compliance verification and validation.

Stability of legal norms:

A first consideration when checking compliance is the evolution of law through time. Legal rules are dynamic, with national and European laws being continuously adopted and amended. Compliance checking tools and methods must face this by detecting and integrating these changes

to provide an up-to-date representation of the law (Boella et al., 2016). But the latest version of a law or legal norm is not sufficient, as the law is anchored in time and can be seen as a chronology of different legal versions of one or several documents. For this reason, compliance-checking tools and methods must be concerned with the dynamic nature of legal norms (Palmirani, Governatori, & Contissa, 2011; Palmirani & Brighi, 2006).

Contextual and temporal reasoning:

Another challenge related to time is the consideration of time *as defined in and by* the law. The conditions for compliance, and more generally legal rules, are context- and time-sensitive. Time-related conditions might include dates of entry into force, rule suspensions, or vague time specifications such as “without undue delay” or “in a timely manner” (e.g.: Data Act, Article 5(1)). On top of temporal considerations, the legal context also matters. The context concerns both the legal framework (jurisdictions) and the context in which the legal constraints apply, in other words: time, space, actors, activities. Temporal logic and contextual ontologies, in combination with semantic markup technologies, can be explored to overcome problems posed by time and context considerations (Fdhila et al., 2016; Malik & Jain, 2017; Palmirani, Ceci, et al., 2011).

Ambiguity and vagueness:

In legal documents, the use of natural language is often intentionally vague or open to interpretation, and legal concepts are “open-textured”. Legal knowledge must be adapted to fit the circumstances of the cases to which it is applied (Hamfelt, 1995). Some mitigation strategies like human-in-the-loop approaches or controlled language can be explored to address these issues (Garzo & Palumbo, 2025).

Explainability:

Another concern is the need to make formal legal knowledge representations understandable by humans. This strongly applies to legal argumentation, but also to compliance-checking where conclusions of compliance/non-compliance must be explained and justified, especially if organizations want to understand why they are (not) compliant and find solutions. A gap needs to be breached between ambiguous rules expressed in natural language and highly structured reasoning processes (Booth et al., 2019; Sadowski & Chudziak, 2025).

Limitations when modelling real-world facts:

One of the main challenges of compliance checking is the identification of real-world facts, and the checking of these facts against the relevant legal framework or standards. In the context of AI and data regulations, the challenge lies in the large number of overlapping rules, and the complexity of AI and data processes to keep track of. One way of keeping track of these “real-world facts” is for enterprises to keep and update records of their activities. A solution to explore for automated compliance checking is the semantic annotation of Business Process Models (BPM), that are used to describe the activities carried out by an enterprise (Tosatto et al., 2013).

Interoperability:

Interoperability is an important factor for ensuring data sharing across territories, sectors and entities, but also for facilitating compliance by providing common meanings, documentation and processes, as illustrated by the entry into force of the Interoperable Europe Act on 11 April

2024. Four main types of interoperability can be delimited: technical interoperability, that refers to the compatibility of systems; syntactic operability, that refers to the implementation and adherence to standards so that structured data can be exchanged through the technical infrastructure; semantic interoperability, for a homogeneous interpretation of information; and finally, pragmatic interoperability between organisations and entities through various quality, trust or collaboration agreements (Janssen et al., 2014). In the context of assisted or automated compliance checking, standards and common practices play an important role in ensuring smooth transitions between the different steps of assessment by providing interoperable information and systems.

In light of these overlapping challenges and considerations, this review aims to improve understanding of the current landscape of methods and tools developed for ensuring compliance with AI and data regulations, including their strengths and limitations. The review is organized as follows. In section 2, we present the review methodology. In section 3, we present the theoretical foundations of compliance checking tools and methods. In section 4, we present the different existing assessment and compliance-checking approaches. In section 5, we present automated and AI-based methodologies. In section 6, we discuss the challenges and limitations of the tools and methods. In section 7, we explore evaluation methodologies for compliance-checking tools and methods. In section 8, we present specific case studies and applications.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Multivocal Literature Review (MLR)

Although there is a significant amount of white literature on compliance checking, some important legal and technical documentation is also published by market actors and public actor bodies outside of the scope of academic literature, and can be found on official EU and Member States web pages or market actors websites, for instance. In addition, tool producers and users need to understand the strengths and limitations of each tool, and how they compare with each other, to improve literacy in compliance checking and facilitate the development and improvement of compliance-checking tools. For these reasons, the chosen methodology is the multivocal literature review (Garousi et al., 2019), that includes both grey and white literature, as a way to provide insights on both the state-of-the-art and the state-of-practice in the field of compliance checking. Grey literature is defined by the Cochrane Handbook For Systematic Reviews of Interventions (*Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions* | Cochrane, n.d.) as “literature that is not formally published in sources such as books or journal articles”.

Given that the scope of this review also encompasses compliance-checking tools and methods that are on the market, we chose to include 2nd tier grey literature with moderate outlet control (such as vendor websites) (Garousi et al., 2019), only in relevant cases when there exists no white or grey literature of higher credibility regarding a particular tool or method. However, in an effort to preserve the scientific rigour of this review, in all other cases we restricted the scope of grey literature to sources issued by official and authoritative sources. In other words, in addition to white literature, we chose to take into consideration soft laws, government reports, documentation published by the European Union, and technical or scientific documentation published outside of books, conferences and journals, but by trusted entities such as the UN, OECD, the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C), standardization and technical committees like CEN-CENELEC, the Object Management Group (OMG) or ISO, among other authoritative sources. This means excluding literature from untrusted or undocumented sources, according to exclusion/inclusion criteria further detailed below, which elaborated based on the CRAAP Test⁵ evaluation criteria. The MLR proposes a series of structured steps for literature extraction, selection and synthesis, that have been adapted for the purpose of this review and are detailed below.

2.2 Data collection method

We started by defining the scope of the review and by formulating research questions defined above in the introduction. The scope and the research questions are the prism through which data sources and keywords were selected. The literature review was executed searching both white and grey literature, selected based on a set of inclusion/exclusion criteria based on the CRAAP Test evaluation criteria. The inclusion and exclusion criteria mirror each other.

⁵ <https://library.csuchico.edu/sites/default/files/craap-test.pdf>

Inclusion criteria:

- **IC1: Currency**

The source was published at a relevant time, and is preferably the latest published on the topic, or has been revised or updated.

- **IC2: Relevance**

The source is directly related to the topic of compliance-checking tools and methods, or is relevant for answering one or several of the research questions. This includes papers that propose, analyse or improve knowledge on compliance checking solutions, or that discuss compliance for EU AI and data regulations.

- **IC3: Authority**

The source is a peer-reviewed paper published in a journal or in conference proceedings, or is an item of 1st tier grey literature (Garousi et al., 2019) from a verifiable author or organization. If this is not the case, the author of the source must have relevant credentials, qualifications, or be affiliated to an authoritative organization.

- **IC4: Accuracy**

The source must provide clear evidence of the information it provides, either through citations or through a review by qualified entities or persons. The source is neutral in tone and free of linguistic errors.

- **IC5: Purpose**

The purpose of the source is to inform. It is objective and impartial.

Exclusion criteria:

- **EC1: Currency**

The source is outdated and has become irrelevant for the topic.

- **EC2: Relevance**

The source is irrelevant for the topic or out of the scope of the research questions.

- **EC3: Authority**

The source cannot be attributed to a specific author, organization or company. The author does not appear to have the relevant qualification or to be affiliated to an authoritative organization.

- **EC4: Accuracy**

The source is an item of 2nd or 3rd tier grey literature (Garousi et al., 2019). The source does not provide clear evidence of the information it provides, either through citations or through

a review by qualified entities or persons. The source presents linguistic (grammar, spelling) errors.

- **EC5: Purpose**

The purpose of the source is to sell, convince or spread an ideology or propaganda. Its purpose is unclear or appears to be biased.

- **EC6: Accessibility**

The source is not in a language comprehensible by the DCs (the languages spoken by the DCs are English, Spanish, French, German, Swahili and Bengali) or is not accessible with institutional credentials.

Keyword string:

The following keyword string was defined to constrain and harmonize the scope of the review:

("legal compliance" OR "regulatory compliance" OR "compliance checking") AND (tool* OR method* OR system* OR framework*) AND ("legal reasoning" OR "rule-based reasoning" OR "case-based reasoning" OR "legal informatics" OR "computational law" OR "legal tech*")

The first part of the keyword string, “legal compliance,” “regulatory compliance,” or “compliance checking,” broadly targets literature concerned with compliance and the legal domain. The second part, which includes terms like tool, method, system, or framework, narrows the results to studies that propose or analyse implementable solutions rather than purely theoretical reflections. The final part of the keyword string refines the scope by making sure the literature is either concerned with legal informatics and computational law, or is related to the more specific fields of rule-based or case-based reasoning, that we deemed important to include considering their role in compliance-checking approaches. The whole keyword string ensures that the results not only address compliance in practice but also engage with the ways legal rules are modeled, interpreted, and automated, in order to make a query that captures interdisciplinary work at the intersection of law, technology, and formal reasoning. We did not restrict the keyword string to EU and AI regulations because tools and methods developed for checking compliance against other legislative measures might still be relevant for our legal scope.

We used the selected keyword string for automatic searching on six digital libraries: ACM Digital Library, Science Direct, Springer Link, IEEE Digital Library (IEEEXplore), Web of Science, and Scopus. The search for grey literature was done on a broader scale using the Google search engine. We used our institutional credentials (provided by UNIBO, UPM, TCD and UGent) to access white literature. If papers were not accessible with institutional credentials, they were excluded from the review. A common Zotero library was set up to host all chosen papers and help with citations.

To know when to stop the search in these libraries, we used two of the stopping conditions proposed by Garousi et al.:

- theoretical saturation, reached when no new concepts emerge from the search results anymore; and
- effort bounded search, i.e., including only the top 200 search engine hits.

D2.2 Survey of Compliance Methods and Tools

Doing forward and backward snowballing (in other words, using reference lists and backlinks) expanded the search base to a wider set of repositories and websites: Jstor, PhilPapers, Cronfa, IOS Press Ebooks, ASCE library, ProQuest, SAGE Journals, Arxiv.org and Semantic Scholar. However, automatic keyword search was not done on these websites. The search included both primary studies on compliance-checking tools and methods and secondary studies like surveys, systematic literature reviews, and commentaries on research papers. In the case of grey literature, primary sources included developer and seller websites and public sector bodies websites, and secondary sources included, for example, reviews of the tools and methods by external stakeholders and practitioners.

Regarding the timeline, upstream work was started on the deliverable on December 18th 2025 by the three appointed DCs (Célestine Lecat (UNIBO), Meem Manab (UPM), Fabian Linde (UPM)), who defined the scope and the methodology of the review. On January 14th 2026, the other DCs in charge of Work Package 2 (Victoria Wiegand (TCD), Sheyla Leyva Sánchez (UPM), Marlin Kisia (UGent)) were involved in the review, and all DCs worked together until the submission of the deliverable on March 25th 2026. The DCs worked in pairs on different aspects of the review, based on their areas of expertise and their PhD thesis.

Throughout the review, the DCs tracked their work progress on each section in a common tracking document. A separate Excel file was created to keep track of all the different compliance-checking tools and methods encountered during the review. The tools and methods are separated into the following categories: rule-based, model-driven, normative reasoning, Semantic Web technologies, ontologies and knowledge graphs, NLP, legal document summarization, named entity recognition, text-mining and legal information retrieval, generative AI, machine learning approaches. For each tool, its name, type (tool, method, standard) and ownership rights (proprietary or nonproprietary) are logged, along with a description, source and references.

3 THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS

3.1 Legal Norms and Their Formalization

In the Legal Theory tradition, *legal norms* are described by Kelsen as “ought” statements prescribing certain modes of conduct, with law being the system composed of these norms (Kelsen, 1966). Alchourron introduces a stronger distinction between norms and their textual formulation. He states that a “norm” is the *meaning* attributed to normative linguistic expressions (Alchourron, 1996), also called legal provisions. A simple categorization of legal norms would be the following (Aarnio, 2011):

- prescriptive norms, including commands, prohibitions and permissions;
- norms of competence, that either grant legislative competence or norms that grant the competence to actualize a previously enacted legal obligation; and
- norms establishing legal definitions.

Another similar distinction can be made between constitutive rules (or norms), meta-rules that create the activity, institution or status they apply to, and regulative rules that regulate pre-existing activities (Roversi, 2021). The main point to take from these two categorisations is that norms can either *define* or *prescribe*.

The emergence of the Rules as Code paradigm⁶ coincides with an increase in research and efforts to formalize these legal norms. According to Herrestad (1991), formalization is a process by which a piece of knowledge is adapted for mechanical processing, in the form of an axiomatic system from which new theorems may be deduced by a rule of inference. Formalization must therefore provide:

- a formal vocabulary to model core concepts;
- axioms that define the relationship between core concepts; and
- rules of inference that allow to deduce new theorems based on existing knowledge.

In the legal domain, it means turning legal knowledge (concepts, rules), that is normally written in natural language, into machine-interpretable representations so that a computer can reason with them, check compliance, or support decisions. This process relies on the abstraction of the *logic layer* and the *semantic layer* of legal texts, creating links between textual knowledge and conceptual knowledge (Valente & Breuker, 1995). In the context of compliance checking, legal formalisms allow organizations to input data on a particular factual situation, and produce conclusions which are aligned with the legislative intent of the legal text as applied to that data (Mowbray et al., 2023). Formalization can be done simultaneously with the creation of the natural language text during legal drafting (Law as Code, text-first), or retrospectively by converting and encoding natural language texts (Rules as Code approach, code-first (Goodenough & Carlson, 2024).

Compliance rules have to be modeled differently depending on the type of normative provisions. In EU regulations, two types of norms can be found: prescriptive rules that take the form

⁶ <https://interoperable-europe.ec.europa.eu/collection/eugovtech/document/rules-code-open-approach>

of an “IF [...] THEN” constraint (Niblett, 1980), and descriptive rules that provide the necessary knowledge and context for the application of prescriptive rules. Prescriptive rules can then be separated into substantive law applicable to conducts (prohibited, obligatory, permitted), and procedural law that concerns the procedures administrating and enforcing substantive law.

Initial research on formalization started as early as the 1960s, with Allen proposing an application of symbolic logic to law (Allen, 1966). Other works followed, with an emphasis on legal reasoning and rule-based systems (based on “IF [...] THEN” rules). A state-of-the-art example for the period is the formalization of the British Nationality Act with logic programming (Sergot et al., 1986). The limitations of classical logic prompted a new wave of research on nonmonotonic logic in the nineties, with the intention of making possible the formalization of legal exceptions and normative conflicts. Today, several markup languages have been developed, with very different sets of features. They manage, for instance, the defeasibility and temporality of rules, the classification of norms and jurisdictions, negations, authorial tracking, among many others.

Later, the emergence of the semantic web in the AI & law community sparked a new interest for modelling not only legal reasoning but also legal knowledge (Valente & Breuker, 1995). Since then, different ontologies and vocabularies (FOLaw (Valente & Breuker, 1995), UFO-L (Griffo et al., 2016), LKIF (Hoekstra et al., 2007), Akoma Ntoso ontology (Barabucci, Cervone, Palmirani, et al., 2010), etc.) have been developed to model legal concepts and their relationships, and will be presented in the following sections. Current formalization methods now often include both semantic and logic modelling methods, and research is increasingly angled toward automated methods of formalization (Horner et al., 2025). A recent example would be the formalization of the GDPR with a framework integrating LegalRuleML and PrOnto legal ontology for automatic legal reasoning, with the goal of checking compliance against the GDPR (Palmirani & Governatori, 2018).

Assessing the quality of formalization methods can be boiled down to four core parameters: correctness, transparency, comprehensibility and multiple interpretations support (Novotná & Libal, 2022). Concrete examples of formalization methods will be discussed in further detail in the following sections.

3.2 Deontic Logic and Defeasible Logic

The representation of the logic of law is an integral part of legal formalization. The difficulty that arises is finding a balance between a simple and comprehensible formalization of logic, and a more flexible – but also more complex – approach that would account for the specificities of legal reasoning, like exceptions, vagueness or temporality, to name a few.

3.2.1 Deontic Logic

One of the main approaches for representing normative constraints in legal formalization is deontic logic. It is a branch of modal logic involving reasoning about norms: obligations, prohibitions and permissions (von Wright, 1951a). Sixty years after Von Wright coined the term, its use in computer science is still being debated. Deontic logic is useful to make explicit, and then reason

about, the distinction between what ought to be the case and what is the case (Benzmüller et al., 2020; Jones & Sergot, 1992).

But deontic logic, used on its own, faces many challenges when formalizing deontic statements. Chisholm's paradox (Chisholm, 1963) is a famous example of what is known as a contrary-to-duty obligation (CTD), a secondary obligation resulting from the violation of a primary obligation. An example would be:

(p1) "She ought to keep her promise"

(p2) "If she does not keep her promise, then she ought to apologize"

In this case, the violation of the primary obligation (p1) triggers the secondary obligation (p2). It is not so much a paradox, but rather a deontic statement that is difficult to formalize (Saint Croix & Thomason, 2014) because of its conditional nature. Paradoxes like this one prompted the development of logic combinations and extensions of deontic logic, like temporal defeasible logic (Governatori et al., 2021), that account for more complex situations than classical logics.

3.2.1 Defeasible Logic

Deontic logic can be combined with other logic frameworks in order to overcome the deontic conflicts presented above. A good example is defeasible deontic logic (Governatori & Palmirani, 2026). Although some authors (Hamfelt, 1995; Yoshino, 1995) have argued that non-monotonic logic is not the best for legal reasoning and advocate for a more minimalistic approach of classical first-order logic, the use of non-monotonic reasoning is now widespread in the AI and law community. Monotonic reasoning, which is very inflexible, is generally seen as poorly fit for legal reasoning, especially for reasoning with uncertainty, exceptions, similarity, vagueness, incomplete or contradictory information (T. Bench-Capon et al., 2012; Booth et al., 2019).

Indeed, the difficulty of legal logic modelling is handling indeterminacy and conflict (Berman & Hafner, 1993). Normative conflicts can be divided into *deontic conflicts*, relating to obligations and permissions, and *capacitive conflicts* relating to legal power, also called legal competence. These conflicts apply both to national and international law (Lindahl & Reidhav, 2015).

Non-monotonic logics allow the retraction of inferences based on new information. Defeasible logic is a rule-based practical instantiation of non-monotonic logic, that resolves conflict between prioritizing some rules over others in a dynamic way (Antoniou, 2004). It is the "first of a family of approaches based on the idea of logic programming without negation as failure" (Antoniou et al., 2001). It is used to model regulations, business rules and contracts. For instance, when checking if an organization is compliant with both international and national regulations, defeasible logic allows to encode priority principles to account for the relative power of rules. Thus, an exception can overrule a general rule, or a national law can overrule an international law.

3.3 Regulatory Frameworks and Compliance Mechanisms

Four main levels of compliance, illustrated in Figure 1, should be distinguished to understand better the mechanisms at stake in regulatory frameworks and compliance strategies.

The first level of compliance lies in prescriptive and procedural rules that come from legislation, regulations, policies, soft laws, codes of conduct, processes and best practices. In this case, one of the frequent solutions proposed by the AI and Law community is to use NLP, LLM, embeddings and transformers to extract these prescriptive and procedural rules from the text they are from, and to formalize them in XML in order to facilitate the three steps described below, in other words the assessment, certification and compliance tasks.

The second level of compliance is the assessment of the strategy implemented by an entity or organisation to comply with norms. This assessment often outputs a report or checklist that can be used as evidence in a possible audit. Assessments can be mandated by declarative rules that describe how to implement compliance in a specific domain, entity, or context (e.g., in a eGOV service, a bank service, or a judicial system). Some examples are the Data Protection Impact Assessments required by the GDPR, Impact Assessment reports, Risk assessments and Fundamental Rights Impact assessment for high-risk AI systems required by the AI Act.

The third level is standards and certifications, that assert that the entity implements some mandatory standards (e.g., ISO/IEC 27004:2016⁷, ISO/IEC 42001:2023⁸). Certifications are issued after verification that some main pillars of the standards are respected. In the case of AI and data, the certifications prove that some constraints are respected (e.g., for medical devices). Standards and certifications will be further discussed in this section.

The fourth level of compliance is the action to verify that the previous steps have been respected with real-world facts, inside of concrete services, processes, software, hardware, and platforms. To collect and document this information, some possible solutions are to use sensors (e.g., Digital Twin, IoT devices, edge cloud), or to add semantic annotation to textual process models (Tosatto et al., 2013).

⁷ <https://www.iso.org/standard/64120.html>

⁸ <https://www.iso.org/standard/42001>

Figure 1: Levels of compliance

At each level of compliance, regulatory frameworks and standards of AI and data-intensive technologies take on various approaches through formalised legislation, soft law, or assessment. Compliance mechanisms can take on the form of non-binding standards, certifications, guidelines, and codes of practice. In this section, we also discuss the role harmonised standards play in compliance checking for EU legislation.

3.3.1 European Legislation

As noted in the Introduction, the EU legislation within scope are the GDPR, AI Act, Data Act, Data Governance Act, and Interoperable Europe Act. These acts apply to all EU member states where each member state authority is charged with implementing the legislation. Member states have the authority to add additional requirements, one example being the German Federal Data Protection Act⁹. Enforcement and compliance mechanisms differ per act and will be briefly discussed throughout this section. The GDPR grants individuals control and security of their processed data through required consent, opt-out rights, and organisational obligations. Organisations using personal data that pose risks to rights and freedoms of individuals may be subject to mandatory impact assessments and the establishment of a data protection officer (European Union, 2018). Organisations can voluntarily demonstrate compliance through approved certifications or code of conducts (European Commission, n.d.-b). (Certifications and codes of conduct will be discussed later in this section). The AI Act institutes risk-based rules for AI providers and deployers to promote safety, fundamental rights, and human-centric AI (European Commission, 2026a). Regulation is applied to AI systems based on their risk level: unacceptable (prohibited), high-

⁹ German Federal Ministry of the Interior, The Federal Data Protection Act: <https://www.bmi.bund.de/EN/topics/constitution/data-protection/federal-data-protection-act/federal-data-protection-act-artikel.html>

risk (requires risk assessments), limited (subjected to transparency rules), and minimal (no rules) (European Commission, 2026a). Compliance of an AI system is thus dependent on its risk level and the necessary requirements outlined in the legislation. Harmonised standards are being developed to assist high-risk AI systems with compliance and are discussed more in depth in the next subsection (Soler et al., 2024). The Data Act ensures fair processing of data generated in products or services by allowing users and organisations control over data they generate in a service or product (European Commission, 2025b). EU member states must designate a ‘data coordinator’ to address all issues regarding implementation and enforcement of the Data Act. The Data Governance Act establishes a framework for altruistic data sharing, publicly held data, and neutral data processing intermediaries (European Commission, 2024). Repositories for the data and intermediaries must be registered through a member state’s competent authority. The Interoperable Europe Act enables cross-border data flows throughout the EU for digital public services (European Union, 2024). Member states must designate a competent authority and submit annual reports of compliance.

The EU governance approach to AI technologies differs from other jurisdictions, such as the United States. The U.S. has no federal legislation on general data protection, data-intensive technologies, or AI. However, U.S. federal governance of AI has been practiced through Executive Orders (EO) from the President which solely act as directives for the executive branch of government. The Biden Administration published EO 14110¹⁰: “Safe, Secure, and Trustworthy Development and Use of Artificial Intelligence,” aiming to influence policy on safe AI, develop standards, increase data access, promote competition, and uphold civil rights (Harris & Jaikaran, 2024). This EO was revoked under the Trump Administration with EO 14179¹¹: “Removing Barriers to American Leadership in Artificial Intelligence.” In general, the U.S. ‘focuses on incentives to innovate and centers markets over government regulation’ for AI, whereas the EU approach involves governed risk-based oversight (Sloane & Wüllhorst, 2025). EU AI legislation prioritises risk assessment and fundamental rights in contrast to the U.S.’s concern for national security (Sloane & Wüllhorst, 2025; Soler et al., 2024). U.S. AI governance often involves an extension of previous legislation commonly from non-discrimination, consumer protection, or road traffic laws implemented either at the state or local level, whereas the EU AI Act applies to all member states (Sloane & Wüllhorst, 2025). It is important to note that state or local AI legislation has been directed to be legally challenged at the federal level under the Trump Administration’s EO 14365¹²: “Ensuring a National Policy Framework for Artificial Intelligence.” Legislative data privacy protection in the U.S.

¹⁰ Federal Register of the National Archives, Executive Order 14110: Safe, Secure, and Trustworthy Development and Use of Artificial Intelligence, a presidential document by the Executive Office of the President on October 30, 2023, <https://www.federalregister.gov/documents/2023/11/01/2023-24283/safe-secure-and-trustworthy-development-and-use-of-artificial-intelligence>.

¹¹ Federal Register of the National Archives, Executive Order 14179: Removing Barriers to American Leadership in Artificial Intelligence, a presidential document by the Executive Office of the President on January 23, 2025, <https://www.federalregister.gov/documents/2025/01/31/2025-02172/removing-barriers-to-american-leadership-in-artificial-intelligence>.

¹² Federal Register of the National Archives, Executive Order 14365: Ensuring a National Policy Framework for Artificial Intelligence, a presidential document by the Executive Office of the President on December 11, 2025, <https://www.federalregister.gov/documents/2025/12/16/2025-23092/ensuring-a-national-policy-framework-for-artificial-intelligence>

is sector specific (i.e. The Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA) for health data, The Family Educational Rights and Privacy Act (FERPA) for school records) or regional (i.e. The California Consumer Privacy Act) (Cole, 2021; Seun Solomon Bakare et al., 2024). Compliance and enforcement of U.S. data protection legislation involves implementing appropriate safeguards and training, and issuing fines (and in some cases imprisonment for HIPAA) (Seun Solomon Bakare et al., 2024).

3.3.2 European Harmonised Standards

Harmonised standards are European standards developed by the European Committee for Standardisation (CEN), the European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardisation (CENELEC), and/or European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) to ‘translate legal requirements into common technical language, simplifying compliance for companies and other stakeholders’ (European Commission, n.d.-a; European Commission, 2026b). The European Commission must request a standard for harmonisation to provide a means of conformity assessments for various industries to ensure compliance with EU legislation. These harmonised standards are not enforced but provide legal certainty through presumed compliance from adhering to a harmonised standard, as well as offer market benchmarking and a means to foster trust and market acceptance (European Commission, 2026b; Golpayegani et al., 2023). Compliance with harmonised standards is voluntary as operators can choose other means to demonstrate compliance with EU legislation (European Commission, n.d.-a).

The European Commission has requested harmonised standards for conformity assessment for the EU AI Act for high-risk AI systems, excluding general-purpose (Soler et al., 2024). CEN and CENELEC are working together in a Joint Technical Committee called JTC 21 to achieve these goals. The areas of concern are:

- risk management
- governance and quality of datasets
- record keeping
- transparency
- human oversight
- accuracy
- robustness
- cybersecurity
- quality management
- conformity assessment

(European Commission, 2026b). These harmonised standards should cover all aspects of an AI system’s lifecycle from inception to post-market deployment (Soler et al., 2024) . Once the standards are published by JCT21, the European Commission will decide if they are to be approved for conformity assessment for the EU AI Act. AI systems developed in accordance with the

harmonised standards will be granted a legal presumption of conformity (Soler et al., 2024). The only harmonised standard available as of March 2026 is prEN 18286¹³ on AI Quality Management, which is accepting review comments from national standardisation bodies.

The harmonised standards for the EU AI Act are intended to make use of available relevant international standards from the International Organisation for Standardisation (ISO) and International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) (Soler et al., 2024). JTC21 is tasked to develop ‘home-grown’ EU standards to address risks to health, safety, and fundamental rights, whereas ISO/IEC standards focus on organisational objectives (Golpayegani et al., 2023; Soler et al., 2024). The standards developed will reference each other and have some level of dependency (Soler et al., 2024).

The development of the harmonised standards for the EU AI Act is facing significant challenges. The estimated time of completion was October 2025 but JTC21 has only released one standard for review, AI Quality Management, as mentioned above (Golpayegani et al., 2023; Soler et al., 2024). Interdependence and need for consensus building in the harmonised standards has caused delays in output (Kilian et al., 2025). Even after the standards are finished approval from the European Commission could take months (Kilian et al., 2025). Furthermore, ISO/IEC issued a lawsuit in the Court of Justice of the European Union on 6 December 2024 to ensure copyright integrity of their monetised standards, as harmonised standards are required to be law to be accessible and free (Kilian et al., 2025).

AI providers face uncertainty given the status of the harmonised standards and a compliance deadline of August 2026 (Kilian et al., 2025). This is particularly challenging for small-medium enterprises (SMEs) and startups who lack resources and experience with compliance and are not well represented in the standardisation process, as observed through interviews in Kilian et al., 2025. These issues are intended to be addressed through the proposed Digital Omnibus by extending deadlines and providing compliance simplifications for SMEs (European Commission, 2025a). The Digital Omnibus is currently undergoing review in the European Parliament.

3.3.3 Standards and Certifications

The prominent international bodies focusing on standardisation for AI technologies are ISO/IEC’s JCT1/SC42 committee, Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE) AI Standards Committee, and CEN-CENELEC’s JCT21 committee (Kilian et al., 2025). Figure 2 from CEN-CENELEC illustrates the current standardisation landscape. National standards committees are also involved and work in collaboration with the international organisations listed previously. This includes the German Institute of Standardisation (DIN) in collaboration with the German Commission for Electrotechnical, Electronic, and Information Technologies (DKE) in a joint committee, The U.S.’s National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST), and the British Standards Institution (BSI) (Kilian et al., 2025; National Institute of Standards and Technology (US), 2024; The British Standards Institution, 2025). AI standards are non-binding and can assist with compliance but do not provide an assumption of conformity, unlike harmonised standards (previously discussed). However, the

¹³ prEN 18286 Reaches Enquiry Stage: A Milestone for AI Quality Management in Europe: <https://jtc21.eu/pren-18286-reaches-enquiry-stage-a-milestone-for-ai-quality-management-in-europe/>

standards developed by these bodies have direct influence on legislation and frameworks for compliance.

Figure 2: CEN-CENELEC's map of standardisation bodies¹⁴

Certifications are mechanisms to demonstrate compliance, particularly for GDPR. These certifications illustrate an actor's data processing activities are compliant and trustworthy (European Commission, 2023). Certification schemes approved by the European Data Protection Board for a data protection seal are Europrivacy, EuroPriSe, and BC 5701:2024 (European Data Protection Board, n.d.). There are also approved national certification criteria for specific member states¹⁵.

3.3.4 Guidelines and Codes of Practice

Guidelines and codes of practice are forms of soft law that seek to influence positive behavior of all actors of AI and data-intensive technologies. *It is important to note that some codes of practice can be used as a means of compliance, such as the EU's General-Purpose AI Code of Practice¹⁶ for compliance with the EU AI Act.* Guidelines are developed by a variety of organisations such as government institutions, research organisations, non-profits, or industry. They often include privacy protection, fairness, non-discrimination, justice, transparency, safety, and common good (Hagendorff, 2020).

3.4 Impact Assessments

Impact assessments are structured frameworks for understanding effects and implications on people and their environment at the early stages in a system's life cycle to take appropriate risk mitigation steps (Stahl et al., 2023). Motivations and purposes of impact assessments vary and can

¹⁴ CEN-CENELEC's Guide 39: <https://www.cencenelec.eu/media/Guides/CEN-CLC/cenclcguide39.pdf>

¹⁵ Register of certification mechanisms, seals, and marks: https://www.edpb.europa.eu/our-work-tools/accountability-tools/certification-mechanisms-seals-and-marks_en

¹⁶ EU's General-Purpose AI Code of Practice: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/contents-code-gpai>

cover privacy, safeguards, understanding impacts, system acceptability, trustworthiness, etc. Impact assessments are created by a variety of organisations, but for the purpose of this deliverable we focus on impact assessments that demonstrate legal compliance. This includes the Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA), the Fundamental Rights Impact Assessment (FRIA), and the Interoperability Assessment.

DPIAs are required by the Article 35 of the GDPR when data processing is high-risk, such as the case for ‘a systematic and extensive evaluation of the personal aspects of an individual, including profiling, processing of sensitive data on a large scale, or systematic monitoring of public areas on a large scale’ (European Commission, n.d.-c). This assessment should be conducted prior to any processing of data and proves compliance for any entity processing high-risk data. DPIAs reinforce accountability and organisational responsibility for GDPR compliance by describing the processing, recognising risks, and highlighting safeguards (Demetzou, 2019).

FRIAs are mandatory for deployers of specific high-risk AI systems and general-purpose AI systems under the AI Act. A deployer is defined as a ‘person, public authority, agency or other body using an AI system under its authority’ (AIA Article 3(4)). Article 27 of the AI Act denotes that deployers of high-risk AI systems used in hiring, admission to education, immigration decisions, law enforcement, biometric identification are subject to FRIAs (Gill-Pedro, 2025). General-purpose AI systems that are ‘used in the context of high-risk AI systems or general-purpose models that pose a systemic risk,’ are also obliged to conduct FRIAs (Mantelero, 2024). AI deployers subject to FRIAs must consider each fundamental right and conduct them prior to deployment. This includes the context of the AI system’s deployment, data collection, and risk analysis and management procedures. While there are currently no official guidelines for conducting an FRIA for compliance with the AI Act, and Article 27 permits AI deployers to choose their methodology, the Danish Institute for Human Rights in collaboration with the European Center for Not-for-Profit Law have published a well regarded template¹⁷.

There have been substantive critiques of the FRIA requirements. Mantelero points out that deployers might not have access to all the information from AI providers to be able to conduct a thorough FRIA (Mantelero, 2024). The AI Act vaguely suggests relying on previously conducted impact assessments from AI providers but the information flow is not clearly laid out. Lasek-Markey et al. argue that the FRIA has limitations as it lacks intersectionality and does not go beyond the impact on individual human rights and take into account societal impacts, such as AI misinformation (Lasek-Markey & Hogan, 2025).

Interoperability Assessments for the Interoperable Europe Act are available at the European Commission’s Interoperability assessments space¹⁸. This space provides guidelines, a repository for assessment reports, a toolbox, and collaborative hub. It includes an interoperability assessment

¹⁷ A guide to Fundamental Rights Impact Assessments under the EU Artificial Intelligence (AI) Act by the Danish Institute for Human Rights and the European Center for Not-for-Profit Law: <https://www.humanrights.dk/publications/guide-fundamental-rights-impact-assessments-under-eu-artificial-intelligence-ai-act>

¹⁸ European Commission’s Interoperability assessment space: <https://interoperable-europe.ec.europa.eu/collection/assessments>

D2.2 Survey of Compliance Methods and Tools

online tool that is free to use and generates a report. This tool is voluntary but the report demonstrates compliance with the Interoperable Europe Act.

Section 3 was concerned with the theoretical foundations of assessment and compliance approaches. In the following section, we will explore these approaches more in depth.

4 ASSESSMENT AND COMPLIANCE CHECKING APPROACHES

4.1 Manual Review and Auditing

Manual compliance checking and auditing remain central practices in organisations seeking to ensure conformity with European regulatory frameworks. Despite the growing availability of compliance software, many organisations still rely heavily on manual or informal compliance practices that are time and labour intensive, rely on domain experts and are not driven by quantitative operational data that is increasingly being generated by organisations (Ryan et al., 2021). These include spreadsheet-based records, paper templates, and internally developed documentation procedures, which are widespread practices. An example would be the management of information required by the accountability framework mandated by article 30 of the GDPR. This principle requires organisations not only to comply with data protection obligations but also to demonstrate compliance to regulators and supervisory authorities. The risk assessment process of GDPR Data protection Impact Assessments (DPIA) and the management of the GDPR Register of Processing Activities (ROPA), where organisations must keep track of their data processing activities, are frequently done with a manual and informal approach. These manual approaches often lack interoperability and standardisation, leading to fragmented documentation of compliance information (Ryan et al., 2020). In practice, Data Protection Officers (DPOs) are responsible for monitoring processes and maintaining sufficient documentation to show that the organisation's data processing activities conform to the GDPR's legal requirements. DPOs must oversee complex organisational processes involving large volumes of heterogeneous personal data and distributed processing activities across jurisdictions.

Under the AI Act, conformity assessments are mandated to demonstrate that an AI system complies with the mandatory requirements set out in the regulation. Deployers of high-risk AI systems must also carry out Fundamental Rights Impact Assessment (AIA, Article 27) of their system before its development. The FRIA must include the persons and groups likely affected, the specific risks to fundamental rights, human-oversight measures and mitigation and governance arrangements. Deployers must then notify the market surveillance authority by submitting the filled-out template developed by the AI Office. The technical documentation of high-risk AI systems must be drawn up before these systems are placed on the market or put into service and must be kept up-to-date (AIA Article 11). This may be challenging for small and medium-sized enterprises due to the need for advanced knowledge of both legal and technical aspects, which is rare among software developers and legal professionals, and may incur high costs (Sovrano et al., 2025b). Sovrano (2025) demonstrates that AI tool-generated assessments of technical documentation, although they sometimes present important issues, are showing encouraging results for the future, with the DoXpert tool showing accuracy and F1 scores around 80% in terms of alignment with legal expert judgements.

On top of previously stated assessment requirements, Article 3 of the Interoperable Europe Act requires Union entities and public sector bodies to carry out Interoperability Assessments using the European Interoperability Framework. Additionally, the Interoperable Europe Act, Data Act and Data Governance Act also set out requirements for interoperability (Interoperable Europe Act core obligations; Data Act Articles 33 and 35) and traceable records of data access and sharing (DGA

Articles 12(o) and 20) that involve complex large-scale monitoring of data and processes. The resulting compliance landscape for all AI and data regulations is highly heterogeneous and difficult to monitor systematically.

While manual compliance auditing continues to play an important role in organisational governance, it is increasingly insufficient to address the scale, complexity, and evidentiary demands of modern EU regulatory frameworks. Future compliance systems are likely to combine human legal interpretation with structured, machine-readable compliance data and automated verification mechanisms. Such approaches can help identify gaps in existing documentation and processes according to the provisions of AI and data regulations (Sovrano et al., 2025b).

4.2 Rule-based compliance checking

Rule-based compliance checking operationalizes regulatory requirements as executable rules evaluated over structured facts (for example, records of processing activities, contract and processor metadata, data subject access requests, authorisation decisions, or configuration states). It is particularly suitable when compliance outcomes must be deterministic, reproducible, and auditable: each verdict can be traced back to the specific input facts and the rule(s) that triggered, producing a transparent proof trail that supports verification and accountability (Goodman & Flaxman, 2017). The core modelling step is to translate normative requirements into a rule vocabulary and an execution-ready representation. Common encodings include production rules (if/then), decision tables, and policy predicates over structured inputs. A typical illustrative encoding turns a regulatory condition into an executable predicate, for example: if personal data are transferred outside the European Economic Area (EEA), then an adequacy decision applies or appropriate safeguards are used, such as Standard Contractual Clauses (SCCs). This example mirrors the structure of Chapter V transfer mechanisms and is widely operationalised in practice through SCC templates and transfer governance processes (*International Data Transfers | European Data Protection Board*, n.d.)

Correctness, however, still depends on the legal interpretation performed during rule authoring: rules reduce interpretation variance at execution time, but they do not eliminate the need for legally sound modelling choices about scope, exceptions, and evidentiary thresholds. This is one reason why legal reasoning scholarship remains relevant even in purely rule-based implementations (Sartor, 2005).

When decision logic must be shared across organisational units and implemented consistently, Decision Model and Notation (DMN) provides a standard way to represent decision logic using decision requirements diagrams and decision tables, aligning business decisioning with compliance constraints (*Decision Model and Notation™ (DMN™) | Object Management Group*, n.d.)

Rule engines typically support two complementary inference styles:

- *Forward chaining* (data-driven). New or updated facts trigger applicable rules, which is well suited to event-driven monitoring (for example, evaluating whether a newly recorded transfer, access request, or system configuration violates a rule).

- *Backward chaining* (goal-driven). Reasoning starts from a compliance query (for example, "is this transfer permissible?" or "is there evidence of lawful basis?") and works backwards to the facts that must be established.

In many practical deployments, a hybrid approach is used. For example, Drools explicitly supports both forward and backward chaining in its rule engine, reflecting the need to combine monitoring-style evaluation with audit and evidence querying (*Drools Rule Engine :: Drools Documentation*, n.d.).

To scale to large rule sets and fact bases, production rule engines commonly rely on established pattern-matching optimisations such as the RETE algorithm, which shares partial matches across rules in a discrimination network and reduces redundant computation during repeated rule evaluations (Forgy, 1982). A key differentiator of rule-based approaches is that they naturally produce meaningful explanations. Fired-rule traces, including rule identifiers, triggering facts, intermediate conclusions, and final verdicts, provide a direct account of the logic underlying each decision that can be communicated to auditors, internal governance functions, and regulators. This kind of traceability aligns well with transparency expectations in regulated settings and is often contrasted with the opacity of many machine learning pipelines. In the context of the GDPR, the transparency debate around automated decision-making and explanation illustrates why decision traceability remains a central design concern, even though the precise legal scope of a "right to explanation" is contested (Goodman & Flaxman, 2017; Wachter et al., 2017).

Artefacts and governance. In practice, sustainable rule-based compliance requires more than a rules file: it requires governance artefacts, quality controls, and lifecycle management.

- *Rule catalogues and coverage tracking.* Rules are often organised in a structured catalogue (for example, domain → article/requirement → atomic rule) to track coverage, ownership, and traceability from regulation to implementation.
- *Decision tables and quality checks.* Decision tables provide a compact representation of multi-condition rules and support quality checks for completeness, consistency, and redundancy, reducing gaps and contradictions before deployment (Vanthienen & Wets, 1994).
- *Execution traces and audit trails.* Ordered rule firings and intermediate conclusions form evidence that can be translated into auditor-facing explanations. In compliance engineering, such traces are central to demonstrating conformance and diagnosing violations (Governatori & Sadiq, 2009).
- *Governance workflows and versioning.* Rule sets need lifecycle governance (draft, review, approval, deprecation) and temporal versioning to ensure point-in-time compliance and controlled change management, especially under regulatory evolution and jurisprudential shifts (Muehlen & Ho, 2006).

A concrete illustration of why versioning matters is cross-border transfer compliance after major court decisions. The Court of Justice of the European Union judgment in Case C-311/18 (*The Court of Justice Invalidates Decision 2016/1250 on the Adequacy of the Protection Provided by the EU-US Data Protection Shield*, n.d.) invalidated the EU–US Privacy Shield adequacy decision and

intensified requirements around the use of safeguards such as SCCs, forcing organisations to revisit transfer rule logic and supporting evidence.

Representative tool families. The rule-based approach is supported by several tool families, which correspond directly to the representations and governance needs described above:

- *Business Rule Management Systems (BRMS) and rule engines*, which execute production rules and can expose rule-firing traces (e.g., *Drools Rule Engine :: Drools Documentation*, n.d.).
- *Policy-as-code engines*, which treat compliance constraints as policy predicates evaluated over structured inputs (e.g., *Open Policy Agent (OPA) | Open Policy Agent*, n.d.).
- *Control catalogue and compliance interchange standards*, which provide machine-readable representations of control frameworks and assessment artefacts to support automated evidence handling (e.g., *OSCAL - Open Security Controls Assessment Language*, n.d.).
- *GDPR-oriented compliance tools* that implement guided validation workflows for specific regulatory scopes (e.g., Cambroner et al., 2022).

While rule-based compliance is effective for discrete control checks and decision points, it is costly to elicit and maintain as regulations evolve. It also struggles with open-textured terms, complex exception and conflict structures, and richer temporal requirements that demand reasoning over sequences of events and deadlines rather than isolated facts. These limitations motivate a shift to more structured approaches, such as model-driven compliance (Section 4.3), where obligations can be represented and checked as properties of processes and their executions, complementing rule-based decisioning rather than replacing it (Muehlen & Ho, 2006).

4.3 Model-driven approaches

Model-driven compliance treats compliance as a property of models that describe system structure and behaviour. Instead of checking compliance only after implementation, regulatory requirements are embedded directly into design and execution artefacts such as Unified Modeling Language (UML) models, Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN) process models, and formal behavioural models (for example, Petri nets). This framing aligns with the GDPR obligation of "data protection by design and by default" (Article 25 of the GDPR) and motivates engineering workflows where privacy and compliance constraints are made explicit, checkable, and maintainable throughout the lifecycle.

Core workflow and methodological families. In the literature and in practice, model-driven compliance typically combines three complementary families that cover different phases of the lifecycle:

- *Design-time verification (static analysis)*. Compliance constraints are checked over models before deployment, using constraint checking, static analysis, and, where appropriate, model checking. The goal is to detect non-compliance early, when remediation is cheaper and the design space is still flexible.
- *Run-time conformance checking (dynamic monitoring)*. Observed system behaviour is captured as event logs and compared against prescribed models. Deviations are detected as

conformance violations and can be linked back to specific steps, cases, or data conditions, enabling continuous compliance monitoring in operation (van der Aalst, 2016).

- *Compliance patterns (reusable templates)*. Reusable model fragments encode recurring obligations (for example, consent management, data minimisation, breach notification, and rights fulfilment). Patterns support consistency across projects and reduce the effort of repeatedly operationalising similar regulatory requirements (Agostinelli et al., 2026).

Foundational privacy engineering work motivates this shift toward embedding compliance into design artefacts. Privacy by Design (PbD) provides proactive design principles that are often treated as conceptual grounding for "by design" compliance (Cavoukian, n.d.). Engineering Privacy offers an engineering-centric synthesis of how privacy constraints can be integrated across the system lifecycle, including architectural and policy mechanisms (Engineering Privacy, 2026). Privacy Design Strategies further bridge abstract privacy goals to reusable design decisions that can be operationalised in model-driven workflows (Hoepman, 2014).

A representative design-time thread for GDPR encodes legal requirements into modelling languages with executable constraints, so that violations can be detected directly on design artefacts.

- *UML and Object Constraint Language (OCL)*. Torre et al. (2021) present a GDPR-oriented UML model and express compliance conditions using the Object Constraint Language (OCL), enabling automated checking over UML design artefacts, for example, ensuring that required elements and relationships exist or that certain constraints hold over processing concepts.
- *BPMN extensions and patterns*. For business-process-centric compliance, BPMN has been extended or constrained in several directions to make privacy and security requirements explicit at the process level:
 - Privacy-Enhanced BPMN (PE-BPMN) introduces privacy-enhanced extensions to BPMN to capture data leakages in process models and support privacy analysis at design time (Pullonen et al., 2019).
 - Complementary tool support extends this line by enabling privacy analysis of BPMN models with explicit representation of privacy-enhancing technologies and information flows (Matulevičius et al., 2020).
 - SecBPMN demonstrates how security policies can be modelled and verified over BPMN process models, providing process-level support for obligations whose enforcement depends on explicit security controls (Salnitri et al., 2014).
 - GDPR-oriented BPMN design patterns provide guidance for capturing and integrating GDPR privacy constraints into BPMN models as reusable modelling solutions (Agostinelli et al., 2026).
- *Privacy threat modelling*. Upstream of constraint checking, threat modelling supports systematic elicitation of privacy requirements so that the right constraints and patterns are introduced early in the design. LINDDUN is a privacy threat analysis framework that uses

Data Flow Diagrams (DFDs) and explicit privacy threat categories to guide this elicitation and fulfilment process (Deng et al., 2011).

Model-driven compliance can leverage formal verification when requirements can be expressed precisely and mapped to a verifiable model.

- *Model checking tools.* The SPIN model checker supports verification of behavioural properties expressed in Linear Temporal Logic (LTL), while NuSMV is a symbolic model checker that supports branching-time temporal properties such as Computation Tree Logic (CTL). These tools are used when compliance properties are best viewed as temporal constraints over behaviours, for example, "a required check must occur before a sensitive action" or "a prohibited action must never occur" (Holzmann, 2008).
- *GDPR-focused compliance formalisation.* Basin et al. (2018) present a methodology for auditing GDPR compliance grounded in purpose and necessity, illustrating how core GDPR concepts must be made explicit in a formal model before systematic verification can be applied.
- *Complementary formalisms.* Model transformation approaches show how privacy compliance information can be propagated across modelling layers (for example, transformations over data-flow representations). Policy-oriented representations can complement modelling workflows when compliance conditions are best expressed as machine-understandable policies (for example, to capture consent and regulatory obligations in a policy language).

Run-time conformance checking: process mining and declarative constraints. At run time, model-driven compliance is commonly operationalised through process mining, where event data is used to discover, compare, and check executions against reference models.

- *Process mining foundations.* Process mining uses event logs to support process discovery and conformance checking against prescribed models (van der Aalst, 2016).
- *Evidence and metrics.* Conformance checking produces interpretable evidence (for example, violating traces and localisation of deviations) and quantitative indicators such as fitness and precision (Rozinat & van der Aalst, 2008).
- *Declarative constraints.* Declare provides a constraint-based approach for expressing temporal compliance conditions over activity occurrences, particularly useful when processes are flexible and not well represented by a single rigid control-flow model (Pescic & van der Aalst, 2006)
- *Control objectives as process constraints.* Sadiq et al. (2007) provide a foundational framing for modelling control objectives and propagating them onto business process models, supporting systematic alignment between governance controls and process-level checks.
- *Practical implementation.* Process Mining for Python (PM4Py) provides a process-mining stack for discovery and conformance checking, aligning model-driven compliance monitoring with data-science pipelines used in operational analytics (Berti et al., 2019).

Model-driven engineering infrastructure and typical artefacts. Model-driven compliance relies on Model-Driven Engineering (MDE) infrastructure to define metamodels, constraints, and

transformations that keep compliance models aligned with design artefacts and, where possible, downstream implementations.

- *Eclipse Modeling Framework (EMF)* supports metamodel-based tooling, including editor and validator generation over modelling languages and domain-specific metamodels (Steinberg et al., 2009).
- *Object Constraint Language (OCL)* is a standard constraint language for specifying invariants and conditions over UML models in a tool-processable form¹⁹.
- *ATLAS Transformation Language (ATL)* supports model-to-model transformations, which can be used to propagate compliance-relevant concepts across modelling layers (Jouault et al., 2008).
- *Meta Object Facility (MOF) Query/View/Transformation (QVT)* provides a standard family of model transformation languages and mappings for synchronisation and transformation specifications²⁰.

Typical outputs span three categories: design-time artefacts (annotated UML/BPMN models, OCL constraint sets, threat-modelling artefacts such as DFDs and LINDDUN-derived requirements, and pattern libraries), run-time artefacts (event logs, declarative constraint models, conformance reports, and violation localisations), and verification outputs (counterexample traces from formal verification and conformance metrics reports from process mining).

Model-driven approaches face scalability constraints, including state-space explosion and model complexity, and a persistent model–reality gap between prescribed models and socio-technical behaviour in operation. They also encounter an expressiveness/decidability trade-off as requirements increasingly involve conflicts, exceptions, and temporally structured obligations that are difficult to capture robustly using only model constraints. These challenges motivate the adoption of normative reasoning and logic-based methods (Section 4.4), which focus on explicit representations of obligations, exceptions, conflicts, and temporal norm structures, together with inference mechanisms for resolving them under formal semantics.

4.4 Normative reasoning and logic-based methods

Normative reasoning and logic-based methods treat compliance as inference over explicit norms under a well-defined formal semantics. In contrast to rule-based checking (Section 4.2), which typically evaluates isolated control checks over structured facts, and model-driven approaches (Section 4.3), which verify properties of process and system models, normative methods represent the normative structure itself: obligations, permissions, and prohibitions; explicit exceptions and overrides; conflicts and contrary-to-duty situations; and time-bounded requirements. Given a fact base (evidence, events, states) and a formalised norm base, these methods derive compliance outcomes, violations, and in many cases the remaining pending duties together with a justification trace.

¹⁹ <https://www.omg.org/spec/OCL/2.4/PDF>

²⁰ <https://www.omg.org/spec/QVT/1.0/PDF>

Deontic logic provides the basic modalities used to encode regulatory norms, and the classical starting point is von Wright, (1951) foundational work. In its standard form, the modality set includes Obligation (O), used for mandatory requirements; Prohibition (F), used for forbidden actions; and Permission (P), used for actions that are allowed under stated conditions. These modalities, together with their formal foundations and relationship to defeasible reasoning, were introduced in Section 3.2. Many compliance-relevant norms are inherently temporal, so deontic formalisms are often extended to capture deadlines and conditional duties (for example, obligations triggered by events such as an access request, or time-bounded duties such as breach notification within a prescribed period).

For reasoning support, higher-order logic environments can embed and mechanise families of deontic logics. Benz Müller et al. (2020) present an infrastructure for automated deontic and normative reasoning that supports experimentation with alternative deontic formalisms and applications such as GDPR contrary-to-duty obligations, for example, the tension between consent withdrawal and retention duties grounded in other legal requirements.

Regulations routinely contain provisions that qualify or override one another, and a central compliance pattern is "normally X, but if exceptional condition Y then not X." This is difficult to model in classical monotonic logics without extensive meta-level encoding. Defeasible and non-monotonic approaches address this by representing priorities, exceptions, and defeat relations explicitly.

Temporal deontic defeasible logic is one approach that combines defeasible rules, temporal constraints, and deontic operators to model norm evolution and time-dependent overrides, while providing a principled conflict-resolution semantics that is often argumentation-based (Riveret & Rotolo, 2008). This family is directly motivated by compliance scenarios such as GDPR Article 17 erasure duties qualified by Article 17(3) retention exceptions. A complementary line focuses on explicit modelling of violations and their normative consequences (penalties, compensations, or remedial duties) which is essential for compliance monitoring rather than only "ideal-world" reasoning. Governatori & Sadiq, (2009) emphasise this violation-centric view and the need to connect normative specifications to observable behaviour.

Tool support exists for executing defeasible rule bases at scale. SPINdle is a defeasible logic reasoner designed as a practical execution engine for defeasible theories, supporting efficient reasoning on large rule sets and enabling embedding into applications as a rule engine (Lam & Governatori, 2009). A concrete GDPR-focused example using Defeasible Logic Programming (DeLP) is provided by Azam et, who propose a practical approach to modelling GDPR compliance with contradiction handling and explicit priorities to address undecided outcomes, and demonstrate its use on cross-border transfer scenarios including Article 46 safeguards. In applied domains, defeasible deontic formalisms have also been used in healthcare regulatory compliance contexts, illustrating how defeasible reasoning can support operational constraints and exceptions in socio-technical settings (Amantea et al., 2021).

Temporal logics. Many compliance obligations and prohibitions are naturally expressed over traces: "always," "eventually," "until," and deadline-constrained achievement obligations after a trigger. Temporal logic approaches operationalise such requirements as properties over executions.

Elgammal et al. (2011), analyse temporal and deontic logics as formal foundations for regulatory compliance specification, highlighting their role for design-time verification and their connection to model checking. In this setting:

- *Linear Temporal Logic (LTL)* is typically used to specify constraints over single execution traces.
- *Computation Tree Logic (CTL)* is used when properties must hold over branching behaviours (sets of possible evolutions), which is relevant when verifying a system model rather than one observed run.

Dynamic Linear Time Temporal Logic (DLTL) combined with Answer Set Programming (ASP) supports temporal deontic action logic encodings where compliance constraints are stated over action occurrences and ordering, and compliance is checked by solving the resulting programme. Giordano et al. (2013) develop such an approach to verify business-process compliance with norms including deadlines and contrary-to-duty obligations.

Answer Set Programming. Answer Set Programming (ASP) is widely used to represent norms and exceptions as logic rules under stable model semantics. It supports the explicit derivation of compliant and non-compliant conclusions from facts and rules, and handles exceptions and conflicts via alternative stable models when the encoding admits multiple consistent outcomes. Two widely used solver toolchains are:

- *clingo*, with multi-shot solving that supports evolving knowledge bases and repeated solving under updates, which is useful when facts arrive over time (Gebser et al., 2019)
- *DLV*, a mature system for disjunctive logic programming and knowledge representation, commonly used as an execution backend for non-monotonic encodings (Leone et al., 2020).

Answer Set Programming has also been used in compliance verification research in combination with trace reasoning and abductive explanations, showing how temporal logic and logic programming perspectives can be integrated to assess whether observed executions satisfy given properties (Chesani et al., 2018).

Event Calculus represents system evolution through events and fluents (conditions holding over intervals). It is well suited to modelling norms that constrain what must hold after event X until event Y, or to represent different types of obligations, including deadline and contrary-to-duty structures, over event streams. (Hashmi et al., 2014) propose an extension of Event Calculus to better represent obligation types and show how it supports modelling temporal aspects of norms in compliance settings.

When the goal is not only to compute compliance outcomes but to obtain machine-checked guarantees about the formalisation itself, for example, consistency, derived duties, and correct handling of contrary-to-duty structures, theorem proving becomes relevant. The LogiKEy framework provides a methodology and tool support for designing normative theories and deontic logics via semantic embeddings in higher-order logic, leveraging off-the-shelf theorem provers and model finders (Benzmüller et al., 2020). Satisfiability Modulo Theories (SMT) solvers are also frequently used as backends for constraint-based reasoning and verification. Z3 is a standard SMT solver widely used in verification contexts and can support high-assurance workflows where compliance

conditions are reduced to satisfiability problems over background theories such as arithmetic, arrays, and bit-vectors (de Moura & Bjørner, 2008).

Logic-based compliance approaches typically produce three categories of artefacts. Formal norm bases comprise deontic rule sets (obligation, permission and prohibition statements) defeasible rule bases with exceptions, overrides, and priorities, and Answer Set Programming encodings consisting of rules and constraints. Proof and solver artefacts include proof scripts and theories, for example, higher-order logic embeddings, solver configurations, and solver outputs such as stable models, derived obligations, violation flags, and counterexamples. Traceability evidence consists of explicit derivation traces indicating which rules, priorities, axioms, or proof steps were used to derive a compliance or violation outcome, supporting auditability and explanation.

These methods provide the expressiveness needed to represent exceptions, conflicts, and temporally structured obligations, but they require careful formalisation and sustained maintenance of the norm base as regulations and interpretations evolve. This connects naturally to two directions in the broader survey. The subsequent semantic and ontology-focused compliance subsections address knowledge representation choices and semantic alignment for interoperability and reuse, since many normative resources, such as GDPR norm bases encoded in LegalRuleML and aligned with PrOnto (Robaldo et al., 2020), depend on these foundations. Section 5's automation and artificial intelligence methods can reduce manual effort in norm extraction, formalisation, and update workflows while preserving the traceability and auditability requirements that are central to compliance engineering.

4.5 Semantic Web Technologies

The Semantic Web (Berners-Lee et al., 2001; Shadbolt et al., 2006) is defined by the W3C as “a common framework that allows data to be shared and reused across application, enterprise, and community boundaries, to be processed automatically by tools as well as manually, including revealing possible new relationships among pieces of data”. The paradigm of the Semantic Web is concerned with overcoming the limitations of the Hypertext Markup Language (HTML) by adding machine- and human-readable semantic information to documents, in order to improve data management and sharing as well as interoperability between systems and organizations. The Semantic Web is strongly connected to the notion of Linked Data (Berners-Lee et al., 2006), a style of publishing and linking structured data on the web, with the aim of creating a global graph of interconnected data. The Semantic Web and Linked Data rely on common standards such as URIs (Uniform Resource Identifiers)²¹ to identify resources, RDF (Resource Description Framework)²² to model information about these resources using a graph format, or SPARQL (SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language)²³ for retrieving semantic web data sources. In the legal field, and notably in the European Union, a strong emphasis is put on establishing common standards and tools for

²¹ <https://www.w3.org/Addressing/>

²² <https://www.w3.org/TR/rdf11-concepts/>

²³ <https://www.w3.org/TR/sparql11-query/>

making legal knowledge representations more interoperable, consistent and trustworthy. One of the four main levels of interoperability (Janssen et al., 2014) is semantic interoperability, for ensuring a common interpretation of information. One way to aim for semantic interoperability is to develop ontologies and other representations that can be reasoned with using semantic technologies. For this purpose, data is described using metadata to add relevant semantic or contextual information such as definitions, author names, dates and time, etc.

The development of the Semantic Web is essential for the management of legal knowledge, notably because it supports automated legal reasoning and information extraction, and improves the explainability of AI systems by providing a common knowledge ground for both humans and machines. In the construction industry, a significant amount of research on Semantic Web methods has already been done for compliance checking against legal building requirements through building information modelling (BIM) (Guo et al., 2021; Jia et al., 2025; Li et al., 2023). Although these tools and methods don't apply directly to AI and data regulations, some of them remain relevant across domains.

Ontologies and vocabularies also play a major role in the Semantic Web architecture, and will be discussed more at length in subsection 4.6. This subsection is focused on Semantic Web standards, methods and tools that can be used side by side with ontologies to build legal knowledge representations useful for compliance checking.

4.5.1 General Semantic Web standards:

The two main goals of Semantic Web standards is to ensure the consistency of knowledge and to make the implicit meaning of knowledge explicit.

One of the main pillars of the Semantic Web is naming conventions. They are essential in the legal domain, to precisely and accurately identify pieces of legislation, and thus support their legal validity. URIs (Uniform Resource Identifiers) are the union of URLs (Uniform Resource Locators) and URNs (Uniform Resource Names). These naming conventions identify abstract and physical objects on the web. They are used in combination with other Semantic Web methods to model identified resources.

Among these methods is another pillar of the Semantic Web: the Resource Description Framework, also called RDF (Robaldo et al., 2023). RDF is a W3C-recommended formal vocabulary and one of the basic "blocks" of the Semantic Web. Its aim is to describe and exchange knowledge in the form of a graph – in other words, to represent Linked Data.

Modelling vocabularies

The RDF Schema, or RDFS²⁴, is an extension of the basic RDF vocabulary that provides a mechanism for describing groups of related resources, and is thus used to structure RDF data by using classes and properties. In short, RDFS is a vocabulary to model RDF vocabularies.

²⁴ <https://www.w3.org/TR/rdf-schema/>

Another vocabulary built on the RDF standard is the Web Ontology Language, also known as OWL²⁵ or OWL 2, its latest extended version (Francesconi & Governatori, 2023). OWL is a W3C ontology language and approved standard. It provides some advanced concepts that RDFS lacks, such as cardinality restrictions on properties or transitive properties. OWL offers formal semantics for designing ontologies by describing classes, properties, individuals, and data values. There are three OWL sublanguages, listed in an increasing order of expressiveness:

- OWL-Lite, which is syntactically simpler;
- OWL-DL, which is much more expressive than OWL-Lite and uses Description Logics (DL), allowing automated reasoning. Ontologies that conform to OWL-DL can be checked for inconsistencies. This feature is useful for legal reasoning;
- OWL-Full is the most expressive OWL sublanguage. Its level of expressiveness does not allow automated reasoning.

Along with RDFS and OWL, SKOS²⁶ is a modeling vocabulary for linking and sharing knowledge. Unlike the other two, it is not a formal language. SKOS is a more lightweight method for modelling thesauri or taxonomies, for instance. It can be used alone or in combination with formal languages like OWL²⁷.

Syntaxes

RDF graphs and datasets can be encoded in a variety of syntax notations and formats, with the most common being triple-based syntaxes like N-Triples²⁸, Turtle²⁹, TriG³⁰, JSON-based syntaxes like JSON-LD (Kellogg et al., 2019) and XML-based syntaxes like RDF-XML³¹.

Performing operations on RDF graphs

Different types of operations can be performed on data expressed in the form of RDF graphs. For instance, it is possible to formulate queries with SPARQL³² across diverse RDF data sources, while SHACL (Shapes Constraint Language)³³ can be used to validate RDF data that could not be validated using OWL and SPARQL, against sets of conditions that are also expressed as graphs.

The methods we just introduced form the ground base of the Semantic Web, but many others could be cited (Casanovas et al., 2016). For instance, reasoners like Pellet (Sirin et al., 2007) or HermiT (Glimm et al., 2014), make it possible to infer logical consequences from data. Ontology

²⁵ <https://www.w3.org/TR/owl2-syntax/>

²⁶ <https://www.w3.org/TR/skos-reference/>

²⁷ <https://www.w3.org/2006/07/SWD/SKOS/skos-and-owl/master.html#Summary>

²⁸ <https://dvcs.w3.org/hg/rdf/raw-file/default/rdf-turtle/n-triples.html>

²⁹ <https://dvcs.w3.org/hg/rdf/raw-file/default/rdf-turtle/>

³⁰ <https://www.w3.org/TR/trig/>

³¹ <https://www.w3.org/TR/rdf12-xml/>

³² <https://www.w3.org/TR/sparql11-query/>

³³ <https://www.w3.org/TR/shacl/>

development has been facilitated by the creation of editors like Protégé (Knublauch et al., 2004) and visualization tools such as VOWL (Lohmann et al., 2014).

4.5.2 The Semantic Web for law

Naming conventions

As stated above, naming conventions are essential for identifying legal texts, with standards being implemented in the EU for a uniform and coherent representation of legal sources. Among them, the CEN MetaLex³⁴ “Open XML Interchange Format for Legal and Legislative Resources” developed during the CEN Workshop on an Open XML interchange format (Palmirani, Cervone, et al., 2011), and the Akoma Ntoso naming convention³⁵ based on an OASIS standard, both provide a standardized way of presenting legal sources in XML. The European Legislation identifier (ELI) and European Case Law Identifier (ECLI) are two RDF-compliant standards that provide technical specifications for Web identifiers – one for laws and regulations, and the other for court rulings – and suggestions for vocabularies to be used to describe metadata pertaining to legal documents in a machine readable format (Filtz et al., 2021). UNR:LEX is another more global standard for identifying legal sources, including legislation, case law, and administrative acts. Unlike ELI and ECLI, it is not EU-specific.

Languages and frameworks

On top of more general Semantic Web vocabularies like RDF, RDFS or OWL, some languages are especially relevant for the legal domain.

This is the case of the Semantic Web Rule Language, or SWRL³⁶ (Pittl & Fill, 2020), which can be used to extend W3C standards like OWL and RDF in order to better describe rules with simple classical logic. It is not flexible and expressive enough to handle complex situations like exceptions or suspensions of rules.

The Open Digital Rights Language, or ODRL³⁷, is another W3C recommendation, specific to digital rights. ODRL is not a full legal reasoning framework. It is primarily a policy expression language that provides an information model and a vocabulary for specifying permissions, prohibitions, and obligations about the usage of digital assets and services (Roshankish & Fornara, 2024). De Vos (2019) proposes a method for checking compliance against GDPR regulations modelled with an ODRL profile (De Vos et al., 2019).

Not directly linked to the Semantic Web, but nonetheless essential for legal knowledge representation, RuleML (Boley et al., 2010) is a family of XML-based languages designed to model rules. LegalRuleML (Palmirani, Governatori, Rotolo, et al., 2011) is an extension of RuleML and an

³⁴ <http://www.metalex.eu>

³⁵ <https://docs.oasis-open.org/legaldocml/akn-nc/v1.0/akn-nc-v1.0.html>

³⁶ <https://www.w3.org/submissions/SWRL/>

³⁷ <https://www.w3.org/TR/odrl-model/>

OASIS markup standard, designed specifically for legal norms and reasoning. Unlike RuleML, it features deontic concepts and rule priorities, allowing it to handle legal conflicts.

Akoma Ntoso (Barabucci, Cervone, Di Iorio, et al., 2010) is another OASIS standard³⁸. It is an XML vocabulary for legal documents, whose main objective is to add semantic information on top of legal text in natural language. Akoma Ntoso provides a markup language for identifying structures based on common legal patterns and references to other legal documents based on URIs, and allows the tracking of non-authoritative metadata. Structures are identified and marked up according to an XML vocabulary based on common patterns found in legal documents. References to legal documents across countries are made using a common naming convention based on URIs.

The Legal Knowledge Interchange Format, or LKIF (Gordon, 2008), is an important framework built on Semantic Web foundations for representing and exchanging legal knowledge in a structured way, with support for legal reasoning. It is an XML schema represented in OWL, developed by the ESTRELLA Project (2008). Like LegalRuleML, LKIF features defeasible rule language.

These frameworks and languages can prove very useful for building methods and tools for compliance checking. They can be used side by side to model legal norms and their logic, against which concrete facts and actions can be checked for compliance. Ontologies and knowledge graphs are also an essential feature of the Semantic Web for information management and retrieval. Considering the richness of the literature on legal ontologies, they will be further explored in the following section.

4.6 Ontologies and Knowledge Representation

In the last decades, the concept of ontology and its practical implementation have evolved from its origins within expert systems (Araszkiwicz et al., 2022). Today, ontologies can be described as conceptual models for knowledge representation and reasoning. They achieve a common understanding of domain knowledge by providing information that is both human- and machine-readable. This is done by defining the meaning of a set of language units and their relationship in formal language. For this reason, they are a key infrastructure of the semantic web and AI systems, as they facilitate data formalization, reuse and sharing.

In this section, we will first present the general classification of ontologies proposed by Roussey (2011), before introducing key ontologies used in the field of legal knowledge modelling, with a focus on compliance checking.

It is difficult to give a precise definition of ontologies. They can range from “lightweight” ontologies like lexicons (Peters et al., 2007) to more complex models integrating constraints and logic. Thus, they can take various forms, based on their scope and purpose (Roussey et al., 2011):

- a thesaurus in the field of information retrieval;
- a model represented in OWL in the field of linked-data;
- a XML schema in the context of databases.

³⁸ <https://www.oasis-open.org/standard/akn-v1-0/>

4.6.1 Classifying ontologies

Roussey (2011) proposes two classifications of ontologies, the first one based on the expressivity and formality of the languages used: natural language, formal language, etc.; and the second one based on the scope of the objects described by the ontology.

The first classification organizes ontologies based on their level of formality, from low to high:

- *Information ontologies* are diagrams and sketches used to clarify and organize ideas. They are destined to humans, not machines.
- *Terminological ontologies* take the form of glossaries, dictionaries, controlled vocabularies, taxonomies, thesauri, or lexical databases... They are used for disambiguating and defining common vocabulary.
 - Languages used: Simple Knowledge Organization System (SKOS) and Resource Description Framework (RDF) recommended by the W3C for creating meta-data structures on the web.
 - Example: the EUROVOC thesaurus for the creation of a EUROVOC ontology schema.
- *Software ontologies* are used for data storage and data manipulation in software development activities, and integrate constraints on top of concept definitions.
 - Languages used: Unified Modeling Language (UML).
- *Formal ontologies* represent the highest degree of formality. This type of ontology relies on strict rules about how to define concepts and relationships and integrates logical definitions, usually based on first-order logic or description logic. Because of this, formal ontologies are not used simply to retrieve and store data, but also to reason with it.
 - Languages used: Web Ontology Language (OWL), including OWL Lite, OWL DL and OWL Full.

For legal knowledge modelling, *formal ontologies* are preferred because of their higher degree of formalization and, more importantly, because they allow data reasoning – an integral part of automatized and semi-automatized compliance checking. The second classification identified by Roussey (2011) is based on the scope of ontologies, in other words, on the level of specialization of the objects they conceptualize:

- *Foundational or upper-level ontologies* are generic, domain-independent ontologies. They can be used as a base to create core or domain ontologies, as their reuse facilitates the development of new ontologies.
 - Example: the Descriptive Ontology for Linguistic and Cognitive Engineering (DOLCE) and the Unified Foundational Ontology (UFO) are two formal foundational ontologies.
- *Core ontologies* are used as a standard to define core concepts in a broad field (like the legal field). They are composed of different domain ontologies and provide the key concepts of a field. Core ontologies can be extended with lexical or task-specific extensions (Peters et al., 2007).

- Example: the Core Legal Ontology (CLO) expresses the basic concepts of law.
- *Domain ontologies* have a more restricted scope and cover a more specialized area or task.
 - Example: IPRONTO is a domain ontology specialized for Intellectual Property Rights management.
- *Local or application ontologies* are single-purpose ontologies designed to be used by a restricted group of people or for a single task.

The state-of-the-art language for knowledge modelling in the Semantic Web is OWL and is used for creating a number of ontologies such as LRI-Core, LKIF, CLO, DALOS or PrOnto, that will be further explained below.

The literature on full-fledged ontologies designed for compliance checking in the domain of AI and data regulations is still scarce. However, various ontologies have been developed for the legal domain, with each of them giving the possibility to model a specific aspect of legal knowledge. In the context of compliance checking, ontologies can help achieve a common understanding of legal requirements and of real-world facts, and facilitate legal reasoning. We will present some of the main ontologies that can be used to help check compliance, with varying scopes and specificities. We will start from upper-level, more generic ontologies before moving on to more specific ontologies, as the latter often derive from the former.

4.6.2 Foundational or upper-level ontologies

Foundational ontologies are the most general and formal ontologies. The main two foundational ontologies used for legal knowledge modelling are the following:

- The Descriptive Ontology for Linguistic and Cognitive Engineering, also called DOLCE (Masolo et al., 2003), is the first top-level (or foundational) ontology and was created more than twenty years ago. It remains largely used in a variety of domains. It does not provide domain knowledge but general categories (endurant, perdurant, quality, abstract) and relations, that can be specialized based on its application by integrating knowledge specific to the domain to be modeled. Building domain ontologies based on a DOLCE foundation, which is stable and interoperable, is ideal for bridging different domains. DOLCE is axiomatized in first-order logic (Borgo et al., 2022; Gangemi et al., 2003).
 - DOLCE+ is an extension of DOLCE developed in the WonderWeb and Metokis EU projects. It is extended by the “Descriptions and Situations” ontology (D&S) and contains modules dedicated to core ontologies of contexts, time, space, plans, etc. (Gangemi et al., 2005).
- The Unified Foundational Ontology, or UFO (Guizzardi et al., 2015, 2022), is another upper level ontology, grounded in philosophical logic, linguistics and cognitive psychology, that has been developed for over twenty years. UFO is also axiomatised in first-order modal logics. It is used as the basis of a legal core ontology described in the next subsection, UFO-L.

4.6.3 Core ontologies

Core ontologies are modular and extensible, and typically model a small set of concepts that can apply to a broad domain. For this reason, they hardly become out-of-date and can be used as a foundation to create more specific domain ontologies (Scherp et al., 2011). Core ontologies for the legal domain can be indirectly used for compliance checking with other methods. They capture statutes, roles and normative relations (Schnitzhofer & Schuetz, 2025). The main legal core ontologies are the following:

- The Functional Ontology for Law (FOLaw) (Valente & Breuker, 1995), was originally designed as a core ontology to describe and explain dependencies between types of knowledge in legal reasoning. It is closer to an epistemological framework than an ontology, since it is concerned with the types of knowledge in legal reasoning rather than with legal knowledge itself. For this reason, its reuse is limited (Van Engers et al., 2008). It distinguishes six categories of legal knowledge: normative knowledge, world knowledge, responsibility knowledge, reactive knowledge, meta-legal knowledge, and creative knowledge.
 - Example of use: the ONtology-based Legal INformation Environment (ON-LINE) (Valente & Breuker, 1995) is an architecture for legal reasoning that uses a representation of legal knowledge based on FOLaw.
- The LRI-Core ontology (Breuker et al., 2005) was developed to overcome the shortcomings of FOLaw, considered to be closer to an epistemological framework than a core ontology, which limits its reuse (Breuker & Hoekstra, 2004). LRI-Core captures abstract commonsense concepts and adapts them for legal information processing, encompassing a broad range of concepts common to all legal fields. Foundational ontologies with a more concrete or mathematical scope like SUMO or the IEEE-Standard Upper Ontology are not as well suited for law, a domain that deals with more abstract categories of knowledge linked to the social world. For this reason, the foundational layer of LRI-Core was created using FOLaw. LRI-Core is relatively light with around 300 concepts and is expressed in OWL-DL (Van Engers et al., 2008). One of its drawbacks is that it covers a small number of legal concepts and remains quite generic (Deroy et al., 2024).
- The Core Legal Ontology (CLO) (Gangemi et al., 2005) is a specialisation of an extension of DOLCE, the Descriptions and Situations ontology (D&S). It introduces legal subclasses in place of the D&S categories. CLO is used to support the definition of domain ontologies, the definition of a juridical wordnet, and the design of legal decision support systems (Gangemi et al., 2005).
 - Example of use: Gangemi et al. provide an example of using CLO, JurWordNet and DOLCE+ for assessing compliance between European Commission directives and national legislations (Gangemi et al., 2003).
- The Legal Knowledge Interchange Format Core (LKIF-Core) (Hoekstra et al., 2007) is one of the most important core ontologies for law, developed in the European ESTRELLA project. It uses a combination of two formalisms, OWL-DL and SWRL, and complies with current semantic web standards. LKIF-Core reuses part of the top-level of LRI-Core and aims to propose a knowledge representation formalism that can support a broad architecture for

the creation of legal knowledge systems. On top of this, its goal is to enable the translation between legal knowledge bases written in different representation formats and formalisms.

- Example of use: the framework proposed by Oyasiji uses a knowledge graph based on LKIF-Core and LegalRuleML for contextual legal reasoning (Oyasiji et al., 2024).
- UFO-L, a legal core ontology, has been introduced based on the UFO foundational ontology (Griffo et al., 2016). UFO-L adopts a relational perspective rather than normative perspective. In other words, it is designed to model legal roles and relations rather than legal norms. In that sense, it is most useful to model legal relations and contracts, and is less prominent than DOLCE in the domain of compliance-checking, since it is less adequate for modelling legal requirements and real-world facts.

4.6.4 “Lightweight” ontologies

There is no formal, consensual definition of lightweight ontologies, but they can be described as ontologies that incorporate lighter sets of logic constraints, while still providing explicit conceptualization and classification of concepts. Lightweight ontologies are a large spectrum and include controlled vocabularies, taxonomies, thesauri, and web directories, among others (Giunchiglia & Zaihrayeu, 2008).

- JurWordNet is an ontology-driven semantic lexicon, designed as an extension of the Italian version of EuroWordNet and used for semantic tagging and information retrieval. It is compliant with CLO (Gangemi et al., 2005). JurWordNet covers a broad range of legal concepts and can be seen as a link between domain ontologies and legislative texts. The LOIS Project extended this legal knowledge base to five other languages, Dutch, Portuguese, German, Czech and English (Peters et al., 2006).
- EUROVOC is a frequently updated multilingual and multidisciplinary thesaurus managed by the Publications Office of the European Union. Its aim is to index the documents issued by the European Union Institutions in order to ease their retrieval. EUROVOC is not strictly legal but provides domain-knowledge about the different fields of competence of the European Union (Leone et al., 2020).
- The European Legal Taxonomy Syllabus, or ELTS (Ajani et al., 2017), is a multilingual and multijurisdictional vocabulary used to model the legal terminology created by the Uniform Terminology project on EU consumer protection law. It is enriched with concepts denoted by vocabulary entries, with semantic relations between different concepts.
- The European Legislation Identifier (ELI) ontology is a technical standard based on voluntary agreement for modelling legal documents, focused on interoperability between European Union countries. It is notably used by the Publication Office. It relies on a shared and uniform set of metadata inspired by FRBR principles (Avgerinos Loutsaris et al., 2023; Leone et al., 2020).
- The AkomaNtoso ontology is an OASIS XML standard designed for the structural representation of parliamentary, legislative and judiciary documents (Avgerinos Loutsaris et al., 2023).

- The Data Catalogue vocabulary (DCAT)³⁹ is an RDF vocabulary for describing metadata of public sector datasets in Europe. It is the standard used by the European Data Portal (Avgerinos Loutsaris et al., 2023).
- The Normative Requirements Vocabulary (NRV) (Gandon et al., n.d.) is an ontology that extends LegalRuleML for the representation of normative requirements and rules. NRV organizes the three main deontic operators – permission, prohibition and obligation – in a hierarchical structure according to different criteria which concern: the need for compensation, the possibility to breach or fulfil a requirement and the temporal aspects involved in their validity and compliance (Leone et al., 2020).
- VAIR (Golpayegani et al., 2023) is an open vocabulary for AI risk for representing and assisting with AI risk assessments in a form that supports automation and integration. VAIR is intended to assist with identification and documentation of risks by providing a common vocabulary that facilitates knowledge sharing and interoperability between actors in the AI value chain.

4.6.5 Domain ontologies

Domain ontologies are more specialised than core ontologies, but vary in scope. In the legal field, domain ontologies can, for example, be used to represent knowledge related to a specific type of legal document or piece of legislation - like privacy policies or the GDPR - or to a legal sub-domain, like criminal law or labor law. They provide a formal representation of a specific domain and a common understanding of the meaning of terms within a discipline (McDaniel & Storey, 2019). The most relevant domain ontologies for compliance checking against AI and data regulations include:

- GDPRov, GConsent and GDPRtEXT (Pandit et al., 2018, 2019), are GDPR-specific ontologies designed to represent processes, consent, and the GDPR text, respectively. Using these vocabularies with a linked-data approach allows organizations to link queries and results directly to the relevant text, thereby making it possible to record and measure their solutions for compliance towards specific obligations.
- The PrOnto ontology (Palmirani et al., 2018) uses defeasible deontic operators to model legal norms from the GDPR. It models the GDPR's main concepts such as agents and roles, data types and documents, legal bases and processing purposes. PrOnto is designed to support information retrieval and provide a model compatible with legal reasoning and compliance-checking techniques (Delorme et al., 2022; Leone et al., 2020).
- PrivOnto (Oltramari et al., 2018) is a semantic framework developed under the Usable Privacy Policy (UPP) project and used for the analysis of privacy policies. It relies on an ontology that models privacy practice statements, populated with about 23,000 annotations of data practices.
- The Provenance Ontology (PROV-O) (Prudhomme et al., 2025) is a W3C recommended ontology that “provides a set of classes, properties, and restrictions that can be used to

³⁹ <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-3/>

represent and interchange provenance information generated in different systems and under different contexts”⁴⁰.

- The Linked Data Rights Ontology⁴¹ is an extension of the ODRL ontology developed by the Ontology Engineering Group of Universidad Politécnica de Madrid that provides the vocabulary for modelling the conditions of use of the Linked Data resources. It concerns, but is not restricted to, intellectual property rights, as it is designed to represent the actions permitted on a resource protected by the intellectual property rights (Leone et al., 2020).
- The DALOS ontology is an ontology of consumer law developed by the European Commission DALOS project⁴², building on the LOIS dataset.
- The Data Privacy Vocabulary (DPV)⁴³ is taxonomical modelling of concepts associated with personal data processing based on the GDPR, produced by the W3C Data Privacy Vocabularies and Controls Community Group (DPVCG) (J. Pandit et al., 2025). The concepts of the DPV ontology enable the expression of information such as data and technologies involved, their purposes and legal basis, measures used for security, relevant laws and rights, and associated risks and impacts. DPV is made interoperable through the use of RDF and other Semantic Web standards, as well as taxonomies based on real-world applications. DPV can be specialized through extensions (Personal Data, Risk Assessment and Management, Locations, etc.), and is still regularly updated.
- HealthDCAT-AP⁴⁴ is a domain-specific metadata model designed to support the implementation of the secondary use framework under the European Health Data Space (EHDS). It does not focus on health data itself but rather on metadata, to harmonise descriptions of health datasets across EU catalogues, to support cross-border discovery and secondary use of health data for research, innovation and public health policy.
- MLDCAT-AP⁴⁵ (the Machine Learning Data Catalogue Application profile) is another extension of DCAT-AP, developed by the SEMIC team. Similarly to HEALTH-DCAT, it provides a metadata model specific to AI and machine learning, to support the safe reuse of datasets across organizations.
- The AI Risk Ontology (AIRO) (Golpayegani et al., 2022) is an open source ontology that provides a minimal set of concepts for representing AI systems as per the requirements of the AI Act with the risk and impacts being represented based on ISO 31000 family of standards.

In short, ontologies are an essential part of legal knowledge modelling, and more generally of the Semantic Web. The diversity of scopes and purposes makes ontologies difficult to compare with each other, unless they are roughly designed for the same purpose. In the context of

⁴⁰ <https://www.w3.org/TR/2013/REC-prov-o-20130430/>

⁴¹ <https://oeg-upm.github.io/vocabUpdates/site/ontologies/purl.oclc.org/NETldrns.html>

⁴² <https://interoperable-europe.ec.europa.eu/collection/justice-law-and-security/document/dalos-project-dalos>

⁴³ <https://w3c.github.io/dpv/2.2/dpv/>

⁴⁴ <https://healthdataeu.pages.code.europa.eu/healthdcat-ap/releases/release-6/>

⁴⁵ <https://semiceu.github.io/MLDCAT-AP/releases/2.0.0/>

compliance checking, ontologies are a precious resource to represent abstract concepts such as normative constraints, roles and processes, as well as more concrete objects such as people and behaviors.

4.6.6 Legal Knowledge Graphs

Ontologies can also be used as a foundational structure and populated to create Knowledge Graphs (KG). Knowledge Graphs are also essential for legal representation, as they organize data by linking entities, relationships and attributes. Falcarin et al. propose to identify the matches between regulatory texts (AI Act, Cyber Resilience Act, NIS2 and Digital Services Act) and other relevant documents (such as the Software Requirements Specification) by aligning two Knowledge Graphs. In doing this, they aim at assessing compliance with the requirements with the development of an auditor-oriented compliance tool. The advantage of such a knowledge representation is that it can be easily visualized and analysed by legal experts (Falcarin et al., 2025). Joshi et al. present another Knowledge Graph of data protection regulations that apply to Cloud data. Since these data compliance regulations have overlapping rules, but are not referencing each other, capturing them in a Knowledge Graph helps providers to comply with each regulation (Joshi et al., 2020). Knowledge Graphs are very versatile and can be developed to represent different aspects of law, specific regulations and requirements, or even processes for facilitating compliance.

Keeping ontologies and knowledge graphs up-to-date and complete is a time-consuming and costly task. A possible solution is using NLP techniques for knowledge-extraction to create and update Knowledge Graphs (Khorshidi et al., 2025; Sumukh & Shashwat, 2024). Sovrano et al. propose an alternative solution based on Open Knowledge Extraction (OKE) and natural language processing: the extraction of concepts and their relations, from a natural language text, modelled in the form of a graph where concepts are nodes and relations are edges. The end result is a Knowledge Graph with a structure closer to that of an ontology, aligned with Ontology Design Patterns (ODP) (Gangemi, 2007), that can be used for Question Answering (Sovrano et al., 2020).

5 AUTOMATED AND AI-BASED METHODOLOGIES

5.1 Use of AI in Extraction, Assessment and Checking Compliance

Automated and AI-based methodologies have become a central pillar in contemporary compliance practice, particularly in regulatory domains characterised by dense, evolving, and text-intensive legal frameworks such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the Digital Services Act (DSA), and the AI Act. These regimes can generate complex corpora of primary legislation, delegated acts, guidance documents, enforcement decisions, contracts, and internal policies. Manual analysis of such materials is resource-intensive, difficult to scale, and prone to inconsistency. AI-driven methods seek to operationalise legal text by transforming unstructured documents into structured, machine-readable representations that can support monitoring, verification, risk assessment, and reporting.

At a technical level, this includes multiple layers of automation. First, Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques enable the parsing, segmentation, and semantic annotation of legal texts. Core task families include document summarisation, legal named entity recognition (L-NER), text mining and information retrieval. These methods serve as the backbone for compliance tooling by identifying actors (e.g. controllers, processors, supervisory authorities), extracting deontic elements (obligations, permissions, prohibitions), and mapping references across regulatory instruments. Both rule-based systems and machine learning architectures, ranging from simple statistical parsing to transformer-based models, are deployed to capture the syntactic and semantic regularities of legal drafting.

Second, specialised pipelines combine statistical modelling, ontological structuring, and explainable AI (XAI) components to detect compliance-relevant patterns in large decision corpora. Topic modelling, semantic graph construction, and structured extraction approaches allow practitioners to surface enforcement trends, penalty rationales, and recurring risk indicators in a reproducible and auditable manner. These hybrid frameworks illustrate a broader shift from purely descriptive analytics towards computational compliance intelligence.

Third, generative AI and large language models (LLMs) introduce a more flexible interaction paradigm. Domain-adapted models such as LEGAL-BERT, built on BERT, as well as fine-tuned compliance-oriented systems derived from foundation models, extend the automation spectrum beyond information extraction to include regulatory interpretation, requirement generation, retrieval-augmented reasoning, and conversational access to legal sources. Architectures based on retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) and knowledge graphs further bridge symbolic and statistical AI, aiming to reconcile general linguistic capability with domain-specific legal accuracy.

Finally, beyond text-centric NLP, machine learning techniques support compliance in operational contexts, such as anomaly detection for data breach identification or fraud monitoring. In these applications, compliance is not inferred from legal language itself but from behavioural or system-level signals that are evaluated against regulatory thresholds (e.g. breach notification timelines).

Taken together, automated and AI-based methodologies represent a continuum: from linguistic preprocessing and rule extraction, through ontology-enhanced modelling and explainable analytics, to generative reasoning and proactive risk detection. The following subsections examine these approaches in detail, analysing their methodological foundations, representative tools, and suitability for compliance with AI and data governance frameworks.

5.2 Natural Language Processing for Legal Texts

Natural language processing (NLP) has become a central enabling technology for working with the large, heterogeneous bodies of text that underpin AI and data regulation, including statutes, regulatory guidance, standards, contracts, and internal organisational policies. At a high level, modern legal NLP systems cover a broad spectrum of tasks, ranging from low-level linguistic processing (tokenisation, sentence splitting, part-of-speech tagging) to high-level analyses that approximate legal reasoning. Recent surveys highlight that legal document summarisation, legal named entity recognition (L-NER), legal question answering (LQA), argument mining, text and clause classification, and judgment or outcome prediction have emerged as core task families around which datasets and benchmarks are being organised (Ariai et al., 2026). For compliance checking in AI and data legislation, this toolbox is particularly relevant: document summarisation helps distil long regulatory texts or privacy policies into compliance-relevant synopses; named entity recognition (NER) and related extraction methods identify entities such as controllers, processors, supervisory authorities, and jurisdictions; text mining and information retrieval can surface obligations, justifications, and exceptions within legislation or case law; and finally, generative AI has introduced a novel way of accessible and comprehensive interaction with regulatory requirements, as well as enhanced existing approaches. The following subsections will detail the state of methods and tools for these tasks.

First, as the variety of its capability hinders its categorisation into a definitive task, we need to present *LexNLP* (Bommarito et al., 2018). This Python library is designed for legal and regulatory text, and includes numerous functionalities, such as document segmentation, key text identification, information type extraction, named entity recognition, text feature transformation, and the development of unsupervised and supervised models.

5.2.1 Legal Document Summarisation

Legal Document Summarisation (LDS) focuses on condensing complex legal texts, such as court judgments, into concise and accurate summaries. Unlike general summarisation, LDS must follow the structure and terminology of legal documents, which include citations, statutory language, and sectioned formats. Methods are either extractive, selecting key sentences directly, or abstractive, generating paraphrased summaries that preserve meaning.

Recent datasets support both approaches. *Multi-LexSum* contains 40,000 U.S. civil rights cases with expert-written summaries (Shen et al., 2022), while the *Common Law Court Judgment Summarisation* (CLSum) (Liu et al., 2024) covers multi-jurisdictional common law judgments from countries like Australia, the UK, and Canada, using LLM-based data augmentation and sparse attention to handle long documents.

Early systems such as *FLEXICON* (Gelbart & Smith, 1991), *SALOMON* (Moens et al., 1999), and *LetSum* (Farzindar & Lapalme, 2004) relied on keyword detection and text structuring. Later, Machine Learning, such as *Casesummarizer* (Polsley et al., 2016), and Reinforcement Learning approaches were introduced (Nguyen et al., 2021). Generally, LDS has evolved from rule-based systems to hybrid, deep learning models that better capture the complexity, precision, and interpretive nuance of legal language.

5.2.2 Named Entity Recognition

Named Entity Recognition (NER) identifies and classifies text mentions into predefined categories such as persons, organisations, or locations. In the legal domain, NER extends to domain-specific entities like laws, legal norms, and procedural terms, making it vital for structuring legal documents and improving information retrieval. Because legal texts are highly formal and complex, specialised systems tailored to their structure and terminology are essential.

Several key datasets support legal NER research. Leitner et al. (2020) developed a large German legal corpus of 67,000 sentences and over two million tokens, with 54,000 manually annotated entities across 19 fine-grained classes (e.g., court, law, legal literature) and 35,000 time expressions. Păis et al. (2021) introduced *LegalNERo*, a Romanian dataset of 370 legal documents annotated for five entity types, including legal references converted into RDF. Au et al. (2022) released *E-NER*, derived from U.S. SEC EDGAR filings, featuring seven adapted classes (person, organisation, government, court, business, legislation/act, location). Kalamkar et al. (2022) created an Indian corpus with 46,545 entities from Supreme Court and High Court judgments (1950–2022), divided into preamble and judgment sections and covering entities such as petitioner, respondent, and statute. Together, these datasets provide multilingual, fine-grained data tailored for legal applications.

Early approaches such as (Dozier et al., 2010) combined lookup methods, contextual rules, and statistical models to identify legal entities in U.S. case law. Later models introduced neural architectures: Păis et al. (2021) combined Bi-LSTM and Conditional Random Fields (CRF) with pre-trained word and character embeddings, legal gazetteers, and ensemble evaluations to improve accuracy. Finally, Smădu et al. (2022) explored cross-lingual domain adaptation using BERT, Bi-LSTM, and CRF layers, employing adversarial learning via a gradient reversal mechanism to reduce domain bias, with mixed results across German and Romanian data.

5.2.3 Text Mining and Legal Information Retrieval

Natural language processing (NLP) methods have become central to automating the analysis and interpretation of legal texts for compliance checking in AI and data regulation. One prominent line of work focuses on extracting structured information from large corpora of enforcement decisions. For instance, Orlando & Santoro (2025) develop an explainable NLP pipeline to extract details of fines from more than 1,900 GDPR enforcement cases. Their system integrates domain-specific preprocessing, keyness statistics, and WordNet-based semantic graphs with a Structural Topic Model (STM) (Roberts et al., 2014) to identify latent “enforcement topics.” The pipeline scrapes and cleans raw text, normalizes synonyms, extracts references to specific GDPR articles, and labels fine tiers and amounts, transforming unstructured decisions into a structured dataset suitable

for automated compliance analytics. By coupling topic modeling (via Latent Dirichlet Allocation (Blei et al., 2003)) with semantic graph representations, the approach surfaces interpretable links between enforcement rationales and penalty severity—helping practitioners detect recurring risk signals and compliance patterns across diverse jurisdictions.

Beyond enforcement analysis, several systems have aimed to formalize the representation of rights and obligations directly from regulatory texts. The Gaius T tool, built on the Cerno framework (Kiyavitskaya et al., 2008), exemplifies this line of research. It applies TXL-based semantic annotation and custom grammars to parse regulations into structural elements such as rights, obligations, constraints, and actors. Domain-specific linguistic indicators and legal-heuristic rules identify continuations and cross-references, creating a structured model that can be exported for downstream compliance or requirements analysis. This enables automatic mapping from natural language regulation to machine-readable compliance artifacts.

Rule extraction at the level of regulatory events extends these methodologies further. Adam and Wim (2011) propose an event-recognition approach implemented within the GATE architecture through rule-based NLP components such as gazetteers and JAPE rules applied to Stanford Parser outputs. Their system targets the identification of deontic and conditional rules, capturing elements like agent, theme, operator, and antecedent–consequent relations, while mapping syntactic structure to semantic roles via VerbNet. Through iterative evaluation against a gold standard, the method balances automation with expert review to refine extraction accuracy in complex legislative texts.

Hybrid frameworks combine symbolic and statistical NLP to improve the robustness of legal rule discovery. Dragoni et al. (2016) introduce a mixed pipeline that integrates ontological text chunking, syntactic parsing, and WordNet-enriched semantic labeling to recognize machine-readable deontic rules (obligations, permissions, and prohibitions) within legal documents. Sentences are parsed into grammatical trees using the Stanford Parser, annotated with deontic indicators, and formalized into rule templates such as “O Term1 WHERE Term2.” By incorporating logical dependency modeling through Combinatory Categorical Grammar (CCG) and Boxer, this hybrid system achieves approximately 80% precision in extracting compliance-relevant rules from the Australian Telecommunications Code.

Taken together, these approaches demonstrate how modern NLP techniques, ranging from XAI-informed topic modeling to ontology-driven rule extraction, can transform legal texts into structured, analysable representations. Such systems form a foundational layer for automated compliance checking, supporting transparency, interpretability, and adaptability in AI and data governance contexts.

Kensho *NERD*⁴⁶ is a proprietary tool that extracts entities and information from text and links them to existing datasets, such as Wikipedia. According to Kensho’s own blog, the tool can be used for contract analysis, risk identification, non-compliance issue identification and overall compliance checking (Oyesiku, 2023).

⁴⁶ <https://kensho.com/nerd>

Luminance' proprietary *Comply* platform⁴⁷ offers a “comprehensive understanding of contractual obligations across the business”, enabled by a “conceptual understanding of individual words, concepts and context” (Luminance, 2025). However, due to it being proprietary, it is unknown how and to what degree of accuracy this is achieved.

5.2.4 Generative AI, Large Language Models and Hybrid AI

Generative AI and Large Language Models (LLMs) are comparatively recent approaches to a wide variety of existing NLP tasks, but also enable new forms of supporting compliance checking. Due to their generable applicability, they are presented here in a distinct subsection - however, they are also relevant to the different NLP tasks that have been presented in previous parts.

In order to maintain the benefit of generality across various tasks, combined with more legal-specific knowledge, LLMs have been developed specifically for the legal domain. There is *LEGAL-BERT* (Chalkidis et al., 2020), a family of models intended to support a variety of legal tasks based on Google's BERT language models (Devlin et al., 2018). Apart from the general base model, different models within this family have been trained on different corpora of English legal text and are hence better adapted to more specific domains compared to the general model. However, (Simeri, 2023) finds that the base LEGAL-BERT model outperforms both (as expected) the base BERT model as well as (surprisingly) the EURLEX-BERT-BASE model trained on EU legislation in retrieving articles from the GDPR. *MISSION KI Compliance Monitor*⁴⁸ is a single, more recent LLM, fine-tuned from the Llama-3-70B-Instruct model specifically for the application in legal compliance.

Beyond these general, largely task agnostic legal LLMs, numerous approaches have been introduced to utilize existing (non legal-specific) LLMs to assist in compliance checking tasks. Many methods aim to improve performance in extracting information from legal texts, for instance by following the so-called *retrieval-augmented generation* (RAG) approach.

Garza et al., (2024) propose a combined approach of LLMs and Semantic Web technology to clarify what is required by privacy regulations, as well as to ensure compliance of specific privacy policies with these requirements. They first introduce the *Privacy Policy Compliance Verification Knowledge Graph* (PrivComp-KG), which is designed to store and retrieve information about privacy policies, regulatory frameworks and domain-specific legal knowledge, and in a second step employ a LLM to retrieve information from this knowledge graph. According to their research, this combined method leads to a correctness score of 0.9, exceeding other models' performance.

Hassani (2024) proposes a method using LLMs for automated extraction of requirement-related legal content. This method serves two purposes: classifying legal provisions, and automating compliance checks. Legal provisions are classified by pre-processing legal text (splitting it into sentences), then classifying these text chunks in parallel with an LLM, based on BERT and GPT and fine-tuned on labelled data classification data, and through keyword-based classification. These two classification pipelines are then combined to estimate the most appropriate label. Automated compliance checks, on the other hand, are conducted by simply passing the regulatory artifact to

⁴⁷<https://www.luminance.com/comply/>

⁴⁸<https://huggingface.co/ACATECH/ncos>

be verified, as well as a prompt constructed from the rules to be verified against, into an LLM to generate a compliance report.

Prathyush Turaga et al. (2025) introduce the *Co-Compliance Officer* (CO2) method to automatically generate knowledge graphs for legal documents through LLMs, with a focus on compliance with the EU AI Act. This happens in four steps: first, the legal document is transformed into “shall/must” requirements; second, an LLM generates an ontology based on the transformed legal document; third, the LLM performs NER based on the generated ontology; finally, the LLM produces cypher scripts to generate the final knowledge graph.

Abualhaija et al. (2025), focusing on GDPR, propose their *XTRAREG* approach, utilizing LLM + RAG to extract privacy requirements from legal sources. It “takes as input the primary legal source (GDPR in our case) and a pre-defined set of additional sources, and outputs a list of automatically generated detailed requirements”.

Finally, Dal Pont et al. (2025) also employ a combination of LLMs and classical NLP to identify and structure obligations in EU digital legislation texts (mainly GDPR, the Digital Services Act and the AI Act). The workflow comprises four modules: Obligation Detection, Deontic Obligation Filtering, Deontic Obligation Analysis, and Deontic Obligation Representation, where the second and third modules are central to the extraction and analysis of deontic obligations.

Apart from the aforementioned methods to extracting and structuring information, LLMs have also been proposed to facilitate the accessibility of legal information and hence alleviate the burden of compliance checking.

Cherubini et al. (2024) suggest integrating LLMs and RAG to access a dataset of legal acts (limited to English and Italian, in their proposal) through interaction with a chatbot. The architecture is divided into two principal pipelines: the first collects and indexes documents from the EUR-Lex database, while the second takes users’ queries as input, fetches relevant data, and subsequently outputs a response to the user.

Chouhan and Gertz (2025) introduce the *LexGuide* framework, building on RAG and hierarchical topic organization in order to structure dialogue progression. To this end, they construct the *EUDial* dataset, which comprises proactive multi-turn dialogues from 204 blogs curated by the Citizens’ Enquiries Unit (AskEP) of the European Parliamentary Research Service.

5.2.5 Neuro-symbolic and Hybrid Approach

Palmirani et al. (2025) outline a hybrid AI pipeline that combines structured legal representations with statistical methods to support, rather than automate, compliance-relevant drafting decisions. Akoma Ntoso XML (AKN) provides the canonical structure for EU legislation with lifecycle metadata, while EUROVOC and the Regulatory Reporting Metadata Vocabulary (RRMV) supply semantic layers for topics, agents, actions, roles, and temporal constraints. On top of this symbolic layer, the system uses embeddings, similarity search, classic IR and string metrics, plus LLMs in a retrieval-augmented, suggestion-only mode, all integrated into the LEOS drafting environment via microservices and an explainable UI where humans review and accept or reject AI proposals. Four modules operationalise this combination of hybrid AI and Akoma Ntoso XML.

REFERA (Reference Embedding Retrieval Assistant) suggests valid, thematically relevant normative references from partial or noisy citations using temporal filters, Levenshtein distance, and EUROVOC-based embeddings, thus reducing incorrect or outdated cross-references. DEFINA (Legal Definition Assistant) reuses existing definitions by retrieving and ranking candidate definitions via Lucene/Tf-idf and EUROVOC similarity, limiting divergent terminology that hampers consistent interpretation. RECONTA (Recital Connector to Articles) uses a fine-tuned ModernBERT classifier to detect links between recitals and articles, which are then reviewed and encoded as AKN analysis metadata with explicit provenance, making interpretative context machine-readable. TRENDS (Template of Reporting Requirement Engine for Normative Drafting) detects, analyses, and templates reporting requirements, extracting RRMV entities and offering standardised clause patterns in LEOS so monitoring and oversight duties are expressed in a structured, queryable form across the acquis.

Corazza et al. (2025) present a hybrid AI framework for automatically detecting, extracting, and tracking Reporting Requests (RRs) in EU legislation by combining ML and LLMs with the RRVM ontology and European legal standards such as AKN4EU, CELLAR, and ELI. The authors first legally analyse and ontologically model RRs (as meta-norms directing institutions to perform reporting actions over time), then annotate a corpus of AKN4EU legislative texts, distinguishing whether paragraphs contain RRs and labelling core entities such as Addresser, Addressee, Action, ActionResult, and PeriodOfTime. Supervised transformer models (notably Legal-BERT and ModernBERT) are trained for binary RR classification and token-level entity extraction, while a range of open LLMs are used in zero- and few-shot in-context learning setups to perform the same tasks, guided by the RRVM concept definitions inside the prompts. Experimentally, supervised models outperform LLMs on RR detection and most entity types, but LLMs show particular promise for extracting more complex elements such as temporal expressions, though both struggle with the full richness of legal time modelling. Extracted entities are converted to RDF using RRVM and combined with CELLAR metadata to populate a dynamic knowledge graph that captures the lifecycle of RRs, including amendments and temporal validity, enabling queries such as “all RRs addressed to the Commission and Parliament at biannual frequency, suspended during COVID, concerning food standards.” This hybrid approach is explicitly designed for explainability and replicability: ontology-based concepts constrain and make the models’ outputs transparent, fixed seeds and published code/data support reproducibility, and the resulting knowledge graph aims to reduce administrative burden, highlight redundancies or overlaps in RRs, and ultimately support better regulation through more systematic monitoring and drafting of reporting obligations.

5.3 (Non-NLP) Machine Learning Approaches in Compliance

The impact of Machine Learning (ML) in compliance checking is in large part as an enabling technique for NLP methods that were discussed above, where statistical and generative AI approaches are based on ML methods.

Nevertheless, one notable use case in checking for compliance with AI and data regulations, based on ML other than for NLP, is the detection of data breaches. ML is widely used for anomaly detection, i.e. the identification of events that deviate from the usual or expected pattern. Common

D2.2 Survey of Compliance Methods and Tools

use cases include fraud detection in the finance sector (AbouGrad & Sankuru, 2025; Ali & Hagag, 2024; Averro et al., 2023; Dhurandhar et al., 2015), the detection of malicious attacks in cybersecurity (Yaseen, 2023), as well as in numerous other sectors (Zamanzadeh Darban et al., 2025). Kingston (2017) introduces the possibility of employing an analogous method to detect the breach of personal data, which is essential for compliance with Art. 33 of the GDPR, requiring that the controller must communicate a personal data breach to the competent supervisory authority within 72 hours. To this end, Kingston proposes a ML system that monitors the collection of data and information of the organisation's security system.

6 CHALLENGES AND LIMITATIONS

6.1 Ambiguity and Vagueness in Legal Texts

Legal language inherently contains multiple forms of ambiguity that resist straightforward formalization into compliance rules. Previously, researchers have identified six distinct types (Massey et al., 2014): lexical (word meanings), syntactic (sentence structure), semantic (referential), pragmatic (context-dependent), vagueness (boundary cases), and incompleteness (missing specifications). Each type poses different challenges for automated compliance checking, and their coexistence within a single regulatory text compounds the difficulty of producing reliable formal encodings.

A particularly significant source of difficulty is the deliberate use of open-textured terms. Provisions such as "appropriate measures" (GDPR Art. 32), "reasonable" standards, or "necessary" restrictions intentionally delegate interpretation to contextual application. This is not a drafting failure but a considered legislative strategy: a higher degree of specificity would reduce adaptability, preventing the law from being applied as technologies and circumstances change over time. Yet this same indeterminacy creates a fundamental tension between making the law and complying with it; the more flexible a norm, the harder it is to encode computationally without either oversimplifying its meaning or introducing arbitrary thresholds (T. J. M. Bench-Capon, 2015). Balancing tests illustrate the same problem in a more structured form: GDPR Article 6(1)(f)'s legitimate interest assessment requires weighing organisational interests against data subject rights and freedoms, a contextual judgment that resists deterministic encoding (Drechsler, 2021).

Compliance tools must therefore navigate a persistent tension between legal precision and computational tractability, i.e. faithfully capturing normative intent and producing executable rules. Overly rigid formalisations risk misrepresenting the law, while permissive approaches fail to provide actionable guidance (T. J. M. Bench-Capon & Coenen, 1992). Natural language processing approaches can identify ambiguous clauses and flag them for human review, but cannot resolve the underlying interpretive questions. Hybrid systems that surface uncertainty and defer to expert judgment therefore represent a pragmatic middle path (Rigoni, 2018). Recent work on "interpretive layers" takes this further, proposing that compliance systems represent multiple plausible rule interpretations alongside metadata indicating their legal warrant, enabling organisations to assess compliance under different readings while preserving accountability for interpretive choices (Robaldo et al., 2020).

6.2 Dynamic and Evolving Regulations

Legal frameworks are not static: they undergo continuous revision through legislative amendments, judicial interpretation, and regulatory guidance, creating sustained temporal challenges for compliance tooling. The AI Act's phased implementation schedule, with different provisions entering into force over 6 to 36 months, illustrates this acutely, requiring temporal versioning mechanisms that track which obligations apply at which point in time, and how transitional rules interact with legacy systems (European Parliament & Council of the European Union, 2024). Sudden judicial interventions can be equally disruptive: the Schrems II decision (CJEU

C-311/18, 2020), which invalidated the EU-US Privacy Shield, forced organisations to revise their data-transfer compliance frameworks at short notice, requiring case-by-case transfer impact assessments, updates to standard contractual clauses, and supplementary technical measures — with immediate compliance obligations and no grace periods (S. M. Giordano, 2021).

At the tool level, regulatory evolution imposes a significant maintenance burden. Static rule sets quickly become outdated, while frequent updates risk introducing inconsistencies or conflicting interpretations. Most existing compliance tools assume a fixed normative baseline and are poorly equipped to accommodate ongoing incremental regulatory change (Hashmi et al., 2018). Jurisdictional fragmentation compounds this further: organisations operating across multiple legal regimes must manage overlapping, conflicting, or divergent requirements simultaneously, with empirical evidence indicating that uncoordinated multi-agency oversight increases compliance costs, reduces profitability, and disproportionately burdens smaller firms (Kalmenovitz et al., 2025).

Machine learning approaches to regulatory monitoring, using NLP to detect amendments in legislative databases or track enforcement decisions, can partially automate change detection. However, legal expertise remains essential for determining whether a textual change alters substantive compliance obligations and for translating such updates into formal rules (Abualhaja et al., 2024). Governance workflows that define explicit rule lifecycles, covering proposal, validation, activation, and deprecation, offer a more systematic approach to managing evolution, but most existing tools neglect the full lifecycle, particularly the ongoing monitoring, adaptation, and retirement of rules. Maintaining alignment between regulations and their encoded representations ultimately requires sustained institutional commitment and cross-functional teams, not only technical infrastructure (Sackmann et al., 2018).

6.3 Human Accountability versus Automation

Compliance tooling is undergoing a marked transformation from predominantly manual, documentation-driven approaches toward automated regulatory technology (RegTech) solutions (e.g. (Broby et al., 2022; Ryan et al., 2021)). This shift promises greater scalability, consistency, and cost efficiency in regulatory monitoring and reporting. However, it also introduces a structural tension between automation and human accountability. As decision-making authority becomes embedded in software artefacts, questions arise regarding how oversight, responsibility, and contestability can be meaningfully preserved.

A central challenge concerns the opacity of automated systems. Many contemporary AI-based compliance tools rely on complex statistical models that exhibit limited transparency to end users and even to their developers. As mentioned in section 5, such statistical models underpin a great variety of approaches to methods and tools in compliance checking. Classical NLP methods, and even more so LLM-based techniques, rely on structures (such as neural networks) with up to hundreds of billions of parameters. This complexity prohibits the identification of factors linking input and output data. For instance, looking at information retrieval (section 5.2.3), it cannot generally be explained *why* the algorithm extracted the information or topics it did. Such “black box” characteristics hinder interpretability and hence scrutiny (Hassija et al., 2024; Von Eschenbach, 2021). Reduced explainability weakens the attribution of responsibility, as decision rationales

cannot be readily reconstructed or communicated (Raja & Zhou, 2023). More broadly, it has been argued that “the complexity of contemporary AI architectures [...] undermine[s] human understanding and decision-making” (Holzinger et al., 2025), thereby eroding the epistemic foundations on which accountability mechanisms depend.

Effective accountability in automated compliance environments requires more than nominal human oversight. It entails structured explainability, systematic documentation, traceability of decisions across data and model pipelines, and mechanisms for contestability and review (Busuioc, 2021; Kanellopoulos, 2018). Explainability plays a pivotal role within this constellation. For rule- and logic-based systems (presented in section 4), which are often used in traditional compliance automation, decision paths can in principle be rendered transparent through formal representations and auditable rule sets. By contrast, machine learning–based systems (presented in section 5) require additional technical interventions to approximate interpretability.

A growing body of tools seeks to address this gap. Post hoc explanation techniques such as SHAP (Štrumbelj & Kononenko, 2014) and LIME (Ribeiro et al., 2016) provide local or global approximations of model behavior, enabling partial insight into the importance of individual input features and their contribution to decision outputs. While valuable, these techniques do not fully resolve the epistemic and normative limitations of complex models; they generate representations of model behavior rather than inherently interpretable decision structures. Consequently, they should be understood as one component within a broader governance framework rather than stand-alone solutions to ensure accountability.

Beyond technical explainability mechanisms, organizational instruments such as Algorithmic Impact Assessments (AIAs) and Data Protection Impact Assessments (DPIAs) function as critical accountability interfaces (Metcalf et al., 2021; Selbst, 2021). These assessments connect internal risk analysis procedures with external obligations of justification, documentation, and stakeholder communication. By clearly defining anticipatory evaluation and ex ante documentation, they aim to address opacity and ensure that automated compliance systems remain embedded within human decision-making frameworks.

6.4 Ethical Considerations

Ethical concerns in the compliance domain operate on two distinct, but interrelated levels. First, they arise from the AI and data-driven systems that are themselves subject to regulation. Second, they emerge from the compliance tools designed to monitor, assess, and enforce adherence to legal and normative standards. Consequently, compliance systems must be evaluated not only for their regulatory effectiveness but also for their own ethical properties and downstream societal impact.

Many obligations in European AI and data governance frameworks are framed in terms of protecting fundamental rights. Regulations such as the EU AI Act and the General Data Protection Regulation explicitly require organizations to identify and mitigate risks to rights protected under the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, including privacy, non-discrimination, and freedom of expression. However, these legal frameworks provide limited methodological guidance on how such impacts should be evaluated in practice. Translating these rather abstract

requirements into operational and measurable compliance criteria therefore remains difficult. As a result, assessing impacts on fundamental rights represents one of the central practical challenges for AI and data governance compliance systems.

A broad ecosystem of “responsible AI” instruments has been developed to operationalize normative commitments such as fairness, accountability, transparency, and ethics (FATE) (Inuwadutse, 2023; Rama & Prinsloo, 2025). These instruments include fairness metrics, structured documentation frameworks, ethics checklists, model cards, impact assessment templates, design toolkits, and more, that seek to translate abstract principles into implementable practices. However, a recent scoping study indicates that most evaluations of responsible-AI tools focus primarily on usability and adoption rather than on demonstrable improvements in substantive outcomes, such as harm reduction or bias mitigation (Berman et al., 2024). This imbalance raises questions regarding their empirical effectiveness and real-world accountability impact.

Substantively, common ethical considerations in AI governance include fairness and non-discrimination, transparency and explainability, and privacy (Tsamados et al., 2022).

Fairness and non-discrimination. Ensuring that automated systems do not disproportionately disadvantage protected or vulnerable groups remains a central concern (Pessach & Shmueli, 2020; Wang et al., 2022). Compliance checking tools and methods might exhibit bias that is inherent to the methods they are based on, such as NLP (Chang et al., 2019) or generative AI (Choudhry et al., 2024). Toolkits, such as AI Fairness 360 (Bellamy et al., 2018) or Aequitas (Jesus et al., 2024; Saleiro et al., 2019), provide statistical fairness metrics and algorithmic mitigation techniques, enabling stakeholders (such as developers and compliance officers) to detect and mitigate bias. These tools operationalize fairness in measurable terms, yet their deployment is based on prior normative choices about which fairness definition is appropriate in a given domain.

Transparency and explainability. As discussed above, explainable AI techniques aim to render decision processes intelligible and auditable, thereby supporting accountability and legal contestability (Blacklaws, 2018). While technical methods can provide approximations of feature importance or model sensitivity, their interpretive sufficiency remains debated, particularly in high-stakes contexts where decision-level justification is required.

Privacy. Data-driven compliance systems frequently process sensitive or large-scale personal data, intensifying privacy risks (Tayyab et al., 2023). For instance, some approaches presented above will involve the handling of personal data, such as when it comes to the extraction of information from or the recognition of entities in legal documents, or the verification of compliance of Data Processing Agreements. Privacy-enhancing technologies (PETs), including differential privacy and secure multi-party computation, offer technical safeguards that limit data exposure while preserving certain analytical capabilities (Hölzel, 2019). These approaches attempt to reconcile regulatory monitoring with data minimization and confidentiality requirements, though often at the cost of analytical precision.

Despite the proliferation of ethical tooling, significant limitations persist. Ethical principles frequently conflict in practice; for instance, optimizing for statistical fairness may reduce predictive accuracy, while strong privacy guarantees may diminish data utility (Petersen, 2021). Moreover, fairness metrics are inherently context-dependent and cannot exhaustively encode normative

judgments about justice, harm, or discrimination (Barr et al., 2025; Dobbe et al., 2018; Dobbe & Wolters, 2024; Glymour & Herington, 2019; Ruf et al., 2020). They inevitably reflect specific modeling assumptions and value trade-offs, which may not align with broader societal or legal conceptions of equality.

Similarly, explainability techniques often fail to deliver faithful, causally grounded explanations at the level required for robust accountability (Das & Rad, 2020). Post hoc explanations may approximate patterns in model behavior without accurately representing underlying decision logic, thereby creating a risk of “explanation theater” rather than substantive transparency.

Overall, ethical and accountability tools provide important infrastructures for operationalizing responsible AI principles in compliance contexts. Yet their effectiveness depends on careful contextualization, explicit normative deliberation, and integration into broader governance frameworks.

6.5 Digital Sovereignty

Digital sovereignty is commonly defined as the capacity of states or political communities to secure continuous access to reliable digital and AI capabilities while enforcing their own legal and normative frameworks over data, infrastructures, and technological ecosystems (Baldoni & Luna, 2025; Srivastava & Bullock, 2024). In regulatory discourse, digital sovereignty operates both as a strategic objective, linked to industrial competitiveness and geopolitical autonomy, and as a legal principle tied to jurisdictional authority over data and algorithmic systems.

A central regulatory instrument in this domain is data localization legislation, which mandates that certain categories of data be stored or processed within national or regional borders. Such measures are intended to safeguard access, reduce dependency on foreign infrastructures, and strengthen enforceability of domestic law. However, data localization can also impede AI development where local computational infrastructure, high-performance computing capacity, or specialized expertise are insufficient (Agata & Kibet, 2025). In these contexts, sovereignty-enhancing regulation may imply innovation constraints, raising trade-offs between autonomy and technological advancement.

For organizations operating across jurisdictions, digital sovereignty manifests as a complex patchwork of cross-border data-transfer constraints. Divergences between frameworks such as the GDPR and foreign surveillance or national-security regimes complicate compliance strategies, particularly when data flows intersect with conflicting legal obligations. As a result, compliance tools increasingly embed jurisdiction-specific constraints regarding data residency, access permissions, and transfer mechanisms. These technical controls incorporate legal fragmentation, translating abstract territorial rules into automated compliance enforcement layers.

Yet the sovereignty effects of such tooling are ambivalent. On the one hand, region-aware compliance tools can reinforce local control by ensuring that, for instance, designated datasets remain within prescribed geographic zones and are processed in conformity with domestic standards. On the other hand, sovereignty may decrease when the compliance tooling, cloud infrastructure, or AI platforms themselves are controlled by foreign vendors (Kaya & Shahid, 2025).

In these cases, formal territorial compliance may coexist with dependencies that undermine true autonomy.

Academic debates concerning “EU AI sovereignty” illustrate these tensions. Scholars highlight frictions between industrial policy objectives, the protection of fundamental rights, and the plurality of public interests within the European polity (Mügge, 2024; Smuha, 2023; Srivastava & Bullock, 2024). Efforts to foster domestic AI ecosystems may conflict with open-market principles or global research collaboration, while rights-based regulatory frameworks may constrain certain forms of technological scaling. Transparency regarding their design assumptions, contestability mechanisms for cross-border enforcement decisions, and multi-stakeholder oversight are therefore essential to prevent sovereignty from being reduced to a purely technical configuration. Without such safeguards, sovereignty-oriented compliance architectures risk entrenching dependencies or embedding contested geopolitical choices into seemingly neutral technical systems.

7 EVALUATION METRICS AND PERFORMANCE

Evaluating compliance tools is a complex exercise. What "performance" means depends fundamentally on the type of approach being assessed, and conflating evaluation criteria across tool families can produce misleading comparisons. For rule-based and logic-based systems, performance is primarily a question of correctness and coverage: does the rule set accurately encode the regulatory requirement, and does it cover all relevant provisions without gaps or contradictions? Accuracy in the statistical sense is less relevant here than formal soundness: a rule either fires correctly or it does not. For model-driven approaches, evaluation centres on conformance metrics such as fitness and precision against process logs, or on the exhaustiveness of formal verification. For semantic web and ontology-based tools, performance is better understood in terms of expressivity and reasoning decidability: OWL-DL supports automated reasoning and inconsistency detection while OWL-Full does not. This makes the choice of ontology profile a design constraint with direct compliance implications. Evaluating a SHACL-based compliance checker, for instance, requires asking whether the constraint shapes correctly capture the regulatory requirement. It is only for the ML and NLP-based approaches that statistical performance metrics such as precision, recall and F1 become the primary evaluation instrument, and even then they must be interpreted against the stakes of the domain. With this in mind, the following subsections assess evaluation dimensions as they apply across the tool families covered in this survey, with reference to the EU AI and data regulations that define its scope.

7.1 Accuracy and Precision of Compliance Tools

Evaluating the accuracy of compliance tools requires domain-adapted benchmarks, since generic NLP benchmarks fail to capture the specific challenges of legal language: technical terminology, long-context dependencies, and low-frequency but high-stakes clause types.

The Contract Understanding Atticus Dataset (CUAD) (Hendrycks et al., 2021) has become a primary academic benchmark for contract review comprising over 13,000 expert annotations across 41 clause types in 510 commercial contracts. The best-performing model at the time of publication, DeBERTa-xlarge, at time of publication achieves an AUPR of 47.8% and a Precision at 80% Recall of 44.0%, figures that reflect the inherent difficulty of legal clause extraction and should be read cautiously as opposed to optimistically. AUPR measures a model's ability to correctly identify relevant clauses across all possible decision thresholds, where a score of 100% would indicate perfect identification and scores closer to 0% reflect near-random performance; it is particularly appropriate for legal tasks where relevant clauses are sparse relative to total document length. LegalBench (Guha et al., 2023), covering 162 tasks across six categories of legal reasoning, provides a broader evaluation platform where large commercial models achieve high balanced accuracy on simpler classification tasks but performance degrades on longer texts and multi-class problems. LexGLUE (Chalkidis et al., 2022) standardises evaluation across seven legal NLU tasks spanning EU legislation, ECHR case law, US court decisions and contract provisions.

For GDPR compliance checking specifically, applied work on privacy policy analysis has demonstrated meaningful results. The Usable Privacy Project (Oltramari et al., 2018) from which the PrivOnto ontology derives, provides one of the more systematically evaluated corpora: approximately 23,000 annotations of data practice statements across privacy policies, supporting both precision-oriented extraction and semantic classification tasks. This line of work is instructive because it shows genuine variety in outcomes across tool types and provides a domain-specific evaluation baseline directly relevant to GDPR. (Cejas et al., 2023) report that an NLP and rule-based system correctly identifies 89.1% of GDPR violations in Data Processing Agreements, with 82.4% recall. These results outperform generic NLP baselines and also indicate that roughly one in ten violations goes undetected, a non-trivial error rate given the enforcement stakes. The choice of evaluation metric carries substantive implications: in compliance contexts, a false negative (a missed violation) typically carries higher legal risk than a false positive. This can make recall-weighted metrics more appropriate than aggregate F1.

For rule-based and ontological tools, accuracy assessment takes the form of correctness being evaluated through formal methods: consistency checking, coverage analysis against the full regulatory text and validation against known test cases encoding specific legal scenarios. The absence of standardised test suites for GDPR or AI Act compliance represents a gap in the literature that limits cross-tool comparison.

7.2 Scalability and Efficiency

The scalability of compliance tooling has advanced through ML-based automation and cloud deployment, though the picture differs considerably across tool families.

For NLP-based systems, scalability requires addressing the token-length limitations of standard transformer models. BERT's 512-token ceiling is inadequate for most legal documents; Longformer and its legal variants extend this to 4,096 - 8,192 tokens using sparse attention mechanisms, while hierarchical architectures process documents by aggregating segment-level representations (Beltagy et al., 2020). Latency increases non-linearly with sequence length and performance tends to degrade at very large context windows. This is a practical constraint for real-time compliance monitoring.

For rule-based systems, scalability is a different challenge: the RETE algorithm (Forgy, 1982) addresses computational efficiency at execution time but the bottleneck is rule elicitation and maintenance. A large rule set covering the full GDPR, AI Act, and Data Governance Act would require sustained expert effort to author and update. This results in a cost that does not diminish with scale.

Semantic web and ontology-based approaches face a scalability constraint tied to reasoning complexity. OWL-DL supports automated reasoning but at computational cost that increases with ontology size and the complexity of applied constraints. SHACL-based validation scales more tractably for large datasets but trades off expressivity against performance. These trade-offs are design decisions with compliance implications, and evaluating a semantic web tool for scalability therefore requires specifying which reasoning tasks are in scope.

7.3 Explainability and Transparency

Explainability in compliance tools is not merely a technical desideratum but a legal requirement under EU law. GDPR Article 22 prohibits solely automated decisions with significant legal effects without providing "meaningful information about the logic involved." The EU AI Act imposes additional obligations: Article 13 requires that high-risk AI systems be sufficiently transparent for deployers to interpret their outputs, and Article 86 establishes an explicit right to explanation of individual AI-assisted decisions. The CJEU's ruling in Case C-203/22 (*Dun & Bradstreet*, 2024) confirmed that the right to explanation for automated credit scoring must include substantive details of the method, not merely its existence.

For rule-based and logic-based compliance systems, explainability is architecturally embedded: deterministic inference chains can be traced directly from input facts to applicable rules to conclusions, generating natural-language audit trails that satisfy GDPR Article 5(2) accountability requirements. The challenge is more acute for ML-based systems, where prediction logic is distributed across model weights. Post-hoc explanation techniques, including SHAP (Štrumbelj & Kononenko, 2014), which uses Shapley values from cooperative game theory to attribute predictions to input features, and LIME (Ribeiro et al., 2016), which fits local surrogate models around individual predictions, can generate feature-level explanations, though their faithfulness to true model reasoning remains debated (Hassija et al., 2024).

A practical tension persists between model performance and interpretability. High-performing deep learning models tend to be less interpretable than rule-based or shallow ML models, while more interpretable architectures such as Explainable Boosting Machines offer a partial middle ground. For high-risk AI applications under the AI Act, including systems assisting judicial decisions, employment screening, or credit scoring, the explainability requirement effectively constrains the design space of permissible architectures, since black-box outputs cannot satisfy the legal standard for meaningful explanation (Von Eschenbach, 2021). Audit trails, time-stamped records of inputs, model versions, and human interventions are increasingly required by financial regulators including the US Security and Exchange Commission (SEC) and, prospectively, the UK Financial Conduct Authority (FCA) (Rundle, et al., 2024).

7.4 Risk Assessment and Prioritisation

Compliance tools increasingly incorporate risk scoring to triage obligations and direct human review toward highest-priority items, rather than treating all regulatory requirements as equally urgent.

The standard risk scoring formula ($\text{Risk} = \text{Likelihood} \times \text{Impact}$) is widely applied in compliance risk assessment, extended in more sophisticated frameworks by additional factors such as risk velocity, control maturity, and regulatory attention multipliers (Compliance & Risks, 2025). The FATF Risk-Based Approach, mandatory since 2012, structures AML risk assessment across customer, geographic, product, and channel dimensions (MONEYVAL, 2024), while the Basel AML Index aggregates risk scores across 177+ jurisdictions using 17 public data sources. These frameworks provide reference architectures that compliance tooling vendors translate into automated scoring engines.

Machine learning has improved predictive risk models in specific compliance domains. In AML, traditional rule-based alert systems generate high false positive rates, which means that only a small proportion of the flagged transactions result in Suspicious Activity Reports, and impose significant operational costs (Ibitola, 2025). AI-enhanced systems claim reductions of 40 - 70% in false positive rates, though these figures are primarily vendor-reported and independently validated evidence remains limited. Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) methods, including AHP for pairwise comparisons, ELECTRE and PROMETHEE for outranking, and TOPSIS for value-based scoring, provide structured frameworks for prioritising competing compliance obligations when resources are constrained.

For EU AI and data regulations specifically, risk-based compliance tools must operationalise the tiered risk classification of the AI Act, distinguish unacceptable, high, limited, and minimal risk, and map obligations to specific organisational roles and system lifecycles. This requires combining rule-based classification logic (to assign risk tier) with impact assessment workflows (to document conformity), a hybrid architecture not yet mature in commercially available tools (Sovrano et al., 2024).

7.5 Adaptability and Customisation

The adaptability of compliance tools determines their usefulness across regulatory jurisdictions, document types, and evolving legal requirements, a critical consideration given the pace of regulatory change in the EU AI and data landscape.

Domain-adapted language models consistently outperform generic models on legal tasks when fine-tuned on task-specific data. LEGAL-BERT (Chalkidis et al., 2020), pre-trained on 12 GB of diverse English legal text drawn from EU and UK legislation, ECJ and ECHR case law, and US contracts, demonstrates consistent performance improvements over generic BERT on downstream legal classification tasks. On the LexGLUE benchmark, fine-tuned domain-specific models outperform zero-shot LLM baselines by substantial margins across micro-F1 and macro-F1 metrics (Chalkidis et al., 2022), confirming that for structured legal classification tasks, fine-tuned smaller models remain competitive with or superior to large-scale generative models applied zero-shot, a relevant consideration for cost-constrained compliance deployments.

Regulatory update management presents a persistent adaptability challenge. Thomson Reuters and CUBE RegPlatform together monitor over 1,500 regulatory bodies and generate approximately 56,000 regulatory change alerts annually (over 200 updates per day) across global jurisdictions (CUBE, 2026). Tools like AscentAI scan regulatory sources continuously and can extract a firm's specific obligations under a new rule in minutes rather than weeks (*AscentAI: AI-Powered Regulatory Compliance*, 2023). However, automated change detection identifies textual amendments; determining whether a legal change alters compliance obligations still requires legal expertise, highlighting the persistent limits of full automation.

Cross-jurisdictional portability remains an open challenge. Tools such as SecurePrivacy and BigID support simultaneous compliance management across the GDPR, the California Consumer Privacy Act (CCPA), the Brazilian General Personal Data Protection Law (LGPD), and other national frameworks using a "highest common denominator" approach, automatically applying the most

stringent applicable standard. The PASTA framework (Yang et al., 2026) demonstrates efficiency gains in multi-policy evaluation through irrelevancy filtering, reducing unnecessary obligation checks across EU AI Act, GDPR, CCPA, and Colorado AI Act requirements simultaneously. Cross-lingual transfer adds a further dimension: multilingual models such as XLM-R and translation-based pipelines enable compliance tools to operate across EU member state languages, though performance remains highest when models are fine-tuned on target-language legal corpora rather than relying on zero-shot cross-lingual transfer alone.

A dimension of adaptability that the current landscape renders particularly acute is the capacity to comply with standards that are not yet finalised. The harmonised standards for the AI Act remain incomplete as of early 2026, with JTC21 having released only one standard (on AI Quality Management) for review. Compliance tools find themselves in the unusual position of having to operationalise legal obligations whose technical specification is still being negotiated. Evaluating a tool's adaptability in this environment therefore requires asking whether its architecture supports rapid integration of new conformity criteria once harmonised standards are approved. Tools built on modular rule sets and policy-as-code approaches are structurally better positioned for this than those with hardcoded compliance logic though empirical evaluations of this adaptability dimension remain scarce in the literature.

7.6 Interoperability of Compliance Tool Outputs

Interoperability is identified as a core challenge in legal compliance verification and it runs as a thread through the semantic web and ontological approaches covered in this document. It is however scarcely treated as an evaluation criterion in its own right.

For compliance tools, interoperability has two dimensions. The first is input interoperability: can the tool consume structured compliance-relevant data expressed in standard formats such as DPV-aligned RDF, LegalRuleML, or OSCAL, without requiring manual re-entry? The second is output interoperability: does the tool produce results in a form that other tools, auditors or supervisory authorities can consume and verify? A DPIA report generated by one platform and unreadable by another is a compliance liability in environments where regulatory scrutiny requires documented and verifiable evidence chains.

Relevant metrics for evaluating interoperability include: conformance to established vocabularies such as DPV (J. Pandit et al., 2025) or LegalRuleML (Palmirani, Cervone, et al., 2011), the availability of structured export formats (RDF, JSON-LD, OSCAL) and compatibility with knowledge graph infrastructure where compliance conditions are encoded as SHACL constraint shapes, among others. The Interoperable Europe Act's mandate for cross-border interoperability in public digital services makes this evaluation dimension directly legally relevant. That most currently available compliance tools do not publish interoperability conformance information is a finding.

8 CASE STUDIES AND APPLICATIONS

8.1 GDPR: The CNIL Privacy Impact Assessment (PIA) as a Structured Compliance Workflow

The Privacy Impact Assessment (PIA)(Commission Nationale de l'Informatique et des Libertés, 2018), operationalised by the Commission Nationale de l'Informatique et des Libertés (CNIL, is one of instructive compliance instruments in the European data protection landscape), can be seen as a practical implementation of the Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) obligation under Article 35 of the GDPR, which requires a structured prior assessment when a processing operation is 'likely to result in a high risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons.' The EDPB's Guidelines on DPIA (WP248 rev.01) further clarify this threshold through a two-criteria test and the CNIL's published blacklists and whitelists of processing operations operationalise it into something one can actually act upon (European Data Protection Board, 2017; CNIL, 2018).

Here PIA will be presented as a productive subject for this survey, as it sits at the intersection of several of the approaches covered in the preceding sections: rule-based checking, model-driven design and semantic grounding. Sometimes in combination and not necessarily by explicit design.

Rule-based checking: The CNIL's own open-source PIA software implements a guided questionnaire that functions, in effect, as a structured decision procedure, where each question maps to a normative requirement. The CNIL's blacklists and whitelists are natural candidates for encoding as decision tables, which also support quality checks for completeness and consistency before deployment .

Model-driven element: Privacy threat analysis frameworks which use Data Flow Diagrams (DFDs) and a structured taxonomy of privacy threat categories can be deployed upstream of the PIA to elicit the threats that the risk assessment phase then quantifies. This positions the PIA within a broader model-driven workflow where threat modelling precedes and informs impact assessment.. For process-centric implementations allow data flows and potential leakage points to be made explicit at the model level, enabling design-time verification of data minimisation constraints before deployment. This is the spirit of GDPR Article 25's data protection by design obligation.

Ontological and semantic grounding: The PrOnto ontology (Palmirani & Governatori, 2018) models core GDPR concepts using defeasible deontic operators, providing a semantic framework that aligns closely with the PIA's context definition requirements. Representing a processing operation in PrOnto-compatible terms supports interoperability across GDPR compliance tools and enables machine-readable alignment between a PIA record and the regulatory text from which its requirements derive. The Data Privacy Vocabulary (J. Pandit et al., 2025) developed under the W3C DPVCG provides a controlled vocabulary for expressing personal data categories, processing operations, legal bases, and purposes in a linked data framework, making it directly applicable to encoding PIA context definition outputs in a machine-readable and interoperable form, enabling, in principle, automated checking against GDPR requirements encoded as SHACL constraint shapes over the resulting knowledge graph.

The primary tool is CNIL's own open-source PIA software that is freely available and widely used across the French and broader European context. It implements the guided methodology,

manages the structured questionnaire and generates exportable assessment reports. Evaluated against the evaluation metrics dimensions discussed, CNIL's PIA presents an uneven profile. The methodology scores well by design where the guided questionnaire produces a structured, human-readable report in which each assessment decision is traceable to a specific normative requirement, satisfying the audit trail expectations that rule-based and logic-based approaches are well positioned to meet. CNIL publishes updated guidance and maintains the open-source tool, but the methodology does not embed automated mechanisms for regulatory change. Organisations are expected to initiate reassessment manually when processing operations or the regulatory context changes. This presents a mixed outlook in the adaptability sense. On interoperability, the current tool produces PDF and JSON export formats. Integration of semantic web infrastructure, encoding PIA outputs in DPV-aligned RDF and validating against SHACL shapes, has been proposed as a route toward interoperable, machine-checkable PIA records; the gap between proposal and widespread practice remains momentarily considerable. The question of whether this suffices remains subjective. It however presents a metric, not previously discussed, human oversight. It requires formal sign-off by a senior responsible official, mandates prior consultation with the supervisory authority when residual risk remains unacceptable and produces a documented action plan.

Several **limitations** bear naming. The risk assessment methodology relies on semi-quantitative severity and likelihood scales that lack standardisation, making cross-organisational comparability difficult. The PIA is also a point-in-time assessment applied to what are dynamic systems. Major regulatory developments can rewrite the underlying compliance logic rapidly, forcing organisations to revisit transfer rule logic and supporting documentation at short notice. Maintaining PIA currency requires a lifecycle governance discipline that is rarely implemented with the rigour the methodology implicitly demands.

Finally, the two-criteria threshold for determining whether a PIA is required is itself a compliance question requiring legal interpretation. The boundary between "likely to result in high risk" and "not likely to result in high risk" can, in contested cases, be resolved by supervisory authorities and courts rather than by any automated system, resulting in deference to legal judgement.

CNIL's PIA illustrates that real-world compliance instruments can coexist within a single workflow and effective tooling requires integration across these frameworks. It also demonstrates the centrality of governance artefacts (i.e the PIA report, the action plan, the sign-off record) as accountability outputs that must be produced, maintained and versioned. And it offers a concrete example of a supervisory authority acting as a compliance engineering infrastructure provider: the CNIL's published guides and open-source software reduce interpretive variance and lower the implementation burden for regulated entities.

8.2 AI Act: "Is My AI System High-Risk?"—Semantic Tool for Determining High-Risk AI Systems - Golpayegani et al.

“Is My AI System High-Risk?”⁴⁹ is an online web form developed by Golpayegani et al. at the ADAPT Centre in Ireland to help determine if an AI system is high-risk or not based on concepts in Annex III of the drafted EU AI Act (Golpayegani et al., 2023). Annex III of the drafted AI Act focuses on AI systems that affect fundamental rights and that are not previously outlined in Annex II, which refers to health and safety. The list in Annex III covers applications in biometrics, critical infrastructure, education and vocational training, employment, access to essential private and public services, law enforcement, migration, and administration of justice and democratic processes. AI providers of ‘high-risk’ systems must provide risk management documentation and mitigation techniques, high-quality datasets, activity logging, human oversight measures, and robust security prior to market deployment according to the act. The executable tool is shown in Figure 3 below.

Is My AI System High-Risk?

A tool to assist you determine whether an AI system is High-Risk according to Annex III of the [EU AI Act](#).

Please fill out the high-risk AI checklist

My AI system Test

is intended to be used in the domain of

Administration Of Democratic Processes ,

for the purpose of Researching Law ,

has the capability of Lie Detection .

The system is intended to be deployed by Educational Institution ,

& the entity who is subjected to its use is Natural Person

Check whether your AI system is high-risk

Your AI system is likely to be High-Risk as per AI Act Annex III-8b: Administration of justice and democratic processes, AI systems intended to be used for influencing the outcome of an election or referendum or the voting behaviour of natural persons in the exercise of their vote in elections or referenda. This does not include AI systems to the output of which natural persons are not directly exposed, such as tools used to organise, optimise or structure political campaigns from an administrative or logistical point of view.

Domain: AdministrationOfDemocraticProcesses
Purpose: ResearchingLaw
Capability: LieDetection
Deployer: EducationalInstitution
Subject: NaturalPerson

Figure 3: “Is My AI System High-Risk?”

We examine this tool to highlight early developments of compliance tools for the EU AI Act, specifically for high-risk AI systems. As discussed in Section 3.3, mechanisms for compliance for the

⁴⁹ “Is My AI System High-Risk?” Tool: <https://regtech.adaptcentre.ie/highrisk>

EU AI Act are still being developed and this tool is one step to assist AI providers in understanding what compliance obligations they are subject to. “Is My AI System High-Risk?” follows rule-based compliance checking and employs semantic web technologies.

Rule-based checking: The web form requests inputs via a drop-down selection to assess an AI system based on normative requirements. These requirements are rule-based and were developed through analysis of high-risk AI use-cases as denoted in Annex III. The following criteria is evaluated in the tool:

- 1) “In which **domain** is the AI system used?”
- 2) What is the **purpose** of the AI system?”
- 3) What is the **capability** of the AI system?”
- 4) Who is the **user** of the AI system?”
- 5) Who is the **AI subject**?” (Golpayegani et al., 2023).

Semantic web technologies and vocabularies: Concepts from the AI Risk Ontology (AIRO, discussed in Section 4.6.5) are reused to semantically model the high-risk criteria, as shown in Figure 4 (Golpayegani et al., 2023). A RDF graph of an AI system is generated based on the received inputs and defined semantics. Assessment is executed through SHACL to determine if conditions for an AI system to be high-risk are met.

Figure 4: “Semantic model of the 5 concepts required for determining high-risk AI” (Golpayegani et al., 2023)

“Is My AI System High-Risk?” is free to use and available online. The paper (Golpayegani et al., 2023) is accompanied by a vocabulary for AI risks (VAIR) and an analysis of the standardisation landscape for the EU AI Act. Based on the evaluation metrics previously discussed, this tool establishes a narrow scope to warrant accuracy while sacrificing scalability. “Is My AI System High-Risk?” focuses on a small section of the AI Act that would prove difficult to do on a large scale as rule elicitation and SHACL evaluation become more complex. VAIR exceeds the expectations of explainability and transparency for the tool and provides a mechanism for cataloguing AI risks. As denoted in the AI Act, the European Commission can amend Annex III high-risk applications rendering the tool outdated and not adaptable as new rules will have to be developed based on legislative changes. In regards to interoperability, Golpayegani et al. adhere to FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles in the development of this tool.

While this tool simplifies identification of high-risk use of AI, there are notable **limitations** the authors disclose. The tool is heuristic through guidance and not formal legal advice. It serves solely as a means to understand which AI systems are subject to high-risk compliance requirements as defined by the draft of the AI Act. The tool does not identify if an AI system has unacceptable risk and is prohibited (as defined in Article 5), and this should be ruled out prior to the use of the tool. The tool is intended for AI providers, or AI users who modify a non high-risk AI system to be high-risk. If an AI system undergoes “substantial modifications” as defined by the EU AI Act, it is subject to reassessment of risk status. The tool does not assess the criteria of general purpose AI systems for high-risk levels.

DECLARATION OF USE OF AI-ASSISTED TECHNOLOGIES

The authors used Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies, the free versions of OpenAI's ChatGPT and Anthropic's Claude, for language assistance such as spelling and grammar checking, and for editing the form of this manuscript with no additions to its content. All technical content, experimental results, and scientific claims were verified and are the responsibility of the authors.

REFERENCES

- Aarnio, A. (2011). Two Types of Norms. In A. Aarnio (Ed.), *Essays on the Doctrinal Study of Law* (pp. 119–124). Springer Netherlands. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-1655-1_15
- Abualhaija, S., Ceci, M., Sannier, N., Bianculli, D., Briand, L. C., Zetsche, D., & Bodellini, M. (2024). AI-Enabled Regulatory Change Analysis of Legal Requirements. *2024 IEEE 32nd International Requirements Engineering Conference (RE)*, 5–17. <https://doi.org/10.1109/RE59067.2024.00012>
- Abualhaija, S., Ceci, M., Sannier, N., Bianculli, D., Lannier, S., Siclari, M., Voordeckers, O., & Tosza, S. (2025). LLM-assisted Extraction of Regulatory Requirements: A Case Study on the GDPR. *2025 IEEE 33rd International Requirements Engineering Conference (RE)*, 142–154. <https://doi.org/10.1109/RE63999.2025.00023>
- Agostinelli, S., De Luzi, F., Maggi, F. M., Marrella, A., & Volpi, A. (2026). Design patterns for GDPR-aware process modeling in BPMN. *Information Systems*, *137*, 102646. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.is.2025.102646>
- Ajani, G., Boella, G., di Caro, L., Robaldo, L., Humphreys, L., Praduroux, S., Rossi, P., & Violato, A. (2017). The European Legal Taxonomy Syllabus: A multi-lingual, multi-level ontology framework to untangle the web of European legal terminology. *Applied Ontology*, *11*(4), 325–375. <https://doi.org/10.3233/AO-170174>
- Alchourron, C. E. (1996). On Law and Logic. *Ratio Juris*, *9*(4), 331–348. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9337.1996.tb00250.x>
- Allen, L. (1966). Logic-Language-Law. *Book Chapters*. https://repository.law.umich.edu/book_chapters/324
- Amantea, I. A., Governatori, G., Quaranta, M., & Molinari, M. (2026). A methodology for compliance of AI systems. *Computer Law & Security Review*, *61*, 106272. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clsr.2026.106272>
- Amantea, I. A., Robaldo, L., Sulis, E., Boella, G., & Governatori, G. (2021). *Semi-automated checking for regulatory compliance in e-Health* (arXiv:2110.07710). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2110.07710>
- Antoniou, G. (2004). Defeasible logic with dynamic priorities. *International Journal of Intelligent Systems*, *19*(5), 463–472. <https://doi.org/10.1002/int.20008>
- Antoniou, G., Billington, D., Governatori, G., & Maher, M. J. (2001). Representation results for defeasible logic. *ACM Trans. Comput. Logic*, *2*(2), 255–287. <https://doi.org/10.1145/371316.371517>
- Araszkiwicz, M., Bench-Capon, T., Francesconi, E., Lauritsen, M., & Rotolo, A. (2022). Thirty years of Artificial Intelligence and Law: Overviews. *Artificial Intelligence and Law*, *30*(4), 593–610. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10506-022-09324-9>

D2.2 Survey of Compliance Methods and Tools

- Ariai, F., Mackenzie, J., & Demartini, G. (2026). Natural Language Processing for the Legal Domain: A Survey of Tasks, Datasets, Models, and Challenges. *ACM Computing Surveys*, 58(6), 1–37. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3777009>
- AscentAI: AI-Powered Regulatory Compliance*. (2023). <https://www.ascentregtech.com/our-difference/ascentai/>
- Au, T. W. T., Lampos, V., & Cox, I. (2022). E-NER — An Annotated Named Entity Recognition Corpus of Legal Text. *Proceedings of the Natural Legal Language Processing Workshop 2022*, 246–255. <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2022.nllp-1.22>
- Avgerinos Loutsaris, M., Alexopoulos, C., Maratsi, M. I., & Charalabidis, Y. (2023). Semantic Interoperability for Legal Information: Mapping the European Legislation Identifier (ELI) and Akoma Ntoso (AKN) Ontologies. *Proceedings of the 16th International Conference on Theory and Practice of Electronic Governance, ICEGOV '23*, 41–53. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3614321.3614327>
- Azam, N., Chak, A., Michala, A., Ansari, S., & Truong, N. B. (2025). A practical solution for modelling GDPR-compliance based on defeasible logic reasoning. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 277, 127140. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2025.127140>
- Barabucci, G., Cervone, L., Di Iorio, A., Palmirani, M., Peroni, S., & Vitali, F. (2010). *Managing semantics in XML vocabularies: An experience in the legal and legislative domain*. Balisage: The Markup Conference 2010. <https://doi.org/10.4242/BalisageVol5.Barabucci01>
- Barabucci, G., Cervone, L., Palmirani, M., Peroni, S., & Vitali, F. (2010). Multi-layer Markup and Ontological Structures in Akoma Ntoso. In P. Casanovas, U. Pagallo, G. Sartor, & G. Ajani (Eds.), *AI Approaches to the Complexity of Legal Systems. Complex Systems, the Semantic Web, Ontologies, Argumentation, and Dialogue* (pp. 133–149). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-16524-5_9
- Basin, D., Debois, S., & Hildebrandt, T. (2018). On Purpose and by Necessity: Compliance Under the GDPR. In S. Meiklejohn & K. Sako (Eds.), *Financial Cryptography and Data Security* (Vol. 10957, pp. 20–37). Springer Berlin Heidelberg. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-662-58387-6_2
- Beltagy, I., Peters, M. E., & Cohan, A. (2020). *Longformer: The Long-Document Transformer* (arXiv:2004.05150). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2004.05150>
- Bench-Capon, T., Araszkievicz, M., Ashley, K., Atkinson, K., Bex, F., Borges, F., Bourcier, D., Bourguine, P., Conrad, J. G., Francesconi, E., Gordon, T. F., Governatori, G., Leidner, J. L., Lewis, D. D., Loui, R. P., McCarty, L. T., Prakken, H., Schilder, F., Schweighofer, E., ... Wyner, A. Z. (2012). A history of AI and Law in 50 papers: 25 years of the international conference on AI and Law. *Artificial Intelligence and Law*, 20(3), 215–319. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10506-012-9131-x>
- Bench-Capon, T. J. M. (2015). Transition systems for designing and reasoning about norms. *Artificial Intelligence and Law*, 23(4), 345–366. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10506-015-9175-9>

D2.2 Survey of Compliance Methods and Tools

- Bench-Capon, T. J. M., & Coenen, F. P. (1992). Isomorphism and legal knowledge based systems. *Artificial Intelligence and Law*, 1(1), 65–86. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00118479>
- Benzmüller, C., Farjami, A., Fuenmayor, D., Meder, P., Parent, X., Steen, A., van der Torre, L., & Zahoransky, V. (2020). LogiKEY workbench: Deontic logics, logic combinations and expressive ethical and legal reasoning (Isabelle/HOL dataset). *Data in Brief*, 33, 106409. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dib.2020.106409>
- Berman, D. H., & Hafner, C. D. (1993). Representing teleological structure in case-based legal reasoning: The missing link. *Proceedings of the 4th International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Law, ICAIL '93*, 50–59. <https://doi.org/10.1145/158976.158982>
- Berners-Lee, T., Chen, Y., Chilton, L., Connolly, D., Dhanaraj, R., Hollenbach, J., Lerer, A., & Sheets, D. (2006). *Tabulator: Exploring and Analyzing linked data on the Semantic Web*.
- Berners-Lee, T., Hendler, J., & Lassila, O. (2001). The Semantic Web: A New Form of Web Content That is Meaningful to Computers Will Unleash a Revolution of New Possibilities. *ScientificAmerican.Com*.
- Berti, A., Zelst, S. J. van, & Aalst, W. van der. (2019). *Process Mining for Python (PM4Py): Bridging the Gap Between Process- and Data Science* (arXiv:1905.06169). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1905.06169>
- Blei, D., Ng, A., & Jordan, M. (2003). Latent Dirichlet Allocation. *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, 3, 993–1022.
- Boella, G., Caro, L. D., Humphreys, L., Robaldo, L., Rossi, P., & van der Torre, L. (2016). Eunomos, a legal document and knowledge management system for the Web to provide relevant, reliable and up-to-date information on the law. *Artificial Intelligence and Law*, 24(3), 245–283. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10506-016-9184-3>
- Boley, H., Paschke, A., & Shafiq, O. (2010). RuleML 1.0: The Overarching Specification of Web Rules. In M. Dean, J. Hall, A. Rotolo, & S. Tabet (Eds.), *Semantic Web Rules* (pp. 162–178). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-16289-3_15
- Bommarito, M. J., Katz, D. M., & Detterman, E. M. (2018). *LexNLP: Natural language processing and information extraction for legal and regulatory texts* (arXiv:1806.03688). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1806.03688>
- Booth, R., Casini, G., Klarman, S., Richard, G., & Varzinczak, I. (2019). Editorial: Defeasible and Ampliative Reasoning. *International Journal of Approximate Reasoning*, 112, 1–3. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijar.2019.05.009>
- Borgo, S., Ferrario, R., Gangemi, A., Guarino, N., Masolo, C., Porello, D., Sanfilippo, E. M., & Vieu, L. (2022). DOLCE: A descriptive ontology for linguistic and cognitive engineering1. *Applied Ontology*, 17(1), 45–69. <https://doi.org/10.3233/AO-210259>
- Breuker, J., & Hoekstra, R. (n.d.). *Epistemology and ontology in core ontologies: FOLaw and LRI-Core, two core ontologies for law*.

- Breuker, J., Valente, A., & Winkels, R. (2005). Use and Reuse of Legal Ontologies in Knowledge Engineering and Information Management. In V. R. Benjamins, P. Casanovas, J. Breuker, & A. Gangemi (Eds.), *Law and the Semantic Web: Legal Ontologies, Methodologies, Legal Information Retrieval, and Applications* (pp. 36–64). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-32253-5_4
- Broby, D., Daly, A., & Legg, D. (2022). Towards Secure and Intelligent Regulatory Technology (Regtech): A Research Agenda. *Technology and Regulation, 2022*, 88–99. <https://doi.org/10.71265/cb65xb64>
- Cambronero, M. E., Martínez, M. A., Vara, J. L. de la, Cebrián, D., & Valero, V. (2022). GDPRValidator: A tool to enable companies using cloud services to be GDPR compliant. *PeerJ Computer Science, 8*, e1171. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj-cs.1171>
- Casanovas, P., Palmirani, M., Peroni, S., van Engers, T., & Vitali, F. (2016). Semantic Web for the Legal Domain: The next step. *Semantic Web, 7*(3), 213–227. <https://doi.org/10.3233/SW-160224>
- Castellanos Ardila, J. P., Gallina, B., & Ul Muram, F. (2022). Compliance checking of software processes: A systematic literature review. *Journal of Software: Evolution and Process, 34*(5), e2440. <https://doi.org/10.1002/smr.2440>
- Cavoukian, A. (n.d.). *Privacy by Design The 7 Foundational Principles*.
- Ceci, M., & Bianculli, D. (2026). Beyond the Digital Judge: Legal Reasoning in Compliance Checking and Compliance Choices. In L. Hagedorn, U. Schmid, S. Winter, & S. Woltran (Eds.), *Digital Humanism* (pp. 137–152). Springer Nature Switzerland. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-032-11108-1_10
- Cejas, O. A., Azeem, M. I., Abualhaija, S., & Briand, L. C. (2023). NLP-Based Automated Compliance Checking of Data Processing Agreements Against GDPR. *IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering, 49*(9), 4282–4303. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TSE.2023.3288901>
- Chalkidis, I., Fergadiotis, M., Malakasiotis, P., Aletras, N., & Androutsopoulos, I. (2020). LEGAL-BERT: The Muppets straight out of Law School. *Findings of the Association for Computational Linguistics: EMNLP 2020*, 2898–2904. <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2020.findings-emnlp.261>
- Chalkidis, I., Jana, A., Hartung, D., Bommarito, M., Androutsopoulos, I., Katz, D., & Aletras, N. (2022). LexGLUE: A Benchmark Dataset for Legal Language Understanding in English. In S. Muresan, P. Nakov, & A. Villavicencio (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 60th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics (Volume 1: Long Papers)* (pp. 4310–4330). Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2022.acl-long.297>
- Chang, K.-W., Prabhakaran, V., & Ordonez, V. (2019). Bias and Fairness in Natural Language Processing. In T. Baldwin & M. Carpuat (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 2019 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing and the 9th International Joint Conference on Natural Language Processing (EMNLP-IJCNLP): Tutorial Abstracts*. Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://aclanthology.org/D19-2004/>

D2.2 Survey of Compliance Methods and Tools

- Cherubini, M., Romano, F., Bolioli, A., De, L., & Sangermano, M. (2024). *Improving the accessibility of EU laws: The Chat-EUR-Lex project*. Ital-IA 2024: 4th National Conference on Artificial Intelligence, Naples, Italy.
- Chesani, F., Gavanelli, M., Lamma, E., Mello, P., & Montali, M. (2018). Evaluating Compliance: From LTL to Abductive Logic Programming. *Fundamenta Informaticae*, 159(1–2), 35–63. <https://doi.org/10.3233/FI-2018-1657>
- Chisholm, R. M. (1963). Contrary-to-Duty Imperatives and Deontic Logic. *Analysis*, 24(2), 33–36. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3327064>
- Choudhry, M. D., Sundarajan, M., Sundaram, K., & Rama, A. K. (2024). Bias and Fairness in Generative AI. In S. Balasubramaniam, S. Kadry, A. Prasanth, & R. Kumar Dhanaraj (Eds.), *Generative AI and LLMs* (pp. 177–192). De Gruyter. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783111425078-009>
- Chouhan, A., & Gertz, M. (2025). *From Answers to Guidance: A Proactive Dialogue System for Legal Documents* (arXiv:2510.19723). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2510.19723>
- Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions* | Cochrane. (n.d.). Retrieved March 10, 2026, from <https://www.cochrane.org/authors/handbooks-and-manuals/handbook>
- Cole, J. (2021, May 24). *The Family Educational Rights and Privacy Act (FERPA): Legal Issues* [Legislation]. U.S. Congressional Research Service. <https://www.congress.gov/crs-product/R46799>
- Commission Nationale de l’Informatique et des Libertés. (2018). *Privacy Impact Assessment (PIA)*. <https://www.cnil.fr/en/privacy-impact-assessment-pia>
- Compliance & Risks. (2025). *Compliance Risk Assessment Methodologies: A Strategic Guide to Protecting Your Organization*. <https://www.complianceandrisks.com/blog/compliance-risk-assessment-methodologies-a-strategic-guide-to-protecting-your-organization/>
- Corazza, M., Palmirani, M., Sapienza, S., & Longo, G. (2025). Reporting Requests Modelling in European Legislation with a Hybrid AI Approach. *Proceedings of the Twentieth International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Law*, 93–102. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3769126.3769255>
- CUBE. (2026). *Regulatory Compliance Solutions | RegTech | CUBE*. <https://cube.global/solutions>
- Dal Pont, T., Galli, F., Sartor, G., & Contissa, G. (2025). “Lost in EU Regulation? Don’t Worry, AI Found the Obligation”: Extracting and Representing Legal Obligations in the GDPR the DSA and the AI Act. *Proceedings of the Twentieth International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Law*, 129–138. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3769126.3769260>
- de Moura, L., & Bjørner, N. (2008). Z3: An Efficient SMT Solver. In C. R. Ramakrishnan & J. Rehof (Eds.), *Tools and Algorithms for the Construction and Analysis of Systems* (pp. 337–340). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-78800-3_24
- De Vos, M., Kirrane, S., Padget, J., & Satoh, K. (2019). ODRL Policy Modelling and Compliance Checking. In P. Fodor, M. Montali, D. Calvanese, & D. Roman (Eds.), *Rules and Reasoning*

(pp. 36–51). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-31095-0_3

Decision Model and Notation™ (DMN™) | Object Management Group. (n.d.). Retrieved March 3, 2026, from <https://www.omg.org/dmn/>

Delorme, G., Talens, G., & Disson, E. (2022). An Ontology for Data Regulation: *Proceedings of the 14th International Joint Conference on Knowledge Discovery, Knowledge Engineering and Knowledge Management*, 66–74. <https://doi.org/10.5220/0011548400003335>

Demetzou, K. (2019). Data Protection Impact Assessment: A tool for accountability and the unclarified concept of ‘high risk’ in the General Data Protection Regulation. *Computer Law & Security Review*, 35(6), 105342. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clsr.2019.105342>

Deng, M., Wuyts, K., Scandariato, R., Preneel, B., & Joosen, W. (2011). A privacy threat analysis framework: Supporting the elicitation and fulfillment of privacy requirements. *Requirements Engineering*, 16(1), 3–32. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00766-010-0115-7>

Deroy, A., Bailung, N. K., Ghosh, K., Ghosh, S., & Chakraborty, A. (2024). *Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Legal Data Mining* (arXiv:2405.14707). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2405.14707>

Devlin, J., Chang, M.-W., Lee, K., & Toutanova, K. (2018). BERT: Pre-training of Deep Bidirectional Transformers for Language Understanding. *arXiv Preprint arXiv:1810.04805*.

Dozier, C., Kondadadi, R., Light, M., Vachher, A., Veeramachaneni, S., & Wudali, R. (2010). Named entity recognition and resolution in legal text. In *Semantic processing of legal texts: Where the language of law meets the law of language* (pp. 27–43). Springer.

Drechsler, L. (2021). Wanted: LED adequacy decisions. How the absence of any LED adequacy decision is hurting the protection of fundamental rights in a law enforcement context. *International Data Privacy Law*, 11(2), 182–195. <https://doi.org/10.1093/idpl/ipaa019>

Drools rule engine: Drools Documentation. (n.d.). Retrieved March 3, 2026, from <https://docs.drools.org/8.38.0.Final/drools-docs/docs-website/drools/rule-engine/index.html>

Elgammal, A., Turetken, O., van den Heuvel, W.-J., & Papazoglou, M. (2011). On the Formal Specification of Regulatory Compliance: A Comparative Analysis. In E. M. Maximilien, G. Rossi, S.-T. Yuan, H. Ludwig, & M. Fantinato (Eds.), *Service-Oriented Computing* (pp. 27–38). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-19394-1_4

European Commission. (n.d.-a). *Harmonised Standards—Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs*. Retrieved February 23, 2026, from https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/single-market/goods/european-standards/harmonised-standards_en

European Commission. (n.d.-b). *How can I demonstrate that my organisation is compliant with the GDPR?* Retrieved March 4, 2026, from https://commission.europa.eu/law/law-topic/data-protection/rules-business-and-organisations/obligations/how-can-i-demonstrate-my-organisation-compliant-gdpr_en

D2.2 Survey of Compliance Methods and Tools

- European Commission. (n.d.-c). *When is a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) required?* Retrieved March 5, 2026, from https://commission.europa.eu/law/law-topic/data-protection/rules-business-and-organisations/obligations/when-data-protection-impact-assessment-dpia-required_en
- European Commission. (2023, January 30). *Europrivacy: The first certification mechanism to ensure compliance with GDPR | Shaping Europe's digital future*. <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/news/europrivacy-first-certification-mechanism-ensure-compliance-gdpr>
- European Commission. (2024, October 11). *Data Governance Act explained | Shaping Europe's digital future*. <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/data-governance-act-explained>
- European Commission. (2025a, November 19). *Simpler EU digital rules and new digital wallets to save billions for businesses* [Text]. European Commission - European Commission. https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_25_2718
- European Commission. (2025b, December 15). *Data Act explained | Shaping Europe's digital future*. <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/factpages/data-act-explained>
- European Commission. (2026a, March 3). *AI Act | Shaping Europe's digital future*. <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/regulatory-framework-ai>
- European Commission. (2026b, March 20). *Standardisation of the AI Act*. <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/ai-act-standardisation>
- European Data Protection Board. (n.d.). *Register of certification mechanisms, seals and marks | European Data Protection Board*. Retrieved March 5, 2026, from https://www.edpb.europa.eu/our-work-tools/accountability-tools/certification-mechanisms-seals-and-marks_en
- European Union. (2018, May 25). *General data protection regulation (GDPR) | EUR-Lex*. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/EN/legal-content/summary/general-data-protection-regulation-gdpr.html>
- European Union. (2024, July 12). *Interoperable Europe Act | EUR-Lex*. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/EN/legal-content/summary/interoperable-europe-act.html>
- Falcarin, P., Chowdhury, P., Carbone, E., Scantamburlo, T., Tripodi, R., & Vascon, S. (2025). Legal Requirements Compliance using NLP and Knowledge Graphs. *2025 IEEE 33rd International Requirements Engineering Conference Workshops (REW)*, 412–418. <https://doi.org/10.1109/REW66121.2025.00060>
- Farzindar, A., & Lapalme, G. (2004). Letsum, an automatic legal text summarizing. *Legal Knowledge and Information Systems: JURIX*, 11.
- Fdhila, W., Gall, M., Rinderle-Ma, S., Mangler, J., & Indiono, C. (2016). Classification and Formalization of Instance-Spanning Constraints in Process-Driven Applications. In M. La Rosa, P. Loos, & O. Pastor (Eds.), *Business Process Management* (pp. 348–364). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-45348-4_20

D2.2 Survey of Compliance Methods and Tools

- Filtz, E., Kirrane, S., & Polleres, A. (2021). The linked legal data landscape: Linking legal data across different countries. *Artificial Intelligence and Law*, 29(4), 485–539. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10506-021-09282-8>
- Forgy, C. L. (1982). Rete: A fast algorithm for the many pattern/many object pattern match problem. *Artificial Intelligence*, 19(1), 17–37. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0004-3702\(82\)90020-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/0004-3702(82)90020-0)
- Francesconi, E., & Governatori, G. (2023). Patterns for legal compliance checking in a decidable framework of linked open data. *Artificial Intelligence and Law*, 31(3), 445–464. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10506-022-09317-8>
- Gandon, F., Governatori, G., & Villata, S. (n.d.). *Normative Requirements as Linked Data*.
- Gangemi, A. (2007). *Design Patterns for Legal Ontology Constructions*. (Vol. 321, p. 85).
- Gangemi, A., Prisco, A., Sagri, M. T., Steve, G., & Tiscornia, D. (2003). *Some Ontological Tools to Support Legal Regulatory Compliance, with a Case Study* (Vol. 2889, p. 620). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-39962-9_64
- Gangemi, A., Sagri, M. T., & Tiscornia, D. (2005). *A Constructive Framework for Legal Ontologies* (pp. 97–124). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-32253-5_7
- Garousi, V., Felderer, M., & Mäntylä, M. V. (2019). Guidelines for including grey literature and conducting multivocal literature reviews in software engineering. *Information and Software Technology*, 106, 101–121. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.infsof.2018.09.006>
- Garza, L., Elluri, L., Piplai, A., Kotal, A., Gupta, D., & Joshi, A. (2024). PrivComp-KG: Leveraging KG and LLM for Compliance Verification. *2024 IEEE 6th International Conference on Trust, Privacy and Security in Intelligent Systems, and Applications (TPS-ISA)*, 97–106. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPS-ISA62245.2024.00021>
- Garzo, G., & Palumbo, A. (2025). Human-in-the-Loop: Legal Knowledge Formalization in Attempto Controlled English. *2025 13th International Symposium on Digital Forensics and Security (ISDFS)*, 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISDFS65363.2025.11011971>
- Gebser, M., Kaminski, R., Kaufmann, B., & Schaub, T. (2019). Multi-shot ASP solving with clingo. *Theory and Practice of Logic Programming*, 19(1), 27–82. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1471068418000054>
- Gelbart, D., & Smith, J. (1991). Flexicon, a new legal information retrieval system. *Can. L. Libr.*, 16, 9.
- Gill-Pedro, E. (2025). Fundamental Rights Impact Assessments in the EU’s AI Act: A teleological and contextual analysis of the obligations of deployers. *European Journal of Law and Technology*, 16(3). <https://www.ejlt.org/index.php/ejlt/article/view/1065>
- Giordano, L., Martelli, A., & Dupré, D. T. (2013). Temporal deontic action logic for the verification of compliance to norms in ASP. *Proceedings of the Fourteenth International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Law, ICAIL '13*, 53–62. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2514601.2514608>

- Giordano, S. M. (2021). The Impact of Schrems II on the Modern Multinational Information Security Practice, Part 1: The Potential Disruption to International Commerce. *ISACA Journal*, 6. <https://www.isaca.org/resources/isaca-journal/issues/2021/volume-6/the-impact-of-schrems-ii-on-the-modern-multinational-information-security-practice-part-1>
- Giunchiglia, F., & Zaihrayeu, I. (2008). *Lightweight Ontologies*. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-39940-9_1314
- Glimm, B., Horrocks, I., Motik, B., Stoilos, G., & Wang, Z. (2014). Hermit: An OWL 2 Reasoner. *Journal of Automated Reasoning*, 53(3), 245–269. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10817-014-9305-1>
- Golpayegani, D., Pandit, H. J., & Lewis, D. (2023). To Be High-Risk, or Not To Be—Semantic Specifications and Implications of the AI Act’s High-Risk AI Applications and Harmonised Standards. *Proceedings of the 2023 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency, FAccT ’23*, 905–915. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3593013.3594050>
- Golpayegani, D., Pandit, H., & Lewis, D. (2022). *AIRO: An Ontology for Representing AI Risks Based on the Proposed EU AI Act and ISO Risk Management Standards*. <https://doi.org/10.3233/SSW220008>
- Goodenough, O. R., & Carlson, P. J. (2024). Words or code first? Is the legacy document or a code statement the better starting point for complexity-reducing legal automation? *Philosophical Transactions. Series A, Mathematical, Physical, and Engineering Sciences*, 382(2270), 20230160. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsta.2023.0160>
- Goodman, B., & Flaxman, S. (2017). European Union Regulations on Algorithmic Decision-Making and a “Right to Explanation.” *AI Magazine*, 38(3), 50–57. <https://doi.org/10.1609/aimag.v38i3.2741>
- Gordon, T. F. (2008). Constructing Legal Arguments with Rules in the Legal Knowledge Interchange Format (LKIF). In P. Casanovas, G. Sartor, N. Casellas, & R. Rubino (Eds.), *Computable Models of the Law* (pp. 162–184). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-85569-9_11
- Governatori, G., & Palmirani, M. (2026). Legal Explanation in Defeasible Deontic Logic via LegalRuleML. *Proceedings of the Twentieth International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Law, ICAIL ’25*, 500–501. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3769126.3769257>
- Governatori, G., Rotolo, A., & Sartor, G. (n.d.). *Logic and the Law: Philosophical Foundations, Deontics, and Defeasible Reasoning*.
- Governatori, G., & Sadiq, S. (2009). *The Journey to Business Process Compliance*. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-60566-288-6.ch020>
- Griffo, C., Almeida, J., Almeida, A., & Guizzardi, G. (2016). *A Pattern for the Representation of Legal Relations in a Legal Core Ontology*.
- Guha, N., Nyarko, J., Ho, D., Ré, C., Chilton, A., K, A., Chohlas-Wood, A., Peters, A., Waldon, B., Rockmore, D., Zambrano, D., Talisman, D., Hoque, E., Surani, F., Fagan, F., Sarfaty, G., Dickinson, G., Porat, H., Hegland, J., ... Li, Z. (2023). LegalBench: A Collaboratively Built

- Benchmark for Measuring Legal Reasoning in Large Language Models. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 36, 44123–44279.
- Guizzardi, G., Botti Benevides, A., Fonseca, C. M., Porello, D., Almeida, J. P. A., & Prince Sales, T. (2022). UFO: Unified Foundational Ontology. *Applied Ontology*, 17(1), 167–210. <https://doi.org/10.3233/AO-210256>
- Guizzardi, G., Wagner, G., Almeida, J. P. A., & Guizzardi, R. S. S. (2015). Towards ontological foundations for conceptual modeling: The unified foundational ontology (UFO) story. *Applied Ontology*, 10(3–4), 259–271. <https://doi.org/10.3233/AO-150157>
- Guo, D., Onstein, E., & Rosa, A. D. L. (2021). A Semantic Approach for Automated Rule Compliance Checking in Construction Industry. *IEEE Access*, 9, 129648–129660. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3108226>
- Haarmann, S., Holfter, A., Pufahl, L., & Weske, M. (2021). Formal Framework for Checking Compliance of Data-Driven Case Management. *Journal on Data Semantics*, 10(1), 143–163. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13740-021-00120-3>
- Hagendorff, T. (2020). The Ethics of AI Ethics: An Evaluation of Guidelines. *Minds and Machines*, 30(1), 99–120. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11023-020-09517-8>
- Hamfelt, A. (1995). Formalizing multiple interpretation of legal knowledge. *Artificial Intelligence and Law*, 3(4), 221–265. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00871851>
- Harris, L., & Jaikaran, C. (2024). *Highlights of the 2023 Executive Order on Artificial Intelligence for Congress* (Legislation No. R47843). U.S. Congressional Research Service. <https://www.congress.gov/crs-product/R47843>
- Hashmi, M., Governatori, G., Lam, H.-P., & Wynn, M. T. (2018). Are we done with business process compliance: State of the art and challenges ahead. *Knowledge and Information Systems*, 57, 79–133. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10115-017-1142-1>
- Hashmi, M., Governatori, G., & Wynn, M. T. (2014). Modeling Obligations with Event-Calculus. In A. Bikakis, P. Fodor, & D. Roman (Eds.), *Rules on the Web. From Theory to Applications* (pp. 296–310). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-09870-8_22
- Hassani, S. (2024). *Enhancing Legal Compliance and Regulation Analysis with Large Language Models* (arXiv:2404.17522). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2404.17522>
- Hassija, V., Chamola, V., Mahapatra, A., Singal, A., Goel, D., Huang, K., Scardapane, S., Spinelli, I., Mahmud, M., & Hussain, A. (2024). Interpreting Black-Box Models: A Review on Explainable Artificial Intelligence. *Cognitive Computation*, 16(1), 45–74. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12559-023-10179-8>
- Hendrycks, D., Burns, C., Chen, A., & Ball, S. (2021). *CUAD: An Expert-Annotated NLP Dataset for Legal Contract Review* (arXiv:2103.06268). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2103.06268>

D2.2 Survey of Compliance Methods and Tools

- Herrestad, H. (1991). Norms and formalization. *Proceedings of the 3rd International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Law, ICAIL '91*, 175–184. <https://doi.org/10.1145/112646.112667>
- Hoekstra, R., Breuker, J., Di Bello, M., & Boer, A. (2007). The LKIF core ontology of basic legal concepts. *CEUR Workshop Proc.*, 321, 43–63.
- Hoepman, J.-H. (2014). Privacy Design Strategies. In N. Cuppens-Boulahia, F. Cuppens, S. Jajodia, A. Abou El Kalam, & T. Sans (Eds.), *ICT Systems Security and Privacy Protection* (pp. 446–459). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-55415-5_38
- Holzmann, G. J. (2008). *The spin model checker: Primer and reference manual* (4th print). Addison-Wesley.
- Horner, E., Mateis, C., Governatori, G., & Ciabattoni, A. (2025). *Toward Robust Legal Text Formalization into Defeasible Deontic Logic using LLMs* (arXiv:2506.08899). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2506.08899>
- Ibitola, J. (2025). AML Program Effectiveness for RIAs: Key KPIs and Metrics under FinCEN’s 2028 Rule. *Flagright*. <https://www.flagright.com/post/key-aml-kpis-for-rias-fincen-compliance-rule>
- International data transfers | European Data Protection Board*. (n.d.). Retrieved March 3, 2026, from https://www.edpb.europa.eu/sme-data-protection-guide/international-data-transfers_en
- J. Pandit, H., Esteves, B., P. Krog, G., Ryan, P., Golpayegani, D., & Flake, J. (2025). Data Privacy Vocabulary (DPV) – Version 2.0. In G. Demartini, K. Hose, M. Acosta, M. Palmonari, G. Cheng, H. Skaf-Molli, N. Ferranti, D. Hernández, & A. Hogan (Eds.), *The Semantic Web – ISWC 2024* (Vol. 15233, pp. 171–193). Springer Nature Switzerland. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-77847-6_10
- Janssen, M., Estevez, E., & Janowski, T. (2014). Interoperability in Big, Open, and Linked Data—Organizational Maturity, Capabilities, and Data Portfolios. *Computer*, 47(10), 44–49. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MC.2014.290>
- Jesus, S., Saleiro, P., De Silva, I. O., Jorge, B. M., Ribeiro, R. P., Gama, J., Bizarro, P., & Ghani, R. (2024). Aequitas Flow: Streamlining Fair ML Experimentation. *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, 25(354), 1–7.
- Jia, L., Chen, M., Chen, C., & Jin, Y. (2025). A Semantic Web and IFC-Based Framework for Automated BIM Compliance Checking. *Buildings*, 15(15), 2633. <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings15152633>
- Jones, A. J. I., & Sergot, M. (1992). Deontic logic in the representation of law: Towards a methodology. *Artificial Intelligence and Law*, 1(1), 45–64. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00118478>
- Joshi, K. P., Elluri, L., & Nagar, A. (2020). An Integrated Knowledge Graph to Automate Cloud Data Compliance. *IEEE Access*, 8, 148541–148555. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3008964>

D2.2 Survey of Compliance Methods and Tools

- Jouault, F., Allilaire, F., Bézivin, J., & Kurtev, I. (2008). ATL: A model transformation tool. *Science of Computer Programming*, 72(1–2), 31–39. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scico.2007.08.002>
- Kalamkar, P., Agarwal, A., Tiwari, A., Gupta, S., Karn, S., & Raghavan, V. (2022). Named Entity Recognition in Indian court judgments. *Proceedings of the Natural Legal Language Processing Workshop 2022*, 184–193. <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2022.nllp-1.15>
- Kalmenovitz, J., Lowry, M., & Volkova, E. (2025). Regulatory Fragmentation. *The Journal of Finance*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jofi.13423>
- Kellogg, G., Champin, P.-A., & Longley, D. (2019). *JSON-LD 1.1 – A JSON-based Serialization for Linked Data* [Technical Report]. W3C. <https://hal.science/hal-02141614>
- Kelsen, H. (1966). On The Pure Theory of Law. *Israel Law Review*, 1(1), 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0021223700013595>
- Khorshidi, S., Nikfarjam, A., Shankar, S., Sang, Y., Govind, Y., Jang, H., Kasgari, A., McClimans, A., Soliman, M., Konda, V., Fakhry, A., & Qi, X. (2025). *ODKE+: Ontology-Guided Open-Domain Knowledge Extraction with LLMs* (arXiv:2509.04696). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2509.04696>
- Kilian, R., Jäck, L., & Ebel, D. (2025). European AI Standards – Technical Standardisation and Implementation Challenges under the EU AI Act. *European Journal of Risk Regulation*, 16(3), 1038–1062. <https://doi.org/10.1017/err.2025.10032>
- Kingston, J. (2017). Using artificial intelligence to support compliance with the general data protection regulation. *Artificial Intelligence and Law*, 25(4), 429–443. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10506-017-9206-9>
- Knublauch, H., Fergerson, R. W., Noy, N. F., & Musen, M. A. (2004). The Protégé OWL Plugin: An Open Development Environment for Semantic Web Applications. In S. A. McIlraith, D. Plexousakis, & F. van Harmelen (Eds.), *The Semantic Web – ISWC 2004* (pp. 229–243). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-30475-3_17
- Lam, H.-P., & Governatori, G. (2009). The Making of SPINdle. In G. Governatori, J. Hall, & A. Paschke (Eds.), *Rule Interchange and Applications* (pp. 315–322). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-04985-9_29
- Lasek-Markey, M., & Hogan, L. (2025). Delivering on the Promise of the Fundamental Rights Impact Assessments in the EU AI Act: Intersectionality and Vulnerability. *European Journal of Law and Technology*, 16(2). <https://ejlt.org/index.php/ejlt/article/view/1046>
- Leitner, E., Rehm, G., & Schneider, J. M. (2020). A dataset of German legal documents for named entity recognition. *Proceedings of the Twelfth Language Resources and Evaluation Conference*, 4478–4485.
- Leone, V., Di Caro, L., & Villata, S. (2020). Taking Stock of Legal Ontologies: A Feature-Based Comparative Analysis. *Artificial Intelligence and Law*, 28(2), 207–236.

D2.2 Survey of Compliance Methods and Tools

- Li, Y., Yang, M., Zhao, Q., Li, Z., Ma, Z., Liu, Y., & Hei, X. (2023). A Semantic Representation Method of Building Codes Applied to Compliance Checking. *Mathematics*, 11(11), 2552. <https://doi.org/10.3390/math11112552>
- Lindahl, L., & Reidhav, D. (2015). Conflict of Legal Norms: Definition and Varieties. In M. Araszkievicz & K. Pleszka (Eds.), *Logic in the Theory and Practice of Lawmaking* (pp. 49–95). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-19575-9_2
- Liu, S., Cao, J., Li, Y., Yang, R., & Wen, Z. (2024). Low-resource court judgment summarization for common law systems. *Information Processing & Management*, 61(5), 103796. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ipm.2024.103796>
- Lohmann, S., Negru, S., Haag, F., & Ertl, T. (2014). VOWL 2: User-Oriented Visualization of Ontologies. In K. Janowicz, S. Schlobach, P. Lambrix, & E. Hyvönen (Eds.), *Knowledge Engineering and Knowledge Management* (Vol. 8876, pp. 266–281). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-13704-9_21
- Luminance. (2025). *A Guide to AI for Compliance [White paper]*. <https://luminance.com/wp-content/uploads/2025/10/A-Guide-to-AI-for-Compliance.pdf>
- Ly, L. T., Maggi, F. M., Montali, M., Rinderle-Ma, S., & van der Aalst, W. M. P. (2015). Compliance monitoring in business processes: Functionalities, application, and tool-support. *Information Systems*, 54, 209–234. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.is.2015.02.007>
- Malik, S., & Jain, S. (2017). Ontology based context aware model. *2017 International Conference on Computational Intelligence in Data Science (ICCIDS)*, 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCIDS.2017.8272632>
- Mantelero, A. (2024). The Fundamental Rights Impact Assessment (FRIA) in the AI Act: Roots, legal obligations and key elements for a model template. *Computer Law & Security Review*, 54, 106020. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clsr.2024.106020>
- Masolo, C., Borgo, S., Gangemi, A., Guarino, N., & Oltramari, A. (n.d.). *WonderWeb Deliverable D18*.
- Massey, A. K., Rutledge, R. L., Antón, A. I., & Swire, P. P. (2014). Identifying and classifying ambiguity for regulatory requirements. *2014 IEEE 22nd International Requirements Engineering Conference (RE)*, 83–92.
- Matulevičius, R., Tom, J., Kala, K., & Sing, E. (2020). A Method for Managing GDPR Compliance in Business Processes. In N. Herbaut & M. La Rosa (Eds.), *Advanced Information Systems Engineering* (pp. 100–112). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-58135-0_9
- McDaniel, M., & Storey, V. C. (2019). Evaluating Domain Ontologies: Clarification, Classification, and Challenges. *ACM Comput. Surv.*, 52(4), 70:1-70:44. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3329124>
- Metcalf, J., Moss, E., Watkins, E. A., Singh, R., & Elish, M. C. (2021). Algorithmic Impact Assessments and Accountability: The Co-construction of Impacts. *Proceedings of the 2021 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency*, 735–746. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3442188.3445935>

D2.2 Survey of Compliance Methods and Tools

- Moens, M.-F., Uyttendaele, C., & Dumortier, J. (1999). Abstracting of legal cases: The potential of clustering based on the selection of representative objects. *Journal of the American Society for Information Science*, 50(2), 151–161.
- MONEYVAL. (2024). *Risk-Based Approach*.
<https://www.coe.int/en/web/moneyval/implementation/risk-based-approach>
- Mowbray, A., Chung, P., & Greenleaf, G. (2023). Representing legislative Rules as Code: Reducing the problems of ‘scaling up.’ *Computer Law & Security Review*, 48, 105772.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clsr.2022.105772>
- Muehlen, M. zur, & Ho, D. T.-Y. (2006). Risk Management in the BPM Lifecycle. In C. J. Bussler & A. Haller (Eds.), *Business Process Management Workshops* (pp. 454–466). Springer.
https://doi.org/10.1007/11678564_42
- Mügge, D. (2024). EU AI sovereignty: For whom, to what end, and to whose benefit? *Journal of European Public Policy*, 31(8), 2200–2225.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/13501763.2024.2318475>
- National Institute of Standards and Technology (US). (2024). *A plan for global engagement on AI standards* (Error: 100-5; p. error: 100-5). National Institute of Standards and Technology (U.S.). <https://doi.org/10.6028/NIST.AI.100-5>
- Nguyen, D.-H., Nguyen, B.-S., Nghiem, N. V. D., Le, D. T., Khatun, M. A., Nguyen, M.-T., & Le, H. (2021). Robust deep reinforcement learning for extractive legal summarization. *International Conference on Neural Information Processing*, 597–604.
- Niblett, B. (1980). *Computer Science and Law*. CUP Archive.
- Novelli, C., Governatori, G., & Rotolo, A. (2023). Automating Business Process Compliance for the EU AI Act. In *Legal Knowledge and Information Systems* (pp. 125–130). IOS Press.
<https://doi.org/10.3233/FAIA230955>
- Novotná, T., & Libal, T. (2022). An Evaluation of Methodologies for Legal Formalization. In D. Calvaresi, A. Najjar, M. Winikoff, & K. Främling (Eds.), *Explainable and Transparent AI and Multi-Agent Systems* (Vol. 13283, pp. 189–203). Springer International Publishing.
https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-15565-9_12
- Oltramari, A., Piraviperumal, D., Schaub, F., Wilson, S., Cherivirala, S., Norton, T. B., Russell, N. C., Story, P., Reidenberg, J., & Sadeh, N. (2018). PrivOnto: A semantic framework for the analysis of privacy policies. *Semantic Web*, 9(2), 185–203. <https://doi.org/10.3233/SW-170283>
- Open Policy Agent (OPA) | Open Policy Agent*. (n.d.). Retrieved March 3, 2026, from <https://openpolicyagent.org/docs>
- Orlando, A., & Santoro, M. (2025). A semantic approach to understanding GDPR fines: From text to compliance insights. *Computer Law & Security Review*, 59, 106187.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clsr.2025.106187>

- OSCAL - *Open Security Controls Assessment Language*. (n.d.). Retrieved March 3, 2026, from <https://pages.nist.gov/OSCAL/>
- Oyasiji, O., Okesiji, A., Lawal, A., Otokiti, B. O., & Gobile, S. (2024). Developing Conceptual AI Models for Legal Text Interpretation and Regulatory Compliance Automation. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Growth Evaluation*, 5(2), 1098–1104. <https://doi.org/10.54660/IJMRGE.2024.5.2.1098-1104>
- Oyesiku, V. (2023, June 16). The Power of NLP for Legal and Compliance. *Kensho Blog*. <https://blog.kensho.com/the-power-of-nlp-for-legal-and-compliance-3a1f4a537a83>
- Păis, V., Mitrofan, M., Gasan, C. L., Coneschi, V., & Ianov, A. (2021). Named Entity Recognition in the Romanian Legal Domain. *Proceedings of the Natural Legal Language Processing Workshop 2021*, 9–18. <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2021.nllp-1.2>
- Palmirani, M., & Brighi, R. (2006). Time Model for Managing the Dynamic of Normative System. In M. A. Wimmer, H. J. Scholl, Å. Grönlund, & K. V. Andersen (Eds.), *Electronic Government* (pp. 207–218). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/11823100_19
- Palmirani, M., Ceci, M., Radicioni, D., & Mazzei, A. (2011). FrameNet model of the suspension of norms. *Proceedings of the 13th International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Law*, 189–193. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2018358.2018385>
- Palmirani, M., Cervone, L., & Vitali, F. (2011). A Legal Document Ontology: The Missing Layer in Legal Document Modelling. In G. Sartor, P. Casanovas, M. Biasiotti, & M. Fernández-Barrera (Eds.), *Approaches to Legal Ontologies: Theories, Domains, Methodologies* (pp. 167–178). Springer Netherlands. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-0120-5_10
- Palmirani, M., Corazza, M., Longo, G., Sapienza, S., & European Commission. Directorate-General for Digital Services. (2025). *Hybrid AI to enhance legal drafting with LEOS*. Publications Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/10.2799/1298773>
- Palmirani, M., & Governatori, G. (2018). Modelling Legal Knowledge for GDPR Compliance Checking. In *Legal Knowledge and Information Systems* (pp. 101–110). IOS Press. <https://doi.org/10.3233/978-1-61499-935-5-101>
- Palmirani, M., Governatori, G., & Contissa, G. (2011). Modelling temporal legal rules. *Proceedings of the 13th International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Law, ICAIL '11*, 131–135. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2018358.2018378>
- Palmirani, M., Governatori, G., Rotolo, A., Tabet, S., Boley, H., & Paschke, A. (2011). LegalRuleML: XML-Based Rules and Norms. In F. Olken, M. Palmirani, & D. Sottara (Eds.), *Rule-Based Modeling and Computing on the Semantic Web* (pp. 298–312). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-24908-2_30
- Palmirani, M., Martoni, M., Rossi, A., Bartolini, C., & Robaldo, L. (2018). Legal Ontology for Modelling GDPR Concepts and Norms. In *Legal Knowledge and Information Systems* (pp. 91–100). IOS Press. <https://doi.org/10.3233/978-1-61499-935-5-91>
- Pandit, H. J., Fatema, K., O’Sullivan, D., & Lewis, D. (2018). GDPRtEXT - GDPR as a Linked Data Resource. In A. Gangemi, R. Navigli, M.-E. Vidal, P. Hitzler, R. Troncy, L. Hollink, A. Tordai, &

- M. Alam (Eds.), *The Semantic Web* (pp. 481–495). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-93417-4_31
- Pandit, H. J., O’Sullivan, D., & Lewis, D. (2019). Test-Driven Approach Towards GDPR Compliance. In M. Acosta, P. Cudré-Mauroux, M. Maleshkova, T. Pellegrini, H. Sack, & Y. Sure-Vetter (Eds.), *Semantic Systems. The Power of AI and Knowledge Graphs* (pp. 19–33). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-33220-4_2
- (PDF) Engineering Privacy. (2026). *ResearchGate*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TSE.2008.88>
- Pesic, M., & van der Aalst, W. M. P. (2006). A Declarative Approach for Flexible Business Processes Management. In J. Eder & S. Dustdar (Eds.), *Business Process Management Workshops* (pp. 169–180). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/11837862_18
- Peters, W., Sagri, M. T., Tiscornia, D., & Castagnoli, S. (2006). The LOIS Project. In N. Calzolari, K. Choukri, A. Gangemi, B. Maegaard, J. Mariani, J. Odijk, & D. Tapias (Eds.), *Proceedings of the Fifth International Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation (LREC’06)*. European Language Resources Association (ELRA). <https://aclanthology.org/L06-1352/>
- Peters, W., Sagri, M.-T., & Tiscornia, D. (2007). The structuring of legal knowledge in LOIS. *Artificial Intelligence and Law*, 15(2), 117–135. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10506-007-9034-4>
- Pittl, B., & Fill, H.-G. (2020). A visual modeling approach for the Semantic Web Rule Language. *Semantic Web*, 11(2), 361–389. <https://doi.org/10.3233/SW-180340>
- Polsley, S., Jhunhunwala, P., & Huang, R. (2016). Casesummarizer: A system for automated summarization of legal texts. *Proceedings of COLING 2016, the 26th International Conference on Computational Linguistics: System Demonstrations*, 258–262.
- Prathyush Turaga, V. S., Pahi, T., Tjoa, S., Siami-Namini, S., & Siami Namin, A. (2025). CO2 (Co-Compliance Officer): An LLM-Based Ontology-Driven Methodology for Generating Knowledge Graphs and AI Compliance Checking. *IEEE Access*, 13, 210576–210606. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2025.3639228>
- Prudhomme, T., De Colle, G., Liebers, A., Sculley, A., Xie, P. “Karl,” Cohen, S., & Beverley, J. (2025). A semantic approach to mapping the Provenance Ontology to Basic Formal Ontology. *Scientific Data*, 12(1), 282. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-025-04580-1>
- Pullonen, P., Tom, J., Matulevičius, R., & Toots, A. (2019). Privacy-enhanced BPMN: Enabling data privacy analysis in business processes models. *Software and Systems Modeling*, 18(6), 3235–3264. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10270-019-00718-z>
- Quaranta, M., Amantea, I., Governatori, G., Molinari, M., Billi, M., Galli, F., & Rotolo, A. (2025). *AI Compliance Frameworks: A Handbook For Compliance Tools based on AI Acts’ Requirements*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5555260>
- Ribeiro, M. T., Singh, S., & Guestrin, C. (2016). “Why Should I Trust You?”: Explaining the Predictions of Any Classifier. *Proceedings of the 22nd ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining*, 1135–1144. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2939672.2939778>

- Rigoni, A. (2018). Representing dimensions within the reason model of precedent. *Artificial Intelligence and Law*, 26(1), 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10506-017-9216-7>
- Riveret, R., & Rotolo, A. (2008). Temporal Deontic Defeasible Logic: An Analytical Approach. In P. Casanovas, G. Sartor, N. Casellas, & R. Rubino (Eds.), *Computable Models of the Law* (pp. 239–253). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-85569-9_15
- Robaldo, L., Bartolini, C., Palmirani, M., Rossi, A., Martoni, M., & Lenzini, G. (2020). Formalizing GDPR Provisions in Reified I/O Logic: The DAPRECO Knowledge Base. *Journal of Logic, Language and Information*, 29(4), 401–449. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10849-019-09309-z>
- Robaldo, L., Pacenza, F., Zangari, J., Calegari, R., Calimeri, F., & Siragusa, G. (2023). Efficient compliance checking of RDF data. *Journal of Logic and Computation*, 33(8), 1753–1776. <https://doi.org/10.1093/logcom/exad034>
- Roberts, M. E., Stewart, B. M., Tingley, D., Lucas, C., Leder-Luis, J., Gadarian, S. K., Albertson, B., & Rand, D. G. (2014). Structural Topic Models for Open-Ended Survey Responses. *American Journal of Political Science*, 58(4), 1064–1082. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ajps.12103>
- Root, V. (2019). The Compliance Process. *Indiana Law Journal*, 94(1), 203–251.
- Roshankish, S., & Fornara, N. (2024). How to Formalize Different Types of Norms in Multi-agent Systems: A Methodology Focused on the T-Norm Model. *SN Computer Science*, 5(6), 749. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42979-024-03052-4>
- Roussey, C., Pinet, F., Kang, M.-A., & Corcho, O. (2011). An Introduction to Ontologies and Ontology Engineering. In *Ontologies in Urban Development Projects* (Vol. 1, pp. 9–38). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-85729-724-2_2
- Roversi, C. (2021). In defence of constitutive rules. *Synthese*, 199(5), 14349–14370. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11229-021-03424-w>
- Rozinat, A., & van der Aalst, W. M. P. (2008). Conformance checking of processes based on monitoring real behavior. *Information Systems*, 33(1), 64–95. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.is.2007.07.001>
- Rundle, D., Paul, S., & Blest, A. (2024). *AI Regulation in Financial Services: Turning Principles into Practice*. <https://www.bclplaw.com/en-US/events-insights-news/ai-regulation-in-financial-services-turning-principles-into-practice.html>
- Ryan, P., Crane, M., & Brennan, R. (2021). GDPR Compliance Tools: Best Practice from RegTech. In J. Filipe, M. Śmiałek, A. Brodsky, & S. Hammoudi (Eds.), *Enterprise Information Systems* (Vol. 417, pp. 905–929). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-75418-1_41
- Ryan, P., Pandit, H. J., & Brennan, R. (2020). *Towards a Semantic Model of the GDPR Register of Processing Activities* (arXiv:2008.00877). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2008.00877>
- Sackmann, S., Kuehnel, S., & Seyffarth, T. (2018). Using Business Process Compliance Approaches for Compliance Management with Regard to Digitization: Evidence from a Systematic

- Literature Review. In M. Weske, M. Montali, I. Weber, & J. vom Brocke (Eds.), *Business Process Management* (pp. 409–425). Springer International Publishing.
- Sadiq, S., Governatori, G., & Namiri, K. (2007). Modeling Control Objectives for Business Process Compliance. In G. Alonso, P. Dadam, & M. Rosemann (Eds.), *Business Process Management* (pp. 149–164). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-75183-0_12
- Sadowski, A., & Chudziak, J. A. (2025). On Verifiable Legal Reasoning: A Multi-Agent Framework with Formalized Knowledge Representations. *Proceedings of the 34th ACM International Conference on Information and Knowledge Management, CIKM '25*, 2535–2545. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3746252.3761057>
- Saint Croix, C., & Thomason, R. H. (2014). Chisholm’s Paradox and Conditional Oughts. In F. Cariani, D. Grossi, J. Meheus, & X. Parent (Eds.), *Deontic Logic and Normative Systems* (pp. 192–207). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-08615-6_15
- Salama, D. M., & El-Gohary, N. M. (2012). *Semantic Modeling for Automated Compliance Checking*. 641–648. [https://doi.org/10.1061/41182\(416\)79](https://doi.org/10.1061/41182(416)79)
- Saleiro, P., Kuester, B., Hinkson, L., London, J., Stevens, A., Anisfeld, A., Rodolfa, K. T., & Ghani, R. (2019). *Aequitas: A Bias and Fairness Audit Toolkit* (arXiv:1811.05577). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1811.05577>
- Salnitri, M., Dalpiaz, F., & Giorgini, P. (2014). Modeling and Verifying Security Policies in Business Processes. In I. Bider, K. Gaaloul, J. Krogstie, S. Nurcan, H. A. Proper, R. Schmidt, & P. Soffer (Eds.), *Enterprise, Business-Process and Information Systems Modeling* (pp. 200–214). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-662-43745-2_14
- Sartor, G. (2005). *Legal reasoning: A cognitive approach to the law*. Springer.
- Scherp, A., Saathoff, C., Franz, T., & Staab, S. (2011). Designing core ontologies. *Applied Ontology*, 6(3), 177–221. <https://doi.org/10.3233/AO-2011-0096>
- Schnitzhofer, F., & Schuetz, C. G. (n.d.). *Towards a Scalable Architecture for Legal Ontologies Integrated into Digital Twins of Administrative Law*.
- Schraagen, M., Bex, F., Van De Luitgaarden, N., & Prijs, D. (2022). Abstractive Summarization of Dutch Court Verdicts Using Sequence-to-sequence Models. *Proceedings of the Natural Legal Language Processing Workshop 2022*, 76–87. <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2022.nllp-1.7>
- Selbst, A. D. (2021). An Institutional View Of Algorithmic Impact Assessments. *Harvard Journal of Law & Technology*, 35(1). https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3867634
- Sergot, M. J., Sadri, F., Kowalski, R. A., Kriwaczek, F., Hammond, P., & Cory, H. T. (1986). The British Nationality Act as a logic program. *Commun. ACM*, 29(5), 370–386. <https://doi.org/10.1145/5689.5920>
- Seun Solomon Bakare, Adekunle Oyeyemi Adeniyi, Chidiogo Uzoamaka Akpuokwe, & Nkechi Emmanuella Eneh. (2024). DATA PRIVACY LAWS AND COMPLIANCE: A COMPARATIVE

REVIEW OF THE EU GDPR AND USA REGULATIONS. *Computer Science & IT Research Journal*, 5(3), 528–543. <https://doi.org/10.51594/csitrj.v5i3.859>

Shadbolt, N., Berners-Lee, T., & Hall, W. (2006). The Semantic Web Revisited. *IEEE Intelligent Systems*, 21(3), 96–101. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MIS.2006.62>

Shen, Z., Lo, K., Yu, L., Dahlberg, N., Schlanger, M., & Downey, D. (2022). Multi-LexSum: Real-world Summaries of Civil Rights Lawsuits at Multiple Granularities. In S. Koyejo, S. Mohamed, A. Agarwal, D. Belgrave, K. Cho, & A. Oh (Eds.), *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems* (Vol. 35, pp. 13158–13173). Curran Associates, Inc. https://proceedings.neurips.cc/paper_files/paper/2022/file/552ef803bef9368c29e53c167de34b55-Paper-Datasets_and_Benchmarks.pdf

Simeri, A. (2023). *GDPR Article Retrieval based on Domain-adaptive and Task-adaptive Legal Pre-trained Language Models*. 14.

Sirin, E., Parsia, B., Grau, B. C., Kalyanpur, A., & Katz, Y. (2007). Pellet: A practical OWL-DL reasoner. *Journal of Web Semantics, Software Engineering and the Semantic Web*, 5(2), 51–53. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.websem.2007.03.004>

Sloane, M., & Wüllhorst, E. (2025). A systematic review of regulatory strategies and transparency mandates in AI regulation in Europe, the United States, and Canada. *Data & Policy*, 7, e11. <https://doi.org/10.1017/dap.2024.54>

Smădu, R.-A., Dinică, I.-R., Avram, A.-M., Cercel, D.-C., Pop, F., & Cercel, M.-C. (2022). Legal Named Entity Recognition with Multi-Task Domain Adaptation. *Proceedings of the Natural Language Processing Workshop 2022*, 305–321. <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2022.nllp-1.29>

Smuha, N. A. (2023). Digital Sovereignty in the European Union: Five Challenges from a Normative Perspective. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4501591>

Soler, G. J., De, N. S., Bassani, E., Sanchez, I., Evas, T., André, A.-A., & Boulangé, T. (2024, October 24). *Harmonised Standards for the European AI Act*. JRC Publications Repository. <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC139430>

Sovrano, F., Hine, E., Anzolut, S., & Bacchelli, A. (2025a). Simplifying software compliance: AI technologies in drafting technical documentation for the AI Act. *Empirical Software Engineering*, 30(4), 91. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10664-025-10645-x>

Sovrano, F., Hine, E., Anzolut, S., & Bacchelli, A. (2025b). Simplifying software compliance: AI technologies in drafting technical documentation for the AI Act. *Empirical Software Engineering*, 30(4), 91. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10664-025-10645-x>

Sovrano, F., Palmirani, M., & Vitali, F. (2020). *Legal Knowledge Extraction for Knowledge Graph Based Question-Answering*. NLD. <https://doi.org/10.3233/FAIA200858>

Srivastava, S., & Bullock, J. (2024). *AI, Global Governance, and Digital Sovereignty* (arXiv:2410.17481). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2410.17481>

D2.2 Survey of Compliance Methods and Tools

- Stahl, B. C., Antoniou, J., Bhalla, N., Brooks, L., Jansen, P., Lindqvist, B., Kirichenko, A., Marchal, S., Rodrigues, R., Santiago, N., Warso, Z., & Wright, D. (2023). A systematic review of artificial intelligence impact assessments. *Artificial Intelligence Review*, 56(11), 12799–12831. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10462-023-10420-8>
- Steinberg, D., Budinsky, F., Paternostro, M., & Merks, E. (2009). *EMF: Eclipse Modeling Framework 2.0* (2nd ed.). Addison-Wesley Professional.
- Štrumbelj, E., & Kononenko, I. (2014). Explaining prediction models and individual predictions with feature contributions. *Knowledge and Information Systems*, 41(3), 647–665. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10115-013-0679-x>
- Sumukh, S., & Shashwat, S. (2024). A Framework for Analyzing Legal Documents by Leveraging Knowledge Graphs. In N. Sharma, A. C. Goje, A. Chakrabarti, & A. M. Bruckstein (Eds.), *Data Management, Analytics and Innovation* (pp. 417–425). Springer Nature. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-97-3245-6_28
- The British Standards Institution. (2025, July 21). *BSI publishes standard to ensure quality among growing AI audit market*. BSI. <https://www.bsigroup.com/en-GB/insights-and-media/media-centre/press-releases/2025/july/bsi-publishes-standard-to-ensure-quality-among-growing-ai-audit-market/>
- The Court of Justice invalidates Decision 2016/1250 on the adequacy of the protection provided by the EU-US Data Protection Shield*. (n.d.).
- Torre, D., Alferez, M., Soltana, G., Sabetzadeh, M., & Briand, L. (2021). Modeling data protection and privacy: Application and experience with GDPR. *Software and Systems Modeling*, 20(6), 2071–2087. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10270-021-00935-5>
- Tosatto, S. C., Governatori, G., & Kelsen, P. (2013). Towards an Abstract Framework for Compliance. *2013 17th IEEE International Enterprise Distributed Object Computing Conference Workshops*, 79–88. <https://doi.org/10.1109/EDOCW.2013.16>
- Valente, A., & Breuker, J. (1995). ON-LINE: An architecture for modelling legal information. *Proceedings of the 5th International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Law, ICAIL '95*, 307–315. <https://doi.org/10.1145/222092.222265>
- van der Aalst, W. (2016). Data Science in Action. In W. van der Aalst (Ed.), *Process Mining: Data Science in Action* (pp. 3–23). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-662-49851-4_1
- Van Engers, T., Boer, A., Breuker, J., Valente, A., & Winkels, R. (2008). Ontologies in the Legal Domain. In H. Chen, L. Brandt, V. Gregg, R. Traunmüller, S. Dawes, E. Hovy, A. Macintosh, & C. A. Larson (Eds.), *Digital Government: E-Government Research, Case Studies, and Implementation* (pp. 233–261). Springer US. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-71611-4_13
- Vanthienen, J., & Wets, G. (1994). From decision tables to expert system shells. *Data & Knowledge Engineering*, 13(3), 265–282. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0169-023X\(94\)00020-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0169-023X(94)00020-4)
- Von Eschenbach, W. J. (2021). Transparency and the Black Box Problem: Why We Do Not Trust AI. *Philosophy & Technology*, 34(4), 1607–1622. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13347-021-00477-0>

D2.2 Survey of Compliance Methods and Tools

von Wright, G. H. (1951a). Deontic Logic. *Mind*, 60(237), 1–15.

von Wright, G. H. (1951b). Deontic Logic. *Mind*, 60(237), 1–15.

Wachter, S., Mittelstadt, B., & Floridi, L. (2017). Why a Right to Explanation of Automated Decision-Making Does Not Exist in the General Data Protection Regulation. *International Data Privacy Law*, 7(2), 76–99. <https://doi.org/10.1093/idpl/ix005>

Witt, A., Huggins, A., Governatori, G., & Buckley, J. (2024). Encoding legislation: A methodology for enhancing technical validation, legal alignment and interdisciplinarity. *Artificial Intelligence and Law*, 32(2), 293–324. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10506-023-09350-1>

Yang, Y., Kim, I.-J., & Yoon, D. (2026). PASTA: A Scalable Framework for Multi-Policy AI Compliance Evaluation (arXiv:2601.11702). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2601.11702>

Yaseen, A. (2023). The role of machine learning in network anomaly detection for cybersecurity. *Sage Science Review of Applied Machine Learning*, 6(8), 16–34.

Yoshino, H. (1995). The systematization of legal meta-inference. *Proceedings of the 5th International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Law, ICAIL '95*, 266–275. <https://doi.org/10.1145/222092.222257>

Zamanzadeh Darban, Z., Webb, G. I., Pan, S., Aggarwal, C., & Salehi, M. (2025). Deep Learning for Time Series Anomaly Detection: A Survey. *ACM Computing Surveys*, 57(1), 1–42. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3691338>

APPENDICES

Appendix A: Tools and Software for Legal Compliance

1. Rule-based tools and methods

Rule-based tools and methods					
Name	Tool or method?	Proprietary?	Description or comment	Reference	URL
Decision Model and Notation (DMN) 1.3	Standard	No	Standard representation of decision logic (decision tables/graphs) to share and implement compliance decisions consistently across stakeholders and systems.	OMG. Decision Model and Notation (DMN) Version 1.3 (About DMN).	https://www.omg.org/spec/DMN/1.3/About-DMN
Drools	Tool	No	Rule engine for executing deterministic compliance rules over facts; supports forward- and backward-chaining inference and rule-firing traces for auditability.	Drools Documentation (Rule Engine).	https://docs.drools.org/latest/drools-docs/drools/rule-engine/index.html
Open Policy Agent (OPA) + Rego	Tool + language	No	Policy-as-code engine and declarative policy language (Rego) to express policy predicates over structured inputs and produce auditable allow/deny decisions.	Open Policy Agent Documentation (OPA + Rego Policy Language).	https://openpolicyagent.org/docs/
NIST OSCAL (Open Security Controls Assessment Language)	Standard	No	Machine-readable formats (XML/JSON/YAML) to represent control catalogs and compliance artifacts, supporting automated	NIST OSCAL project overview.	https://pages.nist.gov/OSCAL/

D2.2 Survey of Compliance Methods and Tools

			assessment and evidence exchange.		
GDPRValidator	Tool	No	Tool to assist GDPR compliance analysis/validation for companies using cloud services; supports guided validation and outputs recommendations/documents.	Cambroner, M.E., et al. (2022). GDPRValidator. PeerJ Computer Science, 8:e1171.	https://peerj.com/articles/cs-1171/
RETE match algorithm	Method	No	Incremental pattern-matching algorithm for production rules; shares partial matches across rules to scale rule execution over large fact bases.	Forgy, C.L. (1982). Rete. Artificial Intelligence, 19(1), 17–37.	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/0004370282900200
Decision table verification (completeness/consistency)	Method	No	Methods to validate decision tables (completeness, consistency, redundancy) and transform them into rule bases, reducing gaps/contradictions before deployment.	Vanthienen, J. & Wets, G. (1994). From Decision Tables to Expert System Shells. Data & Knowledge Engineering, 13(3), 265–282.	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/0169023X94000204
QuickCheck (property-based testing)	Tool/method	No	Property-based testing to generate randomized test cases and check invariants of rule logic; useful for regression testing of evolving compliance rulesets.	Claessen, K. & Hughes, J. (2000). QuickCheck. ICFP 2000.	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/351240.351266

2. Model-based tools and methods

Model-driven tools and methods					
Name	Tool or method?	Proprietary?	Description or comment	Reference	URL
Privacy-Enhanced Business Process Model and Notation (PE-BPMN)	Method/notation	No	Extends Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN) with privacy-related constructs (including privacy-enhancing-technology-related activities) to support modelling and analysis of privacy leakages/information disclosure along business processes.	Pullonen, P., Matulevičius, R. & Bogdanov, D. (2017). PE-BPMN: Privacy-Enhanced Business Process Model and Notation. In BPM 2017, LNCS 10445, 40–56. Springer.	https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-319-65000-5_3
Privacy-enhanced BPMN analysis toolset (Pleak)	Tool	No	Tool support for analysing privacy-enhanced BPMN / PE-BPMN models; supports privacy analysis of information disclosure as described in the PE-BPMN line of work.	Pullonen, P., Tom, J., Matulevičius, R. & Toots, A. (2019). Privacy-enhanced BPMN: Enabling Data Privacy Analysis in Business Process Models. <i>Software and Systems Modeling</i> , 18, 3235–3264.	https://pleak.io/
Achieving GDPR Compliance of BPMN Process Models	Method (patterns/guidance)	No	Identifies GDPR-related privacy constraints and proposes BPMN-oriented design patterns/guidance to integrate such constraints into business process models to support GDPR	Agostinelli, S., Maggi, F.M., Marrella, A. & Sapio, F. (2019). Achieving GDPR Compliance of BPMN Process Models. In CAiSE 2019 Workshops, LNBIP 350, 10–22. Springer.	https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-030-21297-1_2

			compliance by design.		
UML + OCL GDPR compliance modelling	Method	No	Models GDPR requirements in Unified Modeling Language (UML) and expresses compliance conditions using Object Constraint Language (OCL), enabling automated checking over design artefacts.	Torre, D., Alferes, M., Soltana, G., Sabetzadeh, M. & Briand, L. (2021). Modeling Data Protection and Privacy: Application and Experience with GDPR. <i>Software and Systems Modeling</i> , 20, 2071–2087.	https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10270-021-00935-5
LINDDUN privacy threat modelling	Method	No	Systematic privacy threat elicitation methodology using Data Flow Diagrams (DFDs) and explicit privacy threat categories (LINDDUN) to derive privacy requirements early in design.	Deng, M., Wuyts, K., Scandariato, R., Preneel, B. & Joosen, W. (2011). A Privacy Threat Analysis Framework: Supporting the Elicitation and Fulfillment of Privacy Requirements. <i>Requirements Engineering</i> , 16(1), 3–32.	https://doi.org/10.1007/s00766-010-0115-7
Process Mining for Python (PM4Py)	Tool	No	Python process-mining library supporting process discovery and conformance checking from event logs; useful for operational monitoring pipelines.	Berti, A., van Zelst, S.J. & van der Aalst, W.M.P. (2019). Process Mining for Python (PM4Py): Bridging the Gap Between Process-and Data-Science. In <i>ICPM Demo Track</i> , CEUR 2374.	https://github.com/process-intelligence-solutions/pm4py

D2.2 Survey of Compliance Methods and Tools

Declare (declarative process constraints)	Method	No	Declarative approach for expressing temporal constraints over activity executions; used when processes are flexible and compliance is expressed as trace constraints.	Pešić, M. & van der Aalst, W.M.P. (2006). A Declarative Approach for Flexible Business Process Management. In BPM Workshops, LNCS 4103. Springer.	https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/11837862_18
SPIN model checker	Tool	No	Model checker supporting verification of behavioural properties expressed in Linear Temporal Logic (LTL) via exhaustive state-space exploration.	Holzmann, G.J. (2003). The SPIN Model Checker: Primer and Reference Manual. Addison-Wesley.	https://spinroot.com/spin/Doc/Book_extra/s/
NuSMV 2	Tool	No	Symbolic model checker (NuSMV 2) supporting branching-time temporal properties such as Computation Tree Logic (CTL) for verification of system models.	Cimatti, A., Clarke, E.M., Giunchiglia, E., Giunchiglia, F., Pistore, M., Roveri, M., Sebastiani, R. & Tacchella, A. (2002). NuSMV 2: An OpenSource Tool for Symbolic Model Checking. In CAV 2002, LNCS 2404, 359–364. Springer.	https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/3-540-45657-0_29

3. Normative reasoning tools and methods

Normative reasoning tools and methods					
Name	Tool or method?	Proprietary?	Description or comment	Reference	URL
LogiKEy framework (Isabelle/HOL embeddings for deontic and normative reasoning)	Framework + tool support	No	Framework and methodology for designing normative theories using semantic embeddings in Isabelle / Higher-Order Logic (HOL); supports experimentation with deontic logics and domain theories using theorem proving and model finding.	Benzmüller, C., Parent, X. & van der Torre, L. (2020). Designing normative theories for ethical and legal reasoning: LogiKEy framework, methodology, and tool support. <i>Artificial Intelligence</i> , 287, 103348; Benzmüller, C., Parent, X. & van der Torre, L. (2018). A Deontic Logic Reasoning Infrastructure. <i>CiE 2018, LNCS 10936</i> , 60–69.	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0004370219301110
SPINdle (defeasible logic reasoner)	Tool	No	Open-source Java reasoner for defeasible logic (including modal extensions) used to compute conclusions/violations from defeasible rule bases and priorities.	Lam, H.P. & Governatori, G. (2009). The Making of SPINdle. In <i>RuleML 2009, LNCS 5858</i> , 315–322. Springer.	https://sourceforge.net/projects/spindlereasoner/
Defeasible Logic Programming (DeLP) GDPR compliance	Method/system	No	Practical GDPR compliance modelling approach using Defeasible Logic Programming (DeLP),	Azam, N., Chak, A., Michala, A., Ansari, S. & Truong, N.B. (2025). A Practical Solution for Modelling GDPR-Compliance	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0957417425007626

reasoning system			including contradiction handling and explicit priorities to mitigate undecided outcomes in compliance queries.	Based on Defeasible Logic Reasoning. Expert Systems with Applications, 277, 127140.	
clingo (Answer Set Programming solver)	Tool	No	Answer Set Programming (ASP) solver used as an execution engine for non-monotonic norm encodings with exceptions/overrides; supports grounded solving and control for evolving programs.	Gebser, M., Kaminski, R., Kaufmann, B. & Schaub, T. (2019). Multi-shot ASP solving with clingo. Theory and Practice of Logic Programming, 19(1), 27–82.	https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/theory-and-practice-of-logic-programming/article/multishot-asp-solving-with-clingo/FAED3429900D84CDD5155326A36548F2
Temporal deontic action logic for compliance verification in Answer Set Programming	Method	No	Deontic temporal extension of Answer Set Programming for verifying compliance of business processes to norms including deadlines and contrary-to-duty obligations; solved via ASP reasoning.	Giordano, L., Martelli, A. & Theseider Dupré, D. (2013). Temporal deontic action logic for the verification of compliance to norms in business processes. ICAIL 2013.	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2514601.2514608
Modeling obligations with Event-Calculus (RuleML 2014)	Method	No	Normative modelling of obligations using Event Calculus, representing events and fluents to express time-bounded obligations and evaluate compliance/violations over	Hashmi, M., Governatori, G. & Wynn, M.T. (2014). Modeling Obligations with Event-Calculus. In RuleML 2014, LNCS 8620, 296–310. Springer.	https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-319-09870-8_22

D2.2 Survey of Compliance Methods and Tools

			traces.		
Z3 (Satisfiability Modulo Theories solver)	Tool	No	Satisfiability Modulo Theories (SMT) solver used as back-end for proving/solving logical constraints arising in high-assurance normative reasoning and verification workflows.	de Moura, L. & Bjørner, N. (2008). Z3: An Efficient SMT Solver. In TACAS 2008, LNCS 4963. Springer.	https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-540-78800-3_24

4. Semantic Web tools and methods

Semantic Web tools and methods					
Name	Tool or method?	Proprietary?	Description or comment	Reference	URL
RDF	Method + W3C standard	No	Formal vocabulary to describe and exchange knowledge in the form of a graph.	n.a.	https://www.w3.org/TR/rdf12-concepts/
RDFS	Method + W3C standard	No	Schema and extension of RDF for describing groups of related resources, used to structure RDF data by using classes and properties	n.a.	https://www.w3.org/TR/rdf-schema/
OWL	Method + W3C standard	No	Vocabulary that provides formal semantics for designing ontologies by describing classes, properties, individuals, and data values.	n.a.	https://www.w3.org/TR/owl2-syntax/
SKOS	Method + W3C standard	No	Common data model for sharing and linking knowledge organisation systems via the Web.	n.a.	https://www.w3.org/TR/skos-reference/
ODRL	Method + W3C standard	No	Policy expression language that provides a flexible and interoperable information model, vocabulary, and encoding mechanisms for representing	n.a.	https://www.w3.org/TR/odrl-model/

D2.2 Survey of Compliance Methods and Tools

			statements about the usage of content and services.		
SWRL	Method	No	Expressive OWL-based rule language for the Semantic Web.	n.a.	https://www.w3.org/submissions/SWRL/
SPARQL	Method	No	Semantic query language for RDF databases.	n.a.	https://www.w3.org/TR/sparql11-query/
SHACL	Method	No	Language for validating RDF data.	n.a.	https://www.w3.org/TR/shacl/
RuleML	Method	No	XML-based languages designed to model rules.	Boley, H., Paschke, A., Shafiq, O. (2010). RuleML 1.0: The Overarching Specification of Web Rules. In: Dean, M., Hall, J., Rotolo, A., Tabet, S. (eds) Semantic Web Rules. RuleML 2010. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol 6403. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-16289-3_15	n.a.
LegalRuleML	Method + OASIS standard	No	Extension of RuleML and OASIS markup standard, LegalRuleML is designed specifically for legal norms and reasoning.	Palmirani, M., Governatori, G., Rotolo, A., Tabet, S., Boley, H., & Paschke, A. (2011). LegalRuleML: XML-based rules and norms. In Rule-Based Modeling and Computing on the Semantic Web: 5th International Symposium, RuleML 2011 - America,	n.a.

D2.2 Survey of Compliance Methods and Tools

				Proceedings (pp. 298-312). (Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics); Vol. 7018 LNCS). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-24908-2_30	
Akoma Ntoso	Method + OASIS standard	No	Legal document standard for the specification of parliamentary, legislative, and judicial documents, for their interchange between institutions, and for the creation of a common data and metadata model.	n.a.	https://www.oasis-open.org/standard/akn-v1-0/
LKIF	Method	No	Semantic-Web-based language for representing legal knowledge in order to support modeling of legal domains and to facilitate interchange between legal knowledge-based systems.	Gordon, T.F. (2010). An Overview of the Legal Knowledge Interchange Format. In: Abramowicz, W., Tolksdorf, R., Węcel, K. (eds) Business Information Systems Workshops. BIS 2010. Lecture Notes in Business Information Processing, vol 57. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-15402-7_30	https://www.estrellaproject.org/page_id-4/
ECLI	Standard	No	Standard that provides technical specifications for Web identifiers for laws and	n.a.	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/content/help/eurlex-content/ecli.html

D2.2 Survey of Compliance Methods and Tools

			regulations.		
ELI	Standard	No	Standard that provides technical specifications for Web identifiers for court rulings.	n.a.	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli-register/what_is_eli.html
URN:LEX	Standard	No	A Uniform Resource Name (URN) namespace identifier that identifies, names, assigns, and manages persistent resources in the legal domain, and allows adoption of a common convention by multiple jurisdictions.	Spinosa, P., Francesconi, E., & Lupo, C. (2010). A uniform resource name (URN) namespace for sources of law (LEX).	https://www.ietf.org/rfc/rfc9676.html

5. Ontologies and knowledge representations

Ontologies and knowledge representations					
Name	Tool or method?	Proprietary?	Description or comment	Reference	URL
DOLCE	Method	No	Top-level ontology by the WonderWeb project.	Masolo, C., Borgo, S., Gangemi, A., Guarino, N., & Oltramari, A. (n.d.). WonderWeb Deliverable D18.	https://www.loa.istc.cnr.it/old/Papers/D18.pdf
UFO	Method	No	Top-level ontology.	Guizzardi, G., Botti Benevides, A., Fonseca, C. M., Porello, D., Almeida, J. P. A., & Prince Sales, T. (2022). UFO: Unified foundational ontology. Applied ontology, 17(1), 167-210.	n.a.
UFO-L	Method	No	Legal core ontology based on UFO.	Griffo, C. (2015). Ufo-l: A core ontology of legal concepts built from a legal relations perspective. Doctoral Consortium Contributions, IC3K-KEOD.	n.a.
FOLaw	Method	No	FOLaw is closer to an epistemological framework than an ontology, concerned with the types of knowledge in legal reasoning rather than with legal knowledge itself.	Valente, A., & Breuker, J. (1994). A functional ontology of law. Towards a global expert system in law, 112-136.	n.a.

D2.2 Survey of Compliance Methods and Tools

LRI-Core ontology	Method based on standard	No	Light and generic core ontology for law.	Breuker, J., & Hoekstra, R. (2004, October). Epistemology and ontology in core ontologies: FOLaw and LRI-Core, two core ontologies for law. In Proceedings of EKAW Workshop on Core ontologies. CEUR.	n.a.
CLO	Method	No	Specialisation of an extension of DOLCE, the Descriptions and Situations ontology.	Gangemi, A., Sagri, M. T., & Tiscornia, D. (2005). A Constructive Framework for Legal Ontologies (pp. 97–124). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-32253-5_7	n.a.
LKIF-Core	Method	No	Core ontology for law developed by the ESTRELLA Project, based on OWL-DL and SWRL.	hoekstra 2007	n.a.
GDPRov	Method	No	GDPR-specific ontology designed to represent processes.	Pandit, H. J., O’Sullivan, D., & Lewis, D. (2019). Test-Driven Approach Towards GDPR Compliance. In M. Acosta, P. Cudré-Mauroux, M. Maleshkova, T. Pellegrini, H. Sack, & Y. Sure-Vetter (Eds.), Semantic Systems. The Power of AI and Knowledge Graphs (pp. 19–33). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-33220-4_2	https://www.w3.org/community/dpvcg/wiki/GDPRov

D2.2 Survey of Compliance Methods and Tools

GDPRtEXT	Method	No	GDPR-specific ontology designed to represent the GDPR text.	Pandit, H. J., Fatema, K., O'Sullivan, D., & Lewis, D. (2018). GDPRtEXT - GDPR as a Linked Data Resource. In A. Gangemi, R. Navigli, M.-E. Vidal, P. Hitzler, R. Troncy, L. Hollink, A. Tordai, & M. Alam (Eds.), <i>The Semantic Web</i> (pp. 481–495). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-93417-4_31	https://openscience.adaptcentre.ie/ontologies/GDPRtEXT/deliverables/docs/ontology
GConsent	Method	No	GDPR-specific ontology designed to represent consent.	Pandit, H. J., O'Sullivan, D., & Lewis, D. (2019). Test-Driven Approach Towards GDPR Compliance. In M. Acosta, P. Cudré-Mauroux, M. Maleshkova, T. Pellegrini, H. Sack, & Y. Sure-Vetter (Eds.), <i>Semantic Systems. The Power of AI and Knowledge Graphs</i> (pp. 19–33). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-33220-4_2	https://openscience.adaptcentre.ie/ontologies/GConsent/docs/ontology

D2.2 Survey of Compliance Methods and Tools

PrOnto	Method	No	Ontology using defeasible deontic operators to model legal norms from the GDPR.	Palmirani, M., Martoni, M., Rossi, A., Bartolini, C., & Robaldo, L. (2018, July). Pronto: Privacy ontology for legal reasoning. In International Conference on Electronic Government and the Information Systems Perspective (pp. 139-152). Cham: Springer International Publishing.	n.a.
PrivOnto	Method	No	Semantic framework developed under the Usable Privacy Policy (UPP) project and used for the analysis of privacy policies.	Oltramari, A., Piraviperumal, D., Schaub, F., Wilson, S., Cherivirala, S., Norton, T. B., ... & Sadeh, N. (2018). PrivOnto: a semantic framework for the analysis of privacy policies. Semantic Web, 9(2), 185-203.	n.a.
PROV-O	Method + W3C standard	No	The Provenance Ontology provides a set of classes, properties, and restrictions that can be used to represent and interchange provenance information generated in different systems and under different contexts	Lebo, T., Sahoo, S., McGuinness, D., Belhajjame, K., Cheney, J., Corsar, D., ... & Zhao, J. (2013). Prov-o: The prov ontology.	https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-o/
Linked Data Rights Ontology	Method aligned with W3C standards	No	Extension of the ODRL ontology developed by UPM that provides the vocabulary for modelling the conditions of use of the Linked Data resources	n.a.	https://oeg-upm.github.io/vocabUpdates/site/ontologies/purl.orgNETldrns.html

D2.2 Survey of Compliance Methods and Tools

DALOS ontology	Method	No	Ontology of consumer law developed by the European Commission DALOS project.	Francesconi, E., Spinosa, P. L., & Tiscornia, D. (2007). A Linguistic-ontological Support for Multilingual Legislative Drafting: the DALOS Project. In LOAIT (pp. 103-111).	n.a.
JurWordNet	Method	No	Ontology-driven semantic lexicon, designed as an extension of the Italian version of EuroWordNet and used for semantic tagging and information retrieval.	Sagri, M. T., Tiscornia, D., & Bertagna, F. (2004). Jur-wordnet. In Proceedings of the 2nd International Global Wordnet Conference (pp. 305-310).	n.a.
EUROVOC	Method	No	Controlled vocabulary, multilingual and multidisciplinary thesaurus managed by the Publications Office of the European Union.	n.a.	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/browse/eurvoc.html?locale=fr
ELTS	Method	No	The European Legal Taxonomy Syllabus multi-lingual and multi-jurisdictional vocabulary used to model the legal terminology created by the Uniform Terminology project on EU consumer protection law.	Ajani, G., Boella, G., Di Caro, L., Robaldo, L., Humphreys, L., Praduroux, S., ... & Violato, A. (2017). The European legal taxonomy syllabus: a multi-lingual, multi-level ontology framework to untangle the web of European legal terminology. Applied Ontology, 11(4), 325-375.	n.a.
ELI ontology	Method based on standard	No	Ontology based on the ELI standard that defines a common data model for exchanging legislation metadata on the web.	n.a.	https://op.europa.eu/en/web/eu-vocabularies/eli

D2.2 Survey of Compliance Methods and Tools

Akoma Ntoso ontology	Method based on standard	No	The AKN ontology is part of the Akoma Ntoso standard and covers the core set of data elements needed for the effective management and retrieval of official parliamentary, legislative and judiciary information.	n.a.	http://akomantoso.info/?page_id=39
Data Privacy Vocabulary	Method	No	Taxonomical modelling of concepts associated with personal data processing based on the GDPR.	J. Pandit, H., Esteves, B., P. Krog, G., Ryan, P., Golpayegani, D., & Flake, J. (2025). Data Privacy Vocabulary (DPV) – Version 2.0. In G. Demartini, K. Hose, M. Acosta, M. Palmonari, G. Cheng, H. Skaf-Molli, N. Ferranti, D. Hernández, & A. Hogan (Eds.), The Semantic Web – ISWC 2024 (Vol. 15233, pp. 171–193). Springer Nature Switzerland. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-77847-6_10	https://w3c.github.io/dpv/2.2/dpv/

6. NLP tools and methods

NLP tools and methods					
Name	Tool or method?	Proprietary?	Description or comment	Reference	URL
LexNLP	Tool	No	<p>Python library designed for legal/regulatory text.</p> <p>Includes functionality to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Segment documents • Identify key text (e.g. titles and section headings) • Extract types of structured information (e.g. distances and dates) • Extract named entities (e.g. companies and geopolitical entities) • Transform text into features for model training • Build unsupervised and supervised models (e.g. word embedding or tagging models) 	n.a.	https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1806.03688

7. Legal Document Summarization tools and methods

Legal Document Summarization tools and methods					
Name	Tool or method?	Proprietary?	Description or comment	Reference	URL
Casesummarizer	Tool	No	Tool for automated text summarization of legal documents which uses standard summary methods based on word frequency augmented with additional domain-specific knowledge. Summaries are then provided through an informative interface with abbreviations, significance heat maps, and other flexible controls. It is evaluated using ROUGE and human scoring against several other summarization systems, including summary text and feedback provided by domain experts.	Polsley, S., Jhunjunwala, P., & Huang, R. (2016, December). Casesummarizer: a system for automated summarization of legal texts. In Proceedings of COLING 2016, the 26th international conference on Computational Linguistics: System Demonstrations (pp. 258-262).	n.a.
(Nguyen et al., 2021)	Method	No	Reinforcement learning to train current deep summarization models to improve their performance in the legal domain through proximal policy optimization methods and introduce novel reward functions that encourage the generation of candidate summaries satisfying both lexical and semantic criteria.	Nguyen, D. H., Nguyen, B. S., Nghiem, N. V. D., Le, D. T., Khatun, M. A., Nguyen, M. T., & Le, H. (2021, December). Robust deep reinforcement learning for extractive legal summarization. In International Conference on Neural Information Processing (pp. 597-604). Cham: Springer International Publishing.	n.a.

8. NER tools and methods

NER tools and methods					
Name	Tool or method?	Proprietary?	Description or comment	Reference	URL
(Dozier et al., 2010)	Method	No	Named entity recognition and resolution in legal documents (such as US case law, depositions, and pleadings and other trial), using lookup, context rules, and statistical models	Dozier, C., Kondadadi, R., Light, M., Vachher, A., Veeramachaneni, S., & Wudali, R. (2010). Named entity recognition and resolution in legal text. In Semantic processing of legal texts: where the language of law meets the law of language (pp. 27-43). Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg.	n.a.
(Păis et al., 2021)	Method	No	Named entity recognition system for the Romanian legal domain. The system makes use of the gold annotated LegalNERo corpus. Furthermore, the system combines Bi-LSTM and Conditional Random Fields (CRF) with pre-trained word and character embeddings, legal gazetteers, and ensemble evaluations to improve accuracy.	Păiș, V., Mitrofan, M., Gasan, C. L., Coneschi, V., & Ianov, A. (2021, November). Named entity recognition in the Romanian legal domain. In Proceedings of the natural legal language processing workshop 2021 (pp. 9-18).	n.a.

D2.2 Survey of Compliance Methods and Tools

(Smădu et al., 2022)	Method	No	Cross-lingual domain adaptation using BERT, Bi-LSTM, and CRF layers, employing adversarial learning via a gradient reversal mechanism to reduce domain bias, with mixed results across German and Romanian data.	Smădu, R. A., Dinică, I. R., Avram, A. M., Cercel, D. C., Pop, F., & Cercel, M. C. (2022, December). Legal named entity recognition with multi-task domain adaptation. In Proceedings of the Natural Legal Language Processing Workshop 2022 (pp. 305-321).	n.a.
Kensho NERD	Tool	Yes	"Identify companies, organizations, people, places and events in text and connect them to rich knowledge bases." "Kensho NERD can be employed to analyse contracts, flag potential risks, identify non-compliance issues, and ensure adherence to legal requirements."	n.a.	https://blog.kensho.com/the-power-of-nlp-for-legal-and-compliance-3a1f4a537a83 https://kensho.com/nerd

9. Text Mining and Legal Information Retrieval tools and methods

Text Mining and Legal Information Retrieval tools and methods					
Name	Tool or method?	Proprietary?	Description or comment	Reference	URL
Luminance	Tool	Yes	Platform designed to "streamline and enhance compliance to monitor and meet compliance requirements as soon as they're introduced"	n.a.	https://www.luminance.com/ https://www.luminance.com/comply/ https://luminance.com/wp-content/uploads/2025/10/A-Guide-to-AI-for-Compliance.pdf?utm_medium=email&_hsmi=114740112&utm_content=114740112&utm_source=hs_automation
Kensho NERD	Tool	Yes	<p>"Identify companies, organizations, people, places and events in text and connect them to rich knowledge bases."</p> <p>"Kensho NERD can be employed to analyse contracts, flag potential risks, identify non-compliance issues, and ensure adherence to legal requirements."</p>	n.a.	https://blog.kensho.com/the-power-of-nlp-for-legal-and-compliance-3a1f4a537a83 https://kensho.com/nerd

D2.2 Survey of Compliance Methods and Tools

OneTrust	Tool	Yes	"Compliance requires classifying AI systems by risk level, performing impact assessments, maintaining documentation, and continuously monitoring AI use. OneTrust automates this with out-of-the-box assessments, regulatory updates, and policy enforcement to meet evolving requirements."	n.a.	https://www.onetrust.com/solutions/ai-governance/ https://www.onetrust.com/content/dam/onetrust/brand/content/asset/white-paper/ot-operationalizing-ai-governance-white-paper/ot-operationalizing-ai-governance-white-paper.pdf
Gaius T	Tool	No	Tool based on the Cerno framework designed for the automatic extraction of rights and obligations from regulatory compliance	Kiyavitskaya, N. <i>et al.</i> (2008). Automating the Extraction of Rights and Obligations for Regulatory Compliance. In: Li, Q., Spaccapietra, S., Yu, E., Olivé, A. (eds) Conceptual Modeling - ER 2008. ER 2008. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol 5231. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-87877-3_13	n.a.
(Orlando & Santoro, 2025)	Method	No	XAI pipeline combining legal-domain NLP preprocessing, keyness statistics, WordNet-based semantic graphs, and Structural	Orlando, A., & Santoro, M. (2025). A semantic approach to understanding GDPR fines: From text to compliance insights. <i>Computer Law & Security</i>	n.a.

D2.2 Survey of Compliance Methods and Tools

			Topic Model (STM) (Roberts et al., 2014) over 1,900+ GDPR fine summaries	Review, 59, 106187.	
(Dragoni et al., 2016)	Method	No	Hybrid NLP (ontologies and statistical parsing) pipeline for extracting machine-readable deontic rules (obligations, permissions, prohibitions) from legal texts to enable automated compliance checking	Dragoni, M., Villata, S., Rizzi, W., & Governatori, G. (2016). Combining NLP approaches for rule extraction from legal documents. In 1st Workshop on Mining and REasoning with Legal texts (MIREL 2016).	n.a.

10. Generative AI tools and methods

Generative AI tools and methods					
Name	Tool or method?	Proprietary?	Description or comment	Reference	URL
CO2 (Co-Compliance Officer)	Method	No	LLM-Based Ontology-Driven Methodology for Generating Knowledge Graphs and AI Compliance Checking	Turaga, V. S. P., Pahi, T., Tjoa, S., Siami-Namini, S., & Namin, A. S. (2025). CO2 (Co-Compliance Officer): An LLM-Based Ontology-Driven methodology for generating knowledge graphs and AI compliance checking. IEEE Access, 13, 210576- 210606. DOI: 10.1109/ACCESS.2025.3639228	n.a.
LEGAL-BERT	Tool	No	Family of BERT models for the legal domain, intended to assist legal NLP research, computational law, and legal technology applications.	Chalkidis, I., Fergadiotis, M., Malakasiotis, P., Aletras, N., & Androutsopoulos, I. (2020). LEGAL-BERT: The muppets straight out of law school. arXiv preprint arXiv:2010.02559.	n.a.
XTRAREG	Method	No	Method using LLMs and RAG to provide automated assistance in extracting privacy requirements from predefined legal sources.	Abualhaija, S., Ceci, M., Sannier, N., Bianculli, D., Lannier, S., Siclari, M., ... & Tosza, S. (2025, September). LLM-assisted extraction of regulatory requirements: A case study on the GDPR. In 2025 IEEE 33rd International Requirements Engineering Conference (RE) (pp. 142-154). IEEE.	n.a.

D2.2 Survey of Compliance Methods and Tools

MISSION KI Compliance Monitor	Tool	No	Specialized LLM designed for legal compliance applications. It is finetuned from the Llama-3-70B-Instruct model using a custom legal cases dataset to understand more complex contexts and achieve precise results when analysing complex legal issues.	n.a.	https://huggingface.co/ACATECH/ncos
Chat-EUR-Lex	Method	No	Method integrating Chat LLMs and RAG to access a datasets of legal acts in English and Italian, with interaction through a chatbot	Cherubini, M., Romano, F., Bolioli, A., De Mattei, L., & Sangermano, M. (2024, May). Improving the accessibility of EU laws: the Chat-EUR-Lex project. In Ital-IA (pp. 54-59).	n.a.
Privacy Policy Compliance Verification Knowledge Graph (PrivComp-KG)	Method	No	Combination of LLMs and Semantic Web: a knowledge graph stores information about privacy policies, regulatory frameworks and domain-specific legal knowledge, which can then be retrieved by an LLM.	Garza, L., Elluri, L., Piplai, A., Kotal, A., Gupta, D., & Joshi, A. (2024, October). PrivComp-KG: Leveraging KG and LLM for compliance verification. In 2024 IEEE 6th International Conference on Trust, Privacy and Security in Intelligent Systems, and Applications (TPS-ISA) (pp. 97-106). IEEE.	n.a.
(Hassani, 2024)	Method	No	LLMs for automated extraction of requirement-related legal content.	Hassani, S. (2024, June). Enhancing legal compliance and regulation analysis with large language models. In 2024 IEEE 32nd International Requirements Engineering Conference (RE) (pp. 507-511). IEEE.	n.a.

D2.2 Survey of Compliance Methods and Tools

(Dal Pont et al., 2025)	Method	No	LLMs and classical NLP for the identification and structuring of obligations.	Dal Pont, T., Galli, F., Sartor, G., & Contissa, G. (2025, June). "Lost in EU Regulation? Don't Worry, AI Found the Obligation" Extracting and Representing Legal Obligations in the GDPR, the DSA and the AI Act. In Proceedings of the Twentieth International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Law (pp. 129-138).	n.a.
LexGuide Framework	Method	No	LexGuide framework, leveraging RAG with hierarchical topic organisation to structure dialogue progression, ensuring both comprehensive coverage of legal aspects and coherence across conversational turns. Using EUDial, proactive multi-turn dialogue dataset constructed from 204 blogs curated by the Citizens' Enquiries Unit (AsKEP) of the European Parliamentary Research Service.	Chouhan, A., & Gertz, M. (2025). From Answers to Guidance: A Proactive Dialogue System for Legal Documents. arXiv preprint arXiv:2510.19723.	n.a.

11. Machine Learning tools and methods

Machine Learning tools and methods					
Name	Tool or method?	Proprietary?	Description or comment	Reference	URL
(Kingston, 2017)	Method	No	ML (alongside rule-based) systems to detect data breaches for GDPR	Kingston, J. (2017). Using artificial intelligence to support compliance with the general data protection regulation. <i>Artificial Intelligence and Law</i> , 25(4), 429-443.	n.a.